

D2.1 - ANALYSIS OF PRE-NORMATIVE RESEARCH FOR NEW BUILDING MATERIALS

Project: Agile and Flexible Construction Materials Standardization for Boosting the Twin Transition

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1. Introduction to the document goals and organization of the work

This document constitutes the main outcome of the WP2 of the AFCOS project. It describes the analysis of pre-normative research for new building products.

In this chapter, the organization of the work is described, paying attention to the main decisions taken while planning the activities.

1.1. Definitions

First, some relevant definitions have been shared among the partners of the project. These definitions have been introduced to avoid misunderstandings and are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Relevant definitions.

ITEM	DEFINITION
Construction product	<p>We suggest developing all the project documents using the definition of «construction product» provided by the REGULATION (EU) No 305/2011 (CPR):</p> <p><i>‘Construction product’ means any product or kit which is produced and placed on the market for incorporation in a permanent manner in construction works or parts thereof and the performance of which has an effect on the performance of the construction works with respect to the basic requirements for construction works.</i></p> <p>“Construction materials” is typically used in less technical, descriptive documents. Within this project, it will be always replaced by “construction products”.</p>
New or innovative construction product	We use «new/innovative construction product» instead of «new/innovative construction material», by meaning product which is not fully covered by existing standards and/or regulations.
Standardization or normative context	Context defined by all (voluntary, in itself) standards applicable
Legislative context	<p>Context defined by all legal provisions (EU/member states).</p> <p>Notes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By technical rules or regulations, we always mean «legal provisions», which can often refer to standards, putting them into force. <p>Distinction between legislative and normative contexts is then simply given by presence/absence of legally binding provisions in force (international, national, regional)</p>

1.2. WP2 goals

According to the AFCOS project Grant Agreement, the WP2 aimed to design and implement pre-normative research under three different pillars:

1. legislative framework,
2. standardization framework,
3. market framework.

In all three pillars, the main objectives are:

- to understand how standardization of new building products relates to the aspects of the twin transition of the construction sector;
- to understand if the different pillars are enablers or barriers.

The final objective of the WP2 is then to analyze the research results and define pre-normative requirements for standards to boost the twin transition.

1.3. WP2 organization

The work of WP2 is organized in the following sub-tasks.

- Task 2.1. Creation of multistakeholder research group
- Task 2.2. Legislative context – research on European legislation
- Task 2.3. Standardization context – research on existing standards
- Task 2.4. Market context – research on industrial needs for standardization of new building materials
- Task 2.5. Production of analysis of pre-normative approach for new building materials

The task 2.1 is responsible for the organization of the main activities of the WP2. The main decisions taken under this task are those described in this chapter. The main purpose of this task is to create the multistakeholder research groups which are in charge of completing the tasks under WP2.

The main WP2 activities are then performed within the 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4 tasks, and will be described in the following chapters. The activities of these tasks have been performed with the help of the formed multistakeholder research groups.

The final task 2.5 is dedicated to analyzing the results coming from previous tasks, producing the current document.

Within task 2.1, the activities have been organized according to the following sub-tasks.

1. Design phase: identify product families, stakeholders and markets to be investigated.
2. Pre-engagement of stakeholders.
3. Implementation (set up the groups and the IT tools).

1.4. Design phase: stakeholder families

To form meaningful multistakeholder research groups, two types of stakeholders have been identified according to their competences.

- **Category-expert stakeholders.** Their role is to help identifying the obstacles of new construction products of a given category in the legislative, normative and market contexts. In this framework, it is fundamental to identify **categories** common to the three pillars. This requires also identifying product groups. For this project's purposes, in the formation of product categories, special attention is given to products mostly connected with innovation (and more specifically with sustainable and digital innovation).
- **Transversal-expertise stakeholders.** They can help to identify problems in one or more contexts (legal, standardization, market) which are transversal to all the product categories (e.g. building designers). Transversal-expertise stakeholders are experts of one or more contexts (legislative, standardization, market) without focus on a specific product category. In Table 2, the description of some of these stakeholders is provided.

Table 2. Description of some of the transversal-expertise stakeholders

TRANSVERSAL-EXPERTISE STAKEHOLDERS		
Area	Description	List
Certification	Stakeholders involved in the certification activities, CE marking, ...	EOTA members, accreditation bodies (BG, RO), notified bodies for inspection, verification and certification of construction products
Building voluntary certifications	Variety of stakeholders from the sustainable building area	LEED, BREEAM, DGND, etc.
EPD	Variety of stakeholders active in the field of EPD	Local Program Operators, representatives from ECOPlatform or EcoInvent
CEN / CENELEC	Members of Technical Committees (TC)	TC involved for hENs on construction products
Software	Stakeholders active in the software for digitalization of buildings	IFC standard setter (focus on products), BIM, BuildingSmart, representatives from the main LCA software houses
Public procurement	Experts belonging to public administration	Experts from national public or from EU agencies
Designers	National associations/charters of engineers and architects	Representatives from national charters, especially belonging to relevant working groups

Figure 1 and Figure 2 provide a schematic view of the stakeholder organization.

Figure 1. Schematic view of the stakeholder organization (I)

Category (competence / expertise areas)	Legislative context	Normative context	Market context
Category 1			
Category 2			
...			
Category N			

Figure 2. Schematic view of the stakeholder organization (II)

1.5. Design phase: product categories

Within this project's framework, the idea was to **identify two product categories** to be used as an example. In order to cover the maximum spectrum of products, we started our work by classifying construction products. Classification can be made, for instance:

- by product material characteristics (ex. cement, steel, wood, glass, ...),
- by product function in the construction (ex. transparent building façade, insulating cladding, ...).

Some classification approaches are listed in the following:

1. CPR product areas
2. CEN technical committees
3. Central Product Classification (CPC) by UNSD
4. EPD classification
5. LCA classification
6. LEVEL(S)

These approaches are analyzed in detail in the following.

1.5.1. Classification based on CPR product areas

Products can be classified based on CPR product areas, as it is defined in the Annex IV of CPR. This is probably the best approach, because is based on main EU level regulation in the field.

According to CPR, the product groups are 25, which are too much for this project. Therefore, a grouping method is proposed, as it is shown in Table 3. We proposed 7 different product groups, but the last one (group n. 7) should be omitted because it includes products which are not of interest for buildings. So, in the end, the remaining product groups are 6.

Table 3. Product classification based on CPR product areas.

Product group	CPR Classes
1 Concrete products and similar	1 Precast normal/lightweight/autoclaved aerated concrete products.
	15 Cement, building limes and other hydraulic binders.
	24 Aggregates.
	26 Products related to concrete, mortar and grout.
2 Building	2 Doors, windows, shutters, gates and related building hardware.

envelope and internal partitions	4	Thermal insulation products. Composite insulating kits/systems.
	7	Gypsum products.
	9	Curtain walling/cladding/structural sealant glazing.
	19	Floorings.
	21	Internal & external wall and ceiling finishes. Internal partition kits.
	22	Roof coverings, roof lights, roof windows, and ancillary products. Roof kits.
	30	Flat glass, profiled glass and glass block products.
3 Structural products	5	Structural bearings. Pins for structural joints.
	13	Structural timber products/elements and ancillaries.
	14	Wood based panels and elements.
	16	Reinforcing and prestressing steel for concrete (and ancillaries). Post tensioning kits.
	17	Masonry and related products. Masonry units, mortars, and ancillaries.
	20	Structural metallic products and ancillaries.
	33	Fixings.
4 Systems products	6	Chimneys, flues and specific products.
	10	Fixed fire fighting equipment (fire alarm/detection, fixed firefighting, fire and smoke control and explosion suppression product).
	27	Space heating appliances.
	28	Pipes-tanks and ancillaries not in contact with water intended for human consumption.
	31	Power, control and communication cables.
5 Chemicals and plastics	3	Membranes, including liquid applied and kits (for water and/or water vapour control).
	8	Geotextiles, geomembranes, and related products.
	25	Construction adhesives.
	32	Sealants for joints.
6 Water engineering products	35	Fire stopping, fire sealing and fire protective products. Fire retardant products.
	11	Sanitary appliances.
	18	Waste water engineering products.
7 Other	29	Construction products in contact with water intended for human consumption.
	12	Circulation fixtures: road equipment.
	23	Road construction products.

1.5.2. Classification based on CEN work area «Constructions»

Another chance is to perform classification based on CEN work area «Constructions». This approach is interesting also in connection with WP5 activities, where we need to involve technical committees. Also in this case, the number of categories is too large (68 items). Therefore, it is necessary to group the different technical committees in different product groups. This is shown in Table 4. We used in this case the same 6 categories identified in the previous approach based on CPR product areas. In this case, we omitted to report some technical committees, because their activity is not relevant for the purpose of this project. Here we report also a final general category, where we list a few of technical committees whose interest can be transversal to all the products.

Table 4. Product classification based on CEN work area “Construction”.

Product group	CEN TECHNICAL COMMITTEES
1 Concrete products and similar	CEN/TC 51 - Cement and building limes
	CEN/TC 104 - Concrete and related products
	CEN/TC 154 - Aggregates
	CEN/TC 177 - Prefabricated reinforced components of autoclaved aerated concrete or light-weight aggregate concrete with open structure
	CEN/TC 229 - Precast concrete products
	CEN/TC 336 - Bituminous binders
2 Building envelope and internal partitions	CEN/TC 33 - Doors, windows, shutters, building hardware and curtain walling
	CEN/TC 38 - Durability of wood and wood-based products
	CEN/TC 67 - Ceramic tiles
	CEN/TC 88 - Thermal insulating materials and products
	CEN/TC 99 - Wallcoverings
	CEN/TC 128 - Roof covering products for discontinuous laying and products for wall cladding
	CEN/TC 129 - Glass in building
	CEN/TC 134 - Resilient, textile and laminate floor coverings
	CEN/TC 178 - Paving units and kerbs
	CEN/TC 241 - Gypsum and gypsum based products
	CEN/TC 277 - Suspended ceilings
CEN/TC 303 - Floor screeds and screed materials	
3 Structural products	CEN/TC 112 - Wood-based panels
	CEN/TC 124 - Timber structures
	CEN/TC 125 - Masonry
	CEN/TC 135 - Execution of steel structures and aluminium structures

	CEN/TC 167 - Structural bearings
	CEN/TC 175 - Round and sawn timber
	CEN/TC 203 - Cast iron pipes, fittings and their joints
	CEN/TC 250 - Structural Eurocodes
4 Systems products	CEN/TC 50 - Lighting columns and spigots
	CEN/TC 89 - Thermal performance of buildings and building components
	CEN/TC 126 - Acoustic properties of building elements and of buildings
	CEN/TC 127 - Fire safety in buildings
	CEN/TC 156 - Ventilation for buildings
	CEN/TC 169 - Light and lighting
	CEN/TC 191 - Fixed firefighting systems
	CEN/TC 247 - Building Automation, Controls and Building Management
5 Chemicals and plastics	CEN/TC 155 - Plastics piping systems and ducting systems
	CEN/TC 166 - Chimneys
	CEN/TC 185 - Fasteners
	CEN/TC 208 - Elastomeric seals for joints in pipework and pipelines
	CEN/TC 297 - Free-standing industrial chimneys
	CEN/TC 349 - Sealants for joints in building construction
	CEN/TC 351 - Construction Products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances
	CEN/TC 361 - Polymer modified bituminous thick coatings for waterproofing Definitions/requirements and test methods
6 Water engineering products	CEN/TC 165 - Waste water engineering
	CEN/TC 228 - Heating systems and water based cooling systems in buildings
	CEN/TC 254 - Flexible sheets for waterproofing
	CEN/TC 163 - Sanitary appliances
Transversal categories	CEN/TC 350 - Sustainability of construction works
	CEN/TC 371 - Energy performance of buildings
	CEN/TC 442 - Building Information Modelling (BIM)

1.5.3. Classification based on Central Product Classification (CPC) by UNSD

Another proposed classification approach is based on [Central Product Classification \(CPC\) by UNSD](#). However, in the field «Constructions» this classification identifies mostly services and not products (which are at the core of this project). So, for our purposes this appears not to be the best classification approach, and it is not recommended.

1.5.4. Classification based on EPD

This approach would be interesting, because it is related to one of the most widely used declarations in the field of product environmental sustainability, which is very much related to the purpose of this project. However, no standard categories are defined in international standards ruling EPD for construction products. Therefore, also this approach is not recommended.

1.5.5. Classification based on LCA

Similarly to the previous one, also an approach based on the building LCA would be interesting, because it is very much related to the purpose of this project. However, similarly to EPD, no standard categories are defined in international standards ruling LCA for buildings. Therefore, also this approach is not recommended.

1.5.6. Classification based Level(s)

Level(s) is common framework of indicators developed by EU for sustainable buildings. This approach is focused on life cycle and on buildings, that is the final destination of construction products. However, we do not recommend it because it preserves the grouping of very different products within the same types of building elements (e.g., insulation, finishes, structure,...). This is not aligned with the purpose of this project, which is mainly on products.

1.5.7. Classification approach: our proposal

Our proposal is to use categorization approach in grouping shown for nr. 1 (based on CPR) and 2 (based on CEN technical committees). They are very similar: consider that the identified product groups are the same for both the approaches. Therefore, the approach appears to be soundly based.

1.5.8. Product examples

As we previously stated, we propose to choose at least one product for each category, in a way such that all the categories can be properly represented. The proposed products are listed in Table 5.

Table 5. Proposed products.

Product group	PROPOSED PRODUCT(S) / PRODUCT FAMILIES
1 Concrete products and similar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.).
2 Building envelope and internal partitions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope. Photovoltaic products to be integrated into the building envelope.
3 Structural products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products for structural exoskeleton for anti-seismic design and, more generally, for structural reinforcement of existing buildings to upgrade performance to the actual standards
4 Systems products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HVAC management systems: standards for Interoperability of building automation systems
5 Chemicals and plastics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standards for measuring and monitoring Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC) for IAQ
6 Water engineering products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not identified

For the purposes of this project, the idea was to identify just two product families. The selected product families have been the following, which are also highlighted in the previous table:

- **Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.),**
- **Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.**

The choice of these families is mainly related to the fact that they are very different families, able then to cover a broad spectrum of characteristics.

On the one hand, the cement market withstands the entire construction sector. It is a hard-to-abate sector, where the green transition would have a significant impact. However, it is a very difficult sector to change, precisely because of its size but also because of the economic and safety impacts that any changes could bring. It is a sector that moves a extremely large amount of capitals.

On the other hand, the use of bio-based products in building insulation is in the collective imagination one of the easiest ways to achieve a green transition. Nevertheless, it is still an embryonic field, with significant difficulties in expansion due essentially to strong competition from traditional oil- or mineral-based products. It is still an unstructured sector.

In this way, we aim to investigate one big and structured sector that is expected to undergo to significant changes, as well as to a new sector which still must grow and find its final structure.

1.6. Design phase: EU markets

From a standardization point of view, AFCOS project embodies among its partners both the Romanian and the Bulgarian standardization bodies (ASRO and BDS). Similarly, RoGBC and Cleantech partners have strong and structured relationships with industrial partners again in Romania and Bulgaria

For these reasons, the activities under tasks T2.2 and T2.3 (related to the **legislative and standardization studies**) have been mainly focused on the Romanian and Bulgarian markets. Specifically, the work of Bulgarian partners has been mainly focused on the Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products. Similarly, the work of Romanian partner has been mainly devoted to bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

More in general, the activities of task T2.4 (related to market studies) have been expanded also to other EU-level countries.

1.7. Pre-engagement of stakeholders

Stakeholders' engagement has been performed referring to previous contacts of the different project partners. Specific material to promote the participation to the project activities has been prepared. In particular, the aim of this material was to introduce the project and its goals, as well as to underline how the participants to the stakeholder meetings would have had a very significant and recognized role.

1.8. Implementation

Stakeholders' meetings have been organized in different ways, online or in-person, according to the specific needs of the different stakeholders and countries.

1.8.1. Meetings with Bulgarian stakeholders

Two in-person meetings have been organized between Bulgarian project partners and a selected number of Bulgarian stakeholders belonging to the field of Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products. These meetings have been coordinated by the project partner Cleantech Bulgaria.

The two meetings were organized as following.

1. Meeting nr. 1 (March 25th): Introduction to AFCOS project and to the survey;
2. Meeting nr. 2 (May 13th): discussions about survey outcomes and proposed actions.

The two meetings were participated by 5 external stakeholders, representing Bulgarian Association of the Cement Industry, University of Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy , Research Construction Institute , Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works and the company Titan Zlatna Panega Cement.

1.8.2. Meetings with Romanian stakeholders

Two specific meetings have been held with Romanian stakeholders on the 25th and 27th of March. These meetings involved Romanian stakeholders belonging to the Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope and have been coordinated by the project partner ASRO. Among the representatives who took part in the online meetings we can list: Mr. Gabriel Cringeanu – ISOGREEN Thermal Insulation from nature, Dragos Ionita – Sika Romania, Radu Alexandrescu – Details Acoustics, Dacina Silvesan – Simad 2016.

1.8.3. Meetings with EU-level stakeholders (under task 2.4)

Within task T2.4, three one-hour online meetings have been organized for each of the two product groups. The topics of the meetings have been the following:

1. An overview of AFCOS's strategic approach and objectives.
2. A session to discuss challenges and gather insights from your experiences.
3. A collaborative forum to propose solutions and draft recommendations for the European Commission.

Extra one-to-one meetings have been organized in the end of the process, to collect specific recommendations from each of the stakeholders.

In Table 6 and Table 7 we report the lists of the involved stakeholders, for each of the product groups.

Table 6. Lists of the involved stakeholders for the low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products.

LOW CARBON CEMENT AND LOW CARBON CEMENT-BASED PRODUCTS (CONCRETE, MORTAR, GROUT, ETC.)					
Nr.	Company	Country	Description	Website	Contact person
1a	Alliance for Low Carbon Cement and Concrete (ALCCC)	Intern.	Association aiming to shape the policy, legislative, standardization, and financing foundations necessary to make low-carbon cement and concrete the norm.	https://alliancelccc.com/	Joren Verschaeve - <i>Coordinator</i>
1b	Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)	Intern.	International NGO with a network of members and experts advocating for environmentally friendly technical standards, policies, and laws.	https://ecostandard.org/	Joren Verschaeve - <i>Senior Programme Manager</i>
2	Fortera Europe	France	Materials technology company paving the way to zero CO2 cement	http://www.forteraeurope.com/	Jean-Philippe Vacher - <i>Vice-President Market Strategy</i>
3	ICMQ	Italy	Certification institute	https://www.icmq.it/	Igor Menicatti - <i>Product certification manager</i> Manuel Mari - <i>Sustainable product certification manager</i>
4	IBIMI (Building Smart Italian Chapter)	Italy	International organization that aims to improve the exchange of information between software applications used in the construction industry	https://www.buildingsmartitalia.org/	Anna Moreno - <i>Head of International Affairs and Sustainability at IBIMI, President of the forum of the European chapters of</i>

					<i>buildingSMART international</i>
5	Federbeton	Italia	Italian trade federation of the cement, concrete, basic materials, building products, components and structures supply chain.	https://www.federbeton.it/	Roberto Cucitore - <i>Area Tecnologie e Prodotto</i>
6	Betolar Oyi	Finland	Company providing a next-generation building material which enables making concrete without cement.	http://www.betolar.com/	Mirella Lehtiö - <i>Product Approval Engineer</i>
7	C2CA Technologies BV	Netherlands	Company that upcycles waste concrete into sustainable building materials	https://www.c2ca.tech/	Priya(dharshini) Perumal – <i>Chief Scientist</i>

Table 7. Lists of the involved stakeholders for the bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

BIO-BASED PRODUCTS FOR THE INSULATION OF THE BUILDINGS' ENVELOPE					
Nr.	Company	Country	Description	Website	Contact person
1	Central European University	Austria	Consultancy company (public sector) working in the field of life cycle assessment studies	https://www.ceu.edu/	Adel Boumerzoug - <i>Postdoctoral Researcher</i>
2	INDRESMAT SL & INDRESMAT BV	Spain	Company working with energy-saving framing materials for windows and doors	https://www.indresmat.com/	Pablo R. Outón – <i>CEO</i>
3	SIMAD 2016 SRL	Romania	Company working with the distribution of natural thermal insulation, plasters and natural paints produced in Germany.	https://izolatiitermice.eu/	Dacina Silvesan - <i>Manager</i>
4	ISOGREEN	Romania	Company working with cellulose thermal insulation	www.isogreen.eu	Gabriel Cringeanu – <i>General manager</i>
5	Eco Partnersheep Insulation SA & Eco Friendsheep SRL	Romania	Company working with wool insulation	https://ecofriendsheep.eu/	Cristian Mercioniu - <i>Founder and owner</i>
6	ICMQ	Italy	Certification institute	https://www.icmq.it/	Igor Menicatti - <i>Product certification manager</i> Manuel Mari - <i>Sustainable product certification manager</i>
7	Sophia	Italy	Company developing Posidonia bio-based insulation products	https://www.sophiahightech.com/	Antonio Ferrara - <i>R&D Engineer</i>
8	MOGU Srl	Italy	Company engineering materials based on mycelium, the	https://mogu.bio/	Annalisa Moro - <i>EU</i>

			vegetative stage of mushrooms		<i>project manager</i>
9	###	Romania	Company working with sheep wool thermal insulation	###	###

2. Legislative context

In this chapter, a specific analysis of the regulatory framework is performed. This study has been performed within the activities of the Task T2.2.

As already anticipated, within the framework of the AFCOS project, two different product families have been analyzed:

- group A: Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.),
- group B: bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

Specific attention has been put on Bulgarian market for the low carbon cement products and on the Romanian market for the bio-based products.

The work described in this chapter presents a common structure applied to the two product families, each of them focused on a reference market (Bulgaria on the one hand and Romania on the other hand). Clearly, some elements recur when talking about regulations at the European level but differ when talking about references in force at the national level. However, since these are distinct products, there is not full overlap. Therefore, to maintain consistency, it was preferred to report separately the analyses carried out on low carbon cement products referring to the Bulgarian market on the one hand, and on bio-based products referring to the Romanian market on the other hand.

For this reason, this chapter is divided in two separate sections.

- A. Section 2.1 will concentrate on the regulatory framework of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products, with special focus on Bulgaria. Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner TU Sofia.
- B. Section 2.2 will concentrate on the regulatory framework of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope, with special focus on Romania. Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner ASRO.

Each of the sections is organized with the following structure:

1. Structure of the regulatory framework (on EU and on national level);
2. Analysis of the regulatory framework;
3. Conclusions and main outcomes.

2.1. Regulatory framework for low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products, with special focus on Bulgaria

Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner TU Sofia.

2.1.1. Structure of the regulatory framework for the object of study for group A

2.1.1.1. Research on European Legislation for acts related to the object of study for group A

Construction Products Regulation (CPR, 305/2011) [1], Document Type: Regulation, Institution: European Parliament and Council of the EU, Date: 9 March 2011, Level: European, Status: Current, under modification, Subject matter: This Regulation lays down conditions for the placing or making available on the market of construction products by establishing harmonized rules on how to express the performance of construction products in relation to their essential characteristics and on the use of CE marking on those products.

Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011 (COM/2022/144 final) [2], Document Type: Proposal for a Regulation, Institution: European Commission, Date: 30 March 2022, Level: European, Subject matter: The two general objectives pursued by the revision of the CPR are to (1) achieve a well-functioning single market for construction products and to (2) contribute to the objectives of the green and digital transition, particularly the modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. This is an initiative within the Regulatory Fitness Programme (REFIT) as the proposal aligns with the aims of the REFIT programme, which are to make the EU laws simpler, more targeted and easier to comply with.

Directive on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) (2010/75/EU) [3], Document Type: Directive, Institution: European Parliament and Council of the EU, Date: 24 November 2010, Level: European, Status: Current, under modification, Subject matter: This Directive lays down rules on integrated prevention and control of pollution arising from industrial activities. It also lays down rules designed to prevent or, where that is not practicable, to reduce emissions into air, water and land and to prevent the generation of waste, in order to achieve a high level of protection of the environment taken as a whole.

Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) and Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste (COM/2022/156 final) [4], Document Type: Proposal for a Directive, Institution: European Commission, Date: 5 April 2022, Level: European, Subject matter: The aim of the revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive is to stimulate a deep agro-industrial transformation towards zero pollution through the use of breakthrough technologies, thereby contributing to reaching carbon neutrality, increased energy efficiency, a non-toxic environment and a circular economy. It also aims to continue supporting the creation of a competitive level playing field providing a high level of protection of human health and the environment. In addition, the revision will seek to modernize and simplify the current legislation, for instance through digitalization and improving knowledge about sources of pollution. The initiative will also aim to improve public participation in decision-making and increase access to information and justice, including to effective redress mechanisms.

Directive on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe (2008/50/EC) [5], Document Type: Directive, Institution: European Parliament and Council of the EU, Date: 21 May 2008, Level: European, Status: In force, Subject matter: This Directive lays down measures aimed at the following: defining and establishing objectives for ambient air quality designed to avoid, prevent or reduce harmful effects on human health and the environment as a whole; assessing the ambient air quality in Member States on the basis of common methods and criteria; obtaining information on ambient air quality in order to help combat air pollution and nuisance and to monitor long-term trends and improvements resulting from national and Community measures; ensuring that such information on ambient air quality is made available to the public; maintaining air quality where it is good and improving it in other cases; promoting increased cooperation between the Member States in reducing air pollution.

Commission Implementing Decision on publication of the European Assessment Documents (EADs) for construction products drafted in support of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 (2019/450) [6], Document Type: Implementing Decision, Institution: European Commission, Date: 19 March 2019, Level: European, Status: In force, Subject matter: The references of the European Assessment Documents for construction products drafted in support of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 that are listed in Annex to this Decision are hereby published in the Official Journal of the European Union.

Commission Implementing Decision amending Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 as regards European Assessment Documents for internal partition kits for use as non-loadbearing walls, systems of mechanically fastened flexible roof waterproofing sheets, thin metal composite sheet, elastic micro hollow spheres as concrete admixture, decking fixing assemblies and self-supporting translucent roof kits with covering made of plastic sheets (2019/896) [7], Document Type: Implementing Decision, Institution: European Commission, Date: 28 May 2019, Level: European, Status: In force, Subject matter: The Annex to Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 is amended in accordance with the Annex to this Decision.

2.1.1.2. Research on National legislation in the field of construction products for group A.

Law on technical requirements for products [8]. Document Type: Laws. Institution: Council of the Low Union. Date: 3 January 2019. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: This law defines the surveillance of products placed on the market and/or put into service for which essential ecodesign requirements and/or ecodesign requirements are laid down and construction products placed on the market pursuant to Regulation (EU) №305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Directive 89/106/EEC (OJ L 347, 20.12.2011, p. Pc. L 88/5 of 4 April 2011), 'Regulation (EU) №305/2011'

Law on Public Procurement [9] (as amended by SG No. 11 of 6 February 2024) Document Type: Laws. Institution: Council of the Low Union. Date: 15 April 2016. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: This law defines the terms and conditions for the awarding of public contracts for construction, supplies or services and for conducting project tenders by contracting authorities in order to ensure efficiency in the expenditure of: public funds; the funds provided by European funds and programs; the funds related to the performance of activities in the sectors of water supply, energy, transport and postal services; the funds of companies and enterprises that are contractors within the meaning of the law.

Ordinance № RD-02-20-1 of February 5, 2015, on the terms and conditions for use of construction products in the constructions of the Republic of Bulgaria, in force from March 1, 2015 [10]. Document Type: Under statutory act. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 5 February 2015. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: The ordinance determines the conditions and the procedures for: 1.Incorporation of construction products in the construction works of the Republic of Bulgaria; 2.Authorisation, notification and control of persons assessing construction products; 3.Issue or refusal to issue permits to persons for assessing conformity and for evaluation and inspection of constancy of performance of construction products, for the issue of a European Technical Assessment and of Bulgarian technical approvals of construction products; 4.Re-issue, expansion, update, limitation of scope, suspension and cancellation of the permits issued under point 3; 5.The assessment and drafting of a declaration for the characteristics of construction projects which have not been encompassed by the existing harmonised standards and for which no European Technical Assessments have been issued; 6.The determination of Bulgarian national requirements for construction materials regarding their intended use; 7.The implementation of the functions of a point of contact for products in construction materials, in accordance with Article 10 of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 determined harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products.

Ordinance for the essential requirements to the constructions and the conformity assessment of construction products [11], (amend. SG. 60/22 Jul 2014) Document Type: Under statutory act. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 1 January 2007. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: The ordinance defines: the essential requirements for constructions works under Art. 169, para. 1 of the Spatial Development Act, which determine the technical requirements for construction products; construction products or groups of construction products that ensure the fulfillment of the essential requirements to the constructions; the procedures and systems for assessing the compliance of construction products with the essential requirements to the constructions and the methods of certifying compliance; the conditions and procedure for obtaining a permit for conformity assessment and for issuing technical approvals, their validity periods, as well as additional specific criteria for the persons who assess conformity and/or issue technical approvals, and their obligations under the assessment procedures and systems of compliance; the terms and conditions for use of building products in the constructions that meet the requirements of the technical specifications under Art. 5, para. 2 of the Technical Requirements to Products Act; the rules for placing the marking for compliance; the control over the activities of the persons who have been granted permission to assess conformity and to issue technical approvals.

Draft Ordinance on environmental requirements for certain products subject to public procurement [12] - prepared pursuant to Art. 47a, para. 3 of the Law on Public Procurement, as well as the Recommendation of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Council on improving the implementation of environmental policy in public procurement, OECD/LEGAL/0311. The ordinance defines the product scope, the minimum mandatory environmental requirements for the products subject to public

procurement, which are supplied or used for the services provided, as well as the method of proving these requirements.

Ordinance on the management of construction waste and the use of recycled construction materials [13].

Document Type: Under statutory act. Institution: Council of Ministers. Date: 8 December 2017. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: The ordinance regulates: 1. the creation of a management and control system for the collection, transportation and treatment of construction waste; 2. the requirements for the use of recycled building materials in construction; 3. the requirements for the management of construction waste in the process of construction and removal of constructions.

Order № RD-02-14-1329/3.12.2015 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [14].

Document Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 15 December 2015. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Defines Bulgarian national requirements for the use of construction products in constructions in relation to their intended use or uses according to: 1. The national annexes to the harmonized standards from Annex № 1, including for the cases under Art. 5 of Regulation (EU) № 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of March 9, 2011 to determine harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and to repeal Council Directive 89/106/EEC (Regulation (EU) № 305/2011); 2. The national Annexes to the standards from Appendix №2 and the national requirements by product groups from Appendix №3. The appendices are an integral part of the warrant.

Order № RD-02-14-590/5.7.2017 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [15].

Document Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 5 July 2017. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Amends and supplements Order № RD-02-14-1329 of 3.12.2015 for determining Bulgarian national requirements for the use of construction products in construction in connection with their intended use or uses.

Order № RD-02-14-252/10.03.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [16].

Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 10 March 2021. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Amends and supplements Order № RD-02-14-1329 of December 3, 2015, amended and supplemented by Order № RD-02-14-590 of July 5, 2017 and Order № RD-02-14-257 of 13.03.2019 for determining Bulgarian national requirements for the use of construction products in the constructions of the Republic of Bulgaria in connection with their intended use or uses.

Order № RD-02-14-707/12.08.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [17].

Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 12 August 2021. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Approves Working Procedure № RP-OSSPNI-2.1, ISSUE № 04 for Certification of the conformity of concrete with the national requirements for the Annex of construction products in constructions in connection with their intended use or uses determined by Order № RD-02-14-1329 of 3.12.2015, amended and supplemented by Order № RD-02-14-590 of 07.05.2017, and by Order № RD-02-14-257 of 13.03.2019 and by Order № RD-02-14-252 of 10.03.2021

Order № RD-02-14-761/02.09.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [18].

Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 02 September 2021. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Approves: Working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-3.17.1, edition № 01 for certification of conformity of starting mixtures for sprayed concrete and working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-3.17.2, ed. № 01 for certification of the conformity of hardened sprayed concrete with the national requirements for the Annex of construction products in constructions in connection with their intended use or uses.

Order № RD-02-14-1169/30.11.2022 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works [19].

Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 30 November 2022. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Amends and supplements Order № RD-02-14-1329 dated December 3, 2015, amended and supplemented by Order № RD-02-14-590 dated 07.05.2017, and by Order № RD-02-14-257 of 13.03.2019 and with Order № RD-02-14-252 of 10.03.2021 for determining national requirements for the use of construction products in construction in connection with their intended use or uses.

Regulations on labor safety in the production of cement [20]. Type: Others acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 20 December 1997. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: This regulation

defines the requirements for safety, occupational hygiene and fire safety in the production of cement.

2.1.2. Analysis of the regulatory framework for the object of study for group A

The following criteria were used for the purposes of this analysis:

- Anticipated requirements in the legislation supporting the achievement of results for the implementation of environmental and digital transition policies.
- Existence of mechanisms to stimulate "Green building".
- Obstacles in legislation to require the use of environmentally friendly materials in public procurement.
- Difficulties in implementation at the national level.

2.1.2.1. Analysis of European legislation in the area of the research object group A

The Construction Products Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 305/2011) lays down conditions for the placing or making available on the market of construction products by establishing harmonized rules on how to express the performance of construction products in relation to their essential characteristics and on the use of CE marking on those products.

Within the meaning of the Regulation any product which is intended for incorporation in a permanent manner in construction works is defined as a construction product. Furthermore, products performance must have an impact on the performance of the construction works with respect to the basic requirements for construction works.

There is one specific feature in this Regulation that is of great importance. While its scope covers construction products, the seven essential requirements it sets out relate to construction works as a whole, not to the construction products themselves. Construction works must satisfy these seven requirements for construction works: Mechanical resistance and stability; Safety in case of fire; Hygiene, health and the environment; Safety and accessibility in use; Protection against noise; Energy economy and heat retention; Sustainable use of natural resources.

There are two important definitions:

- 'essential characteristics' - those characteristics of the construction product which relate to the basic requirements for construction works;
- 'performance of a construction product' - means the performance related to the relevant essential characteristics, expressed by level or class, or in a description.

According to the provisions of the Regulation, when a construction product is placed on the internal market of the European Union, it must be accompanied by a declaration of performance, issued on the basis of a harmonized technical specification, and affixed with the CE marking.

Harmonized technical specifications are harmonized standards and European Assessment Documents. Through them is provided a "common technical language" (common technical standards) on how to test and communicate the performance of construction products. The use of standards is recommended for assessment of products conformity when they are cited in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU).

Harmonized standards are documents developed by a recognized European Standards Organizations and created following a standardization request (old mandate) from the European Commission to one of these organizations. The references (such as titles, identification numbers) of harmonized standards shall be published in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU). When a construction product is covered by a harmonized standard, the manufacturer shall apply the test methods already defined in the harmonized standard, which will ensure the use of the common technical language required to complete the declaration of performance.

The European Assessment Documents (EAD) are developed and approved by the European Organization for Technical Assessment (EOTA) agreed with the European Commission, which publishes in the Official Journal

of the European Union (OJEU) a list of the approved EADs. These documents allow a manufacturer to request the issuance of a European technical assessment (ETA) for their specific product for which there is no published harmonized standard.

The harmonized standard provides a common technical platform for issuing performance declarations by manufacturers of construction products covered by this harmonized standard. As not all construction products are covered by a harmonized standard, the Construction Products Regulation enables manufacturers to obtain a European technical assessment as well as the right to draw up a declaration of performance and affix the CE marking to a non-covered construction product (in whole or in part) from a harmonized standard.

Construction products covered by a harmonized standard or a European Technical Assessment (ETA) issued for them shall be accompanied by a Declaration of Performance (DoP) when they are placed or made available on the market. The DoP refers to the essential characteristics of the product, expressed by level or class, or in a description, in accordance with the requirement of the applicable harmonized technical specification. This declaration is issued by the manufacturer for a specific product depending on the intended use of the product.

The Declaration of Performance can be published on a website under the conditions defined by Delegated Regulation (EU) No 157/2014, when the following conditions are simultaneously guaranteed:

- the content of the Declarations of Performance that have been published for download must under no circumstances be modified.;
- the website should be monitored and maintained, so that the uploaded DoPs are constantly available;
- free access to the Declarations of Performance 10 years after the construction product is placed on the market;
- provided instructions regarding access to the website and the Declarations of Performance;
- ensured traceability of the Declarations of Performance to each individual product/batch.

For any construction product covered by a harmonized standard, or for which a European Technical Assessment has been issued, the CE marking shall be the only marking which attests conformity of the construction product with the declared performance in relation to the essential characteristics, covered by that harmonized standard or by the European Technical Assessment. In this respect, Member States shall not introduce or shall withdraw any references in national measures to a marking attesting conformity with the declared performance in relation to the essential characteristics covered by a harmonized standard other than the CE marking.

Figure 3. CE marking procedures described in the CPR.

The methods used by the Member States in their requirements for construction works, as well as other national rules in relation to the essential characteristics of construction products, shall be in accordance with harmonized standards. These provisions mean that when a Member State defines requirements for a construction product, they shall be defined for the essential characteristics of the product, in the same way as defined in the harmonized standard. The Member State may not require methods for determining the performance of these essential characteristics that differ from those specified in the harmonized standard. When the Member State requires the achievement of a certain level or class of the performance of a product for its specific use, it is obliged to determine the requirement based on the levels and classes defined in the harmonized standard. When the normative legal acts do not define requirements for the use of a construction product, the designers shall determine the levels of the products' performance indicators, through which they will ensure the fulfillment of the basic requirements for the construction. In the investment projects, the intended construction products shall be defined in accordance with the harmonized standards.

The CE marking shall be affixed to a construction product by the manufacturer or by those responsible for placing the product on the market. It indicates responsibility for the conformity of the construction product with the declared performance. If a Declaration of Performance has not been drawn up for the product, the CE marking should not be affixed.

The Commission's proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and

repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011 (COM/2022 /144 final) aims making the EU laws simpler, more targeted and easier to comply with. According to the provisions of the document Regulation (EU) 305/2011 shall be repealed with effect from 1 January 2045. This proposal aims to tackle the following problems:

1. Single market for construction products not achieved.
2. Implementation challenges at national level.
3. Complexity of the legal framework, simplification not achieved.
4. Unable to deliver on broader policy priorities, such as the green and digital transition, and product safety.

The Commission's 2016 implementation report on the Construction Products Regulation identified certain shortcomings in its implementation and a significant number of challenges linked among others to standardization, simplification for micro-enterprises, market surveillance and enforcement, deserving further examination and discussion. The evaluation of the Construction Products Regulation, opinions of the REFIT platform as well as Member States' and stakeholders' feedback pointed clearly to the shortcomings of the framework, hindering the functioning of the single market for the construction products, and therefore failing to achieve the CPR's objectives.

The two general objectives of the Construction Products Regulation revision are:

1. achieve a well-functioning single market for construction products;
2. to contribute to the objectives of the green and digital transition, particularly the modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy.

The specific objectives are:

1. to unblock the technical harmonization system;
2. to reduce national barriers to trade for products covered by the Construction Products Regulation;
3. to improve enforcement and market surveillance;
4. to provide more clarity (more comprehensive definitions, reducing overlaps, collision rules with other legislation) and simplification;
5. to reduce the administrative burden, including through simplification and digitalization;
6. to ensure safe construction products;
7. to contribute to reducing the overall climate and environmental impact of construction products, including through the application of digital tools (Digital Product Passport).

With the Construction Products Regulation, the single market for construction products is not achieved. At the national level, insufficient market surveillance and enforcement prevents benefits in terms of opening up markets and levelling the playing field for competitors from materializing fully. Moreover, some Construction Products Regulation provisions are insufficiently clear or create overlaps, either within the CPR framework itself, or between the CPR and other EU legislation. Further, there is the inability of the Construction Products Regulation to deliver on broader policy priorities, particularly the green and digital transition.

This proposal is expected to improve the overall functioning of the single market for construction products, particularly by addressing the current issues relevant to the standardization system and eradicating further barriers to trade, such as duplication or overlapping of regulatory provisions either at the EU or national/regional levels. This would in turn increase legal certainty as well as predictability and improve the level playing field for the construction industry. Trust in the entire system would be leveraged thanks to more streamlined market surveillance practices across the EU. Finally, this proposal addresses the climate and environmental performance and circularity of construction products, which can only be tackled at the EU level, where the common technical language (standards) is being developed.

The standardization process at the core of the Construction Products Regulation has been underperforming.

In recent years, draft harmonized standards developed by the European Standardization Organizations (ESOs) could rarely be cited in the Official Journal (OJEU) mainly due to legal deficiencies. The lack of citation of up-to-date harmonized standards for construction products is a key factor undermining the smooth functioning of the single market, creating trade barriers and additional costs and administrative burden on economic operators. Outdated harmonized standards also mean that they are not always market-relevant, as the process cannot keep pace with the developments in the sector. Moreover, the current situation does not allow to fulfil the regulatory needs of the Member States. Due to these deficiencies, Member States apply national marks, certifications and approvals. This is in breach of the Construction Products Regulation and not in line with the jurisprudence of the European Court of Justice. In addition, given the underperformance of the conventional standardization route, the workload has progressively increased on the alternative route to obtaining the CE marking via the European assessment documents (EADs). This increase in workload has therefore led to the Commission needing more time to carry out its assessments and it may even risk to paralyzing the system.

An EU strategy on Standardization: 'Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU single market' from 2022 identified construction as one of the most pertinent areas where harmonized standards could improve competitiveness and reduce market barriers.

The implementation challenges at national level also add to the complexity of the legal framework and contribute to the fact that market surveillance activities widely vary (in quality and effectiveness) from one Member State to another. Ineffective market surveillance and enforcement in general limits the trust in the regulatory framework and is therefore a disincentive for companies to comply with the legislation. Drawbacks linked to the functioning of the Notified Bodies were identified in the implementation report indicating that relevant Construction Products Regulation provisions would benefit from more accuracy.

The CE marking is linked to the assessment of the performance of a construction product, and not to its conformity with product requirements, as these are not set by the Construction Products Regulation. Given that this is a rather exceptional situation compared to other New legislative framework legislation, the meaning of the CE marking is often misunderstood and misinterpreted.

In addition, there are no specific provisions on providing information in the digital format. This will become a challenge particularly as reliable product information (from manufacturing to the installation in the building and demolition) will be necessary in the context of tools for assessing and reporting on the sustainability performance of buildings.

The available harmonized assessment methods for the performance of construction products cover only some elements linked to the environmental impacts such as pollution but have not been established with regards to sustainable use of natural resources. Furthermore, the Construction Products Regulation does not allow to establish environmental, functional and safety product requirements for construction products, therefore hampering the possibility to address non-performance-based issues. However, to stimulate the incentives and demand for low-carbon and carbon-storing construction products, coherent and transparent information on the climate, environmental and sustainability performance of the construction products is needed as well as the possibility to govern inherent product characteristics such as durability or reparability. Moreover, digital information on construction products is not sufficiently available to address the goals of circularity and sustainability.

The proposal aims at addressing the identified shortcomings of the Construction Products Regulation and the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy action plan in relation to construction products, while building on the core principles of the Construction Products Regulation (including the harmonized standards developed by the European Standardization Organizations). Addressing and improving the core functioning of the Construction Products Regulation framework, in particular the standardization process, is imperative in delivering of the policy objectives. Some of the new features such as product requirements or Commission acts containing technical specifications will be applied only when needed for specific products.

The Commission may issue standardization requests in accordance with Regulation (EU) 1025/2012 laying down the basic principles and cornerstones for the establishment of these essential characteristics and their

assessment methods. The Commission shall verify that the basic principles and corner stones, and the Union law are respected in the standards prior to publishing the reference thereof in the Official Journal.

It is necessary to establish well-functioning information flows, including via electronic means and in machine-readable format, to ensure that coherent and transparent information about construction products performances is available. This is expected to increase transparency and to improve efficiency in terms of information transfer. Ensuring digital access to comprehensive information about construction products would contribute to the digitalization of the construction sector altogether, making the framework fit for the digital age.

Building a stronger Single Market for construction recovery as one of the priority ecosystems that face the most important challenges meeting climate and sustainability goals and embracing the digital transformation, and on which the competitiveness of the construction sector depends. It is therefore appropriate to lay down rules for declaring environmental and sustainability performance of construction products, including the possibility of establishing relevant thresholds and classes. The performance class for the environmental performance of the products should accurately reflect the variety of products and their most current status and should allow environmentally friendly products to be accurately identified.

The Directive on industrial emissions (Directive 2010/75/EU) lays down rules on integrated prevention and control of pollution arising from industrial activities. It also lays down rules designed to prevent or, where that is not practicable, to reduce emissions into air, water and land and to prevent the generation of waste, in order to achieve a high level of protection of the environment taken as a whole.

This Directive shall apply to the industrial activities giving rise to pollution as a production of cement - production of cement clinker in rotary kilns with a production capacity exceeding 500 tons per day or in other kilns with a production capacity exceeding 50 tons per day.

Member States shall take the necessary measures to provide that installations are operated in accordance with the following principles:

1. all the appropriate preventive measures are taken against pollution;
2. the best available techniques are applied;
3. no significant pollution is caused;
4. the generation of waste is prevented in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC;
5. where waste is generated, it is, in order of priority and in accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC, prepared for re-use, recycled, recovered or, where that is technically and economically impossible, it is disposed of while avoiding or reducing any impact on the environment;
6. energy is used efficiently;
7. the necessary measures are taken to prevent accidents and limit their consequences;
8. the necessary measures are taken upon definitive cessation of activities to avoid any risk of pollution and return the site of operation to the satisfactory state.

The Industrial Emissions Directive is the primary EU legal instrument to regulate industrial emissions and aims to achieve significant benefits to the environment and human health, in particular through the mandatory application of best available techniques. Sectors within the scope of this Directive account for a considerable share of overall pollution (emissions to air and water and waste generation) in Europe.

Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 November 2010 on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) and Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste (COM/2022/156 final).

The revision of the Industrial Emissions Directive aims to:

1. ensure access by private individuals and civil society to information, participation in decision-making,

- and access to justice (including effective redress) in relation to permitting, operation and control of the regulated installations, resulting in increased civil society action;
2. clarify and simplify the legislation and reduce administrative burden while promoting consistency of implementation by the Member States;
 3. promote the uptake of innovative technologies and techniques during the ongoing industrial transformation, by revising Best Available Techniques reference documents without delay, when there is evidence that better performing innovative techniques become available, and ensuring permits support frontrunners;
 4. support decarbonization by fostering synergies in the use of and investments in techniques that prevent or reduce pollution and carbon emissions, as evidenced by a coupling of the trends in emission intensities etc.;

The Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe lays down measures aimed at the following:

1. defining and establishing objectives for ambient air quality designed to avoid, prevent or reduce harmful effects on human health and the environment as a whole;
2. assessing the ambient air quality in Member States on the basis of common methods and criteria;
3. obtaining information on ambient air quality in order to help combat air pollution and nuisance and to monitor long-term trends and improvements resulting from national and Community measures;
4. ensuring that such information on ambient air quality is made available to the public;
5. maintaining air quality where it is good and improving it in other cases;
6. promoting increased cooperation between the Member States in reducing air pollution.

Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 of 19 March 2019 on publication of the European Assessment Documents (EADs) for construction products drafted in support of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council

The references of the European Assessment Documents for construction products drafted in support of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 that are listed in Annex to this Decision are hereby published in the Official Journal of the European Union.

Reference and title of the European Assessment Document - 260014-00-0301 Calcined layer silicate-based type II addition

Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/896 of 28 May 2019 amending Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 as regards European Assessment Documents for internal partition kits for use as non-loadbearing walls, systems of mechanically fastened flexible roof waterproofing sheets, thin metal composite sheet, elastic micro hollow spheres as concrete admixture, decking fixing assemblies and self-supporting translucent roof kits with covering made of plastic sheets.

The Annex to Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 is amended in accordance with the Annex to this Decision.

In the Annex to Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450, the following is added: 260017-00-0301 | Elastic micro hollow spheres as concrete admixture.

2.1.2.1.1. [Analysis of the latest draft of a new Construction Products Regulation](#)

The aim of the latest proposal for a draft regulation on construction products is focused on improvement of balance between delegated acts and implementing acts with regards to Commission's empowerments, and balanced solutions to the existing shortcomings in the implementation of the current Construction Products Regulation.

The construction industry is a huge and inert system and changes to it must be made very carefully and

gradually. Compromise texts have been written on the issues for which there are significant differences in the latest edition.

The compromise text introduces the concept of "harmonized area", which covers all construction products covered by a harmonized technical specification. However, an exception clause allows Member States to set national requirements for characteristics that are not regulated in harmonized technical specifications.

On 3D printing, the compromise text reflects the political compromise that was negotiated in Parliament. The text on 3D printing is now included in the texts related to the definitions and obligations of manufacturers.

The compromise text on the Construction Product Digital Passport empowers the Commission to adopt delegated acts to lay down future functionalities, actors, procedures and requirements and provides sufficient time to ensure that the system works properly and all the actors have time to adapt before using it.

As regards green public procurement, the compromise text widens the scope and removes the explicit prohibition of applying green procurement provisions to public construction works procurement.

Regarding the repeal of the previous CPR, the compromise text provides that it will be repealed by 2039 in order to allow sufficient time to ensure an orderly transition and proper migration of harmonized technical specifications from the old legal framework to the new one.

Regarding entry into force, the compromise text provides that the articles related to the development of standards will be applicable immediately from the date of entry into force. All other articles, except article 90, will apply 12 months after the date of entry into force. Article 90, related to sanctions, will apply 24 months from the date of entry into force to give Member States enough time to adapt their legislations.

The Commission's Communication on a New Industrial Strategy for Europe highlights the need to address the sustainability of construction products and highlights a more sustainable built environment as essential to Europe's transition to climate neutrality. The Commission Communication sets out rules for declaring the environmental and sustainable performance of construction products, including the possibility to establish relevant thresholds and classes. Performance classes for the environmental performance of products should accurately reflect the variety of products and their current status and should allow the most environmentally friendly products to be accurately identified. Furthermore, in environmental impact assessment, such performance classes must be understandable, must not be misleading, nor allow shifting of responsibility.

The EU's 2022 standardization strategy identifies construction as one of the most relevant areas where harmonized standards can improve competitiveness and reduce market barriers.

Standardization requests referred to in paragraph 2 may include a request for a proposal for one or more of the following elements:

1. voluntary or mandatory threshold levels in relation to essential characteristics;
2. classes of performance in relation to the essential characteristics;
3. these essential characteristics which shall always be declared by the manufacturers.

The pursuit of environmental goals, including the fight against climate change and the transition to a circular economy, necessitates laying the foundations for the development and application of an assessment method for calculating the environmental sustainability of construction products. Calculations should cover the life cycle of the product, using the methods established through standardization. For new products, calculated life cycles should include all stages of the product's life, from the acquisition of raw materials or generation from natural resources to their final disposal. For used and recycled products, the life cycle calculation starts with dismantling from construction work and includes all subsequent stages until final disposal. The Commission should provide software to perform the calculation, in particular the applicable characterization factors applicable according to EN 15804 or future applicable standards.

The Regulation follows the recent trend in product legislation to develop a fallback solution where European

Standardization Organizations do not provide valid harmonized standards. Where the standardization body provides a harmonized standard in accordance with the standardization request, which includes elements that do not meet the regulatory needs of the Member States or are not aligned with the safety, environment, circular economy and climate objectives of the Union, the Commission should review the request for standardization or to make a harmonized standard binding with limitations. The fallback decision should be possible to apply to harmonized standards that do not comply with a request for standardization and address a product family or category that are either not previously covered by a harmonized standard or already covered by a harmonized standard more applicable standard of 5 years or covered by a harmonized standard applicable with limitations. Where harmonized standards lay down the rules for the assessment of the essential characteristics that are relevant to the construction requirements of the Member States, they should become mandatory for the purposes of applying this Regulation as harmonized performance standards, since only such mandatory standards achieve the objective of allowing the free movement of products.

In order to achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Commission should be able to set minimum thresholds for the environmental performance of construction products and requirements to prevent and reduce the impact of construction products on the environment. However, the "safety first" principle applicable to the design, the product and the construction work must in all cases be respected and must cover the protection of health.

In order to be able to make an informed choice, users of construction products should be sufficiently well informed about the environmental characteristics of the products, about their compliance with environmental requirements and the degree of fulfillment of the manufacturer's environmental obligations in this regard. The Commission is therefore empowered to adopt delegated acts establishing specific labeling requirements.

Digitization and the availability of product information increases transparency in favor of product safety, environmental protection and human health, while reducing the administrative burden and costs for economic operators.

Contracting authorities and entities should, where appropriate, be required to align their public procurement with specific environmental procurement criteria to be set out in delegated acts adopted pursuant to this Regulation. Criteria for specific product families or categories must be met when contracts require a mandatory minimum environmental sustainability for construction products in terms of their essential characteristics covered by harmonized technical specifications. Minimum requirements should be established according to transparency, objectivity and non-discriminatory criteria.

In order to facilitate the smooth introduction of future harmonized technical specifications and taking into account the time required to draw up the declaration of performance and conformity, economic operators should be allowed to opt for the voluntary application of this Regulation as of the entry into force of those harmonized technical specifications.

The Commission identifies the technical aspects necessary to prepare standardization requests.

The methods and criteria for evaluating the performance of the product in relation to its essential characteristics shall be laid down in harmonized standards which shall become binding through the implementing acts referred to in paragraph 8. These harmonized standards shall, where appropriate and without jeopardizing the accuracy, reliability or stability of results to provide methods that are less burdensome than testing to assess the performance of products in terms of their essential characteristics.

Where a reference to a harmonized standard cannot be published in the Official Journal, the Commission may publish such reference with restrictions. The Commission may adopt implementing acts establishing common specifications that provide alternative means of complying with product requirements.

In order to improve legal certainty and reduce the fragmentation of the EU market for construction products, it is necessary to clearly define the area regulated at EU level, the so-called "harmonized area", as opposed to the elements remaining within the competence of the states - members. The harmonized area covers all products subject to harmonized technical specifications. Member States shall respect the harmonized area

in their national laws, regulations or administrative measures and shall not prohibit or impede the provision of access to products covered by it where they are in accordance with this Regulation. Member States register in the single digital portal all their national laws, regulations and administrative measures related to construction products in their territory covered by the harmonized area.

Where a product is covered by a harmonized technical specification adopted in accordance with Articles 4 or 4a, the manufacturer shall apply the applicable assessment and verification system referred to in Annex V and draw up a declaration of performance and conformity before such product is placed on the market. Where a product is covered by a harmonized technical specification adopted in accordance with Article 5, the manufacturer shall also verify the conformity of the product with the applicable product requirements laid down by delegated acts. A manufacturer of a product not covered by any harmonized technical specification can issue a declaration of performance and conformity with the relevant European assessment and a European technical assessment document.

The methods and criteria for evaluating the performance of the product, including the products used, in terms of their main characteristics can be defined in European assessment documents if this product is not covered by a harmonized standard or an implementing act.

The European technical assessment is issued by a technical assessment body at the request of a manufacturer based on a European assessment document, the reference of which is published in the Official Journal of the European Union in accordance with Article 38. The European technical assessment is issued according to a special procedure. Provided that there is a European Assessment Document, a European Technical Assessment can be issued even if a request for standardization has been issued. Such issuance should be possible in case of invalidity of the European assessment document. European Technical Assessments issued on the basis of a European Assessment Document remain valid for five years either after the expiry date of the European Assessment Document in accordance with Article 38(2) or after a reference that the European Assessment Document has been withdrawn by the Official Journal of the European union during the course of its validity. Products can no longer be placed on the market based on a European Technical Assessment when the relevant European Assessment Document becomes invalid. Products covered by a European Assessment Document for which a European Technical Assessment Document has been issued can be CE marked and thus obtain the same status as CE marked products based on harmonized technical specifications where the manufacturer meets the obligations, specified in the regulation.

The micro-enterprise may replace the type test or type calculation for essential characteristics under assessment and verification system 3 with a specific section in the technical documentation providing data equivalent to an assessment required for that essential characteristic in accordance with the applicable harmonized technical specifications or European assessment document.

The Commission adopts delegated acts to supplement this regulation to create a digital passport system for construction products in accordance with the conditions specified in this chapter. The digital product passport must meet the following conditions:

- Must be linked via one or more data carriers to a permanent unique identification code of the product type;
- All information included in the product passport shall be based on open standards developed in an interoperable format and shall be, as appropriate, machine-readable, structured, searchable and transferable via an open interoperable data exchange network. Where other Union legislation requires or allows the inclusion of specific information in the product passport, this information may be included in the product passport.
- Mandatory use and technical adaptation. Six months after the entry into force of the delegated act, the system must be fully operational and fulfill its intended purpose. In the meantime, the system can be used voluntarily by manufacturers. The Commission is empowered to adopt delegated acts to further specify, add and remove functionalities to adapt to technical progress or to adapt it in relation to information requirements in other EU legislation.

Where Member States provide incentives for a product category for which performance is expressed as a

performance class or as a class included in environmental sustainability labeling these incentives are targeted at the two highest performance classes.

In doing so, the Commission shall take into account the following criteria:

- a. the number of products in each feature class
- b. the need to ensure the availability of products meeting these requirements to avoid significant negative impacts on consumers.

For the implementation of "Green" public procurement, the Commission adopts delegated acts defining mandatory minimum requirements for environmental sustainability for construction products.

For public procurement procedures covered by Directives 2014/24/EU²⁶ or 2014/25/EU²⁷ of the European Parliament and of the Council, where contracts require minimum environmental sustainability performance for construction products in terms of their essential characteristics covered of harmonized technical specifications, contracting authorities apply mandatory minimum environmental sustainability requirements set out in the delegated acts. The first impact assessment will be launched by the Commission by 31 December 2026. Member States and the Commission provide technical assistance and advise national contracting authorities in charge of public procurement on how to comply with mandatory minimum environmental sustainability requirements.

Where contracting authorities and contracting entities use the derogation in accordance with the public procurement procedure, it cannot be considered environmentally sustainable in relation to the construction products to which the exemptions are applied.

Member States shall report every three years to the Commission on the use of this provision, pursuant to Article 82 of Directive 2014/24/EU. This provision does not affect the possibility to exclude abnormally low bids under Article 69 of Directive 2014/24/EU and Article 84 of Directive 2014/25/EU.

The environment is related to the extraction and production of materials, the production of the product, the transportation of materials and products, their maintenance, their potential to remain as long as possible within a circular economy and its end-of-life phase. When determining product-specific environmental requirements, harmonized technical specifications may differentiate them according to performance classes.

2.1.2.2. Analysis of National legislation in the area of the research object group A

The Technical Requirements to Products Act shall regulate the supervision of the products put on the market and/or commissioned, for which there are defined essential requirements and/or ecodesign requirements of the released/submitted to the market construction products according to Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC (OJ of the EU, No. L 88/5 of 4 April 2011), herein after referred to as "Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011"; Products designed and produced according to the requirements of the national standards of the European Union Member States, which introduce harmonized European standards shall be regarded as being in conformity with the essential requirements and/or with ecodesign requirements covered by these standards.

Construction products shall ensure the fulfilment of the basic requirements to construction projects, where they comply with Bulgarian national requirements regarding the intended use or uses and where there are harmonized European standards, reference numbers of which are published in the "Official Journal" of the European Union or a European Technical Assessment (ETA) is issued, and operational parameters of the essential characteristics of construction projects are determined and declared subject to compliance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011.

Where no technical specifications are available, construction products shall be deemed suitable for use in construction for their intended use, if their operation features and methods of determining thereof meet the requirements of: 1. the legislation act regarding designing, carrying out, control and maintenance of constructions, when they contain requirements to the construction products, and/or: 2. the national standards, with which European or international standards are being introduced; 3. Bulgarian national

standards or the national standards containing methods and requirements equivalent to the Bulgarian, where standards of item 2 are not available; 4. Bulgarian technical approvals, where standards under item 2 and 3 are not available.

The Council of Ministers shall assign by a decision to ministers and to other bodies of the executive authority the drafting of ordinances which shall determine the essential requirements to products.

Essential requirements to products shall determine the results to be achieved or the risks to be avoided in order to provide protection of the life and the health of people, the safety of the domestic animals, the protection of the consumers and the protection of the environment and belongings.

The Council of Ministers shall adopt, at the proposal of the ministers and other bodies of the executive authority the respective ordinances which shall determine the following: 1. products or groups of products for which essential requirements are determined; 2. essential requirements to products; 3. procedures for conformity assessment to the essential requirements and the ways of certifying the conformity; 4. documents required and the procedure for obtaining permits for conformity assessment, as well as additional specific criteria for the persons who assess the conformity and their obligations regarding the conformity assessment; 5. rules for placing the marking for compliance; 6. additional obligations to manufacturers, importers and traders, when determined in the corresponding "New approach" directive of the European Union.

Conformity assessment of the product to essential requirements, called hereinafter "conformity assessment" shall be implemented according to the procedures determined in the ordinances.

The procedure of issuing European technical approvals and introduction of the Manuals for technical approvals shall be set forth by the ordinance for the essential requirements to the constructions and the conformity assessment of construction products.

The conformity assessment procedures, determined by the ordinances and/or by the implementation measures and which are applicable to the respective product, shall be performed by the producers or by the notified before the European Commission bodies, whose identification numbers are announced in the Information system of notified and empowered bodies in the field of "New approach" Directives.

According to the Technical Requirements to Products Act, Chapter three - Assessment and certification of conformity of products to essential requirements. Notified bodies.:

The Minister of Regional Development and Public Works:

- is a notified body and shall inform the European Commission subject to compliance with Art. 42 of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011;
- shall nominate a specialized directorate to operate as a Product Contact Point for Construction according to Art. 10 of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 and subject to compliance with Art. 9, Art. 10 and Art. 11 of Regulation (EC) No. 764/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 July 2008 laying down procedures relating to the application of certain national technical rules to products lawfully marketed in another Member State and repealing Decision No. 3052/95/EC;
- issue permissions to persons to carry out conformity assessment and to carry out assessment and inspection of consistency of operation parameters of construction products, to issue a European Technical Assessment and of Bulgarian technical approvals of construction products, where they meet the requirements of Art. 43 and Art. 46 of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 and of Art. 10 of the Technical Requirements to Products Act; to withdraw and the re-issue already issued permits, to expand and update their scope, to suspend and to limit their effect;
- determine by an order Bulgarian national requirements to construction products regarding their intended purpose of use, including for the cases referred to in Art. 5 of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011; the order shall be promulgated in State Gazette;
- determine by an ordinance the terms and conditions for use of building materials in the constructions and also the terms and conditions for the procedure of implementation of activities under items 1 –

4, including for the control of the persons referred to in item 3.

For application of a unified approach during the implementation of conformity assessment procedures at a national level and unification of the national approach with the approach in the European Union the notified bodies shall:

1. participate in national working groups on the respective ordinance of Art. 7 for coordination and cooperation on issues referring to conformity assessment;
2. maintain the competence of the staff by participating in the activity for national standardization and being informed about decisions and documents of the working groups at the European Commission for the directives "New approach" and participate in working groups of notified bodies of the member states.

The State Agency for Metrological and Technical Surveillance and the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works shall ensure: organizationally – technically the work of the respective national working groups and determine their representatives for participation in them; access of national working groups to decisions and documents.

The conformity of each product with the essential requirements shall be certified by a marking for compliance, by an additional marking and by a declaration of conformity when required by the ordinances and by a technical dossier. The requirements for the contents of the declaration of conformity and of the technical dossier shall be determined by the ordinances.

The manufacturer or his authorized representative or other persons, pointed out in the ordinances, shall put marking for compliance, additional marking and compile in Bulgarian language declaration of conformity when this is required by the ordinances. For the products marked for compliance, have additional marking and declarations for compliance, when required by the ordinances of Art. 7, it shall be considered that they comply with the essential requirements and their compliance has been assessed by procedures determined by the ordinances.

The Council of Ministers shall determine by an ordinance the rules for putting and graphic inscription of the marking for compliance.

The manufacturer or his authorized representative or other persons, pointed out in the ordinances shall be obliged to keep the technical dossier for no less than 10 years from the last date of production of the product unless the respective ordinance stipulates another time period.

Market surveillance shall be carried out in order to ensure conformity of products placed on the market and/or commissioned with the requirements of the Act and the ordinances and/or the implementing measures from the Technical Requirements to Products Act and/or the requirements of Chapter five of the Technical Requirements to Products Act and/or the ordinance referred to in Art. 21e, Para 1 of the Act on Protection against the Harmful Impact Of Chemical Substances And Mixtures. Surveillance of construction products on the market shall be carried out by the Chairman of the State Agency for Metrological and Technical Surveillance, jointly with the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works.

Market surveillance bodies shall prohibit by a prescription the distribution and/or the using of products for which, as a result of the tests, it has been established that they do not comply with the essential requirements and/or with ecodesign requirements, and/or the requirements of the ordinance referred to in Art. 21e, Para 1 of the Act on Protection from the Harmful Impact of the Chemical Substances and Mixtures and shall prescribe to the producer, to his authorized representative, to the importer or to the trader to withdraw them from the market.

The names and the registration numbers of the Bulgarian standards implementing relevant European standards shall be published by the Bulgarian Institute for Standardization.

The application of the standards for products that are designed and manufactured in accordance with the requirements of the national standards of the Member States of the European Union, which implement harmonized European standards, the numbers of which are published in the "Official Journal" of the

European Union, are considered being in conformity with the basic requirements and/or to the eco-design requirements that are covered by these standards is voluntary in the area of application of the regulations adopted by the Council of Ministers, which determine the basic requirements for products.

The application of the standards for construction products, which ensure the fulfilment of the basic requirements to construction projects, where they comply with Bulgarian national requirements regarding the intended use or uses and where there are harmonized European standards, reference numbers of which are published in the "Official Journal" of the European Union or a European Technical Assessment (ETA) is issued, and operational parameters of the essential characteristics of construction projects are determined and declared subject to compliance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 is mandatory in the field of the regulation under Art. 7.

On the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, there is a **Law on Public Procurement** (in force from 15.04.2016, as amended by SG No. 11 of 6 February 2024).

This law defines the terms and conditions for the awarding of public contracts for construction, supplies or services and for conducting project tenders by contracting authorities in order to ensure efficiency in the expenditure of: 1. public funds; 2. the funds provided by European funds and programs; 3. the funds related to the performance of activities in the sectors of water supply, energy, transport and postal services; 4. the funds of companies and enterprises that are contractors within the meaning of the law.

A public procurement is the acquisition by one or several contracting authorities, by means of a contract for the public procurement of construction, supplies or services from contractors chosen by them, regardless of whether they are intended for public purposes - in the case of public contracting authorities, and in the case of sectoral contracting authorities - when they are intended for performance of sectoral activities.

Public procurement is awarded in accordance with the principles of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and in particular those of free movement of goods, freedom of establishment and freedom to provide services and mutual recognition, as well as with the resulting principles of

1. equality and non-discrimination;
2. free competition;
3. proportionality;
4. publicity and transparency.

Construction is also an object of public procurement.

When awarding public contracts, contracting authorities are not entitled to limit competition by including conditions or requirements that give an unreasonable advantage or unreasonably limit the participation of economic entities in public contracts and which are not consistent with the subject, value, complexity, quantity or volume of the public contract.

From 01.01.2024, with Art. 47a, the law lays down Mandatory environmental requirements, according to which, when awarding public procurements by public contracting authorities of value, public contracting authorities, as well as their associations, award public procurements with an estimated value greater than or equal to BGN 10,526,116 (for construction), the documentation contains environmental requirements for the products that are supplied or used for the services provided. Contracting authorities apply the requirements by specifying them in the technical specifications of the public procurement, or as indicators under the following award criteria: level of costs, taking into account cost-effectiveness, including the costs of the entire life cycle; optimal quality/price ratio, which is assessed on the basis of the price or the level of costs, as well as indicators including quality, environmental and/or social aspects related to the subject of the public procurement.

The products, the minimum mandatory environmental requirements and the way to prove them are determined by an ordinance issued by the Minister of Environment and Water together with the Minister of Finance and the Minister of Economy and Industry.

Pursuant to Art. 47a, para. 3 of the Law on Public Procurement, as well as the Recommendation of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) Council on improving the implementation of environmental policy in public procurement, OECD/LEGAL/0311, a **draft Ordinance on environmental requirements for certain products** subject to public procurement has been prepared.

The ordinance defines the product scope, the minimum mandatory environmental requirements for the products subject to public procurement, which are supplied or used for the services provided, as well as the method of proving these requirements.

In the thus prepared draft of the Ordinance on the environmental requirements for certain products, there is no mention of "construction products".

At the same time, on the territory of the country, there is no other regulation in force or in the draft, which would determine what the environmental requirements should be for construction products and, in particular, for products from the considered "group A".

According to additional provisions of the Law on Public Procurement, "Environmental requirements" are requirements that ensure that the products that are supplied or used for the services provided have a reduced impact on the environment throughout their life cycle.

On the territory of the country of operation **Ordinance No. RD-02-20-1**, dated February 5, 2015, on the terms and conditions for use of construction products in the constructions of the Republic of Bulgaria, issued by the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. The regulation defines the terms and conditions for incorporation of construction products in the constructions of the Republic of Bulgaria; authorization, notification and control of persons for assessing compliance of construction products; issuing or refusing to issue permits to persons to carry out conformity assessment and to assess and verify the constancy of performance of construction products, to issue European technical assessment and Bulgarian technical approvals of construction products.

According to the Ordinance, construction products for which harmonized technical specifications have entered into force: harmonized standards or an issued European Technical Assessment (ETA), ensure the meeting of the basic requirements toward construction works, where performance of their essential characteristics are determined and declared in accordance with the requirements of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 and meet the Bulgarian national requirements in regard to intended use, as established in Art. 8, para. 1, item 1 and item 5.

Construction products for which no harmonized European standards have been in place nor has an ETA been issued, ensure the meeting of the basic requirements toward construction works where their characteristics are determined, declared and compliant with the Bulgarian national requirements regarding intended use, as established in Art. 8, para. 1.

In Art.8 is written that: (1) National requirements for the incorporation of construction products in construction works, including in the cases under Art. 5 of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, are determined with:

1. legislation relating to the design, completion, maintenance and monitoring of construction works where these include requirements vis-à-vis construction products, and/or
2. national standards, by means of which international or European standards are enacted;
3. Bulgarian national standards or the national standards equivalent to methods used in Bulgaria and requirements where standards under point 2 are unavailable;
4. Bulgarian technical approvals (BTA).
5. order of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works in connection with the intended use or uses of products.

National requirements, as determined pursuant to paragraph 1, item 5, are drafted in National Annexes to standards in the relevant technical committees of the Bulgarian Institute for Standardisation (BDS) or are concurred with them when no harmonized standards are available.

According to Art. 9 (1) Bulgarian Technical Approvals are issued for construction products for which no ETA is issued nor a harmonized European standard or a standard under Art. 8, para. 1, items 2 and 3 is available or such that tangibly differ from them.

It is not necessary to issue Bulgarian Technical Approvals for construction products which have been legally placed on the markets of other Member States of the European Union, Turkey and the Member States of the European Free Trade Association - states belonging to the European Economic Area Agreement within the meaning of Regulation (EU) 2019/515, except at the stated request of the manufacturer. In these cases, the manufacturer or his authorized representative certifies the legal placing of the product on the market in another member state to the persons for evaluating construction products through a declaration of mutual recognition according to Art. 4 of Regulation (EU) 2019/515, if such has been prepared, or documentation and information pursuant to Art. 5, paragraph 5 of Regulation (EU) 2019/515.

The Bulgarian Technical Approval is a positive technical assessment for the viability of a construction product for meeting the basic requirements toward construction works, in which the product is invested long-term, depending on its use. It can be issued if it is proven possible to ensure at least one basic requirement for the construction when the construction product is invested in accordance with the intended use. Bulgarian Technical Approvals are developed and issued on the grounds of research, tests and assessment of the viability of construction products for their intended use. Whenever products' guidelines for European Technical Approvals and/or European Assessment Documents are published, BTA shall be drafted in accordance with the rules and procedures therein taking the geographical and climatic features, the national experience and traditions of the Republic of Bulgaria into account. In all other cases BTA shall be issued in accordance with the respective basic requirements for construction works designated as designated in relevant regulations. The validity period of an issued BTA is 5 years and may be extended.

The validity period of the issued BTA is discontinued prior to the date of expiry after the end of the period of simultaneous application under Art. 17, para 5, letter c of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 or one year after the publication of a standard for the product under Art. 8, para 1, items 2 and 3.

The costs for the BTA issue procedure shall be at the expense of the manufacturer or of its authorised representative and shall be determined with a contract.

Annex No. 4 to Art. 18, para. 4, item 4 of Ordinance No. RD-02-20-1 describes the product areas for issuing Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTOBTA) and their codes. Product areas belonging to the researched product family is reported in Table 8.

Table 8. List of product areas for issuing Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTOBTA) and their codes, from Annex No. 4 to Art. 18, para. 4, item 4 of Ordinance No. RD-02-20-1.

Code	Product area
1	precast normal/lightweight/autoclaved aerated concrete products
15	cement, building limes and other hydraulic binders
16	reinforcing and prestressing steel for concrete (and ancillaries), post tensioning kits
26	products related to concrete, mortar and grout

With the **Ordinance on the management of the construction waste and on the use of recycled building materials** adopted with Decree No. 267 of 05.12.2017 and Prom. SG. 98/8 Dec 2017, are regulated: 1. the establishment of a system for management and control over the collection, transport and treatment of construction waste; 2. the requirements for the use of recycled building materials for the purpose of construction; 3. the requirements of direct management of construction waste in the process of construction and removal of construction works.

The aim of this Regulation is to: 1. prevent and limit air, water and soil pollution and to reduce the risk to human health and to the environment as result of the collection, treatment and transport of construction waste materials; 2. encourage the recycling and utilization of the same in order to achieve the objectives

under Art. 32 of the Bulgarian Waste Management Law.

The Ordinance applies to the waste according to Annex No. 1, generated by construction and assembly works, as well as by the removal of constructions, regardless of the category of the construction, according to Art. 137, para. 1 of the Spatial Development Act; for recycled building materials; for products prepared from construction waste for reuse.

Regarding the management of construction waste, the persons whose activity it is generated and/or the persons who should treat it, the following priority order applies: 1. prevention of formation; 2. preparation for reuse; 3. recycling of construction waste; 4. recovery in reverse embankments; 5. incineration with energy recovery and processing into materials that are used as fuel; 6. disposal of construction waste.

According to the Ordinance on the management of the construction waste and on the use of recycled building materials, "Mineral waste" is waste generated as a result of construction or removal of constructions, which mainly consists of mineral materials, such as bricks, concrete, construction mortars, natural stone, sand, ceramic building materials, concrete blocks and/or aerated concrete blocks, etc., some of which fall into the researched "group A".

In the Ordinance, non-hazardous as well as hazardous construction waste are classified by their names and waste codes, according to Ordinance No. 2 of 2014 on the classification of waste. The researched "group A" includes codes reported in Table 9.

Table 9. Hazardous and non-hazardous waste belonging to the research group under study. Table from [21].

I. Classification of non-hazardous construction waste	
Waste code according to Ordinance No. 2 of 2014 on waste classification	Name of the non-hazardous construction waste
17 01	Concrete, bricks, roof tiles, tiles, porcelain and ceramic products:
17 01 01	concrete
17 01 02	bricks
17 01 03	shingles, tiles, earthenware and ceramic products
17 01 07	concrete mixtures, bricks, roof tiles, tiles, earthenware and ceramic products, other than those mentioned in code 17 01 06
II. Classification of hazardous construction waste	
Waste code according to Ordinance No. 2 of 2014 on waste classification	Name of hazardous construction waste
17 01 06*	Mixtures of or individual fractions of concrete, bricks, roof tiles, tiles, earthenware and ceramic products containing hazardous substances

Quantitative goals for material recovery by types of construction waste by year have also been set, which for the considered "group A" are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Quantitative goals for material recovery by types of construction waste by year. Table from [21].

I. Waste code	Year			
	2017	2018	2019	2020 and every subsequent year
17 01 01 concrete	85 %	85 %	85 %	85 %
17 01 02 bricks	50 %	57 %	63 %	70 %

I. Waste code	Year			
	2017	2018	2019	2020 and every subsequent year
17 01 03 shingles, tiles, earthenware and ceramic products	50 %	57 %	63 %	70 %

Requirements to the activities of collection and utilization of construction waste, as well as to the sites where these activities are carried out must be observed.

Storage areas for accepted waste shall be designated on the site. Separate areas are set aside for the separate storage of pre-sorted waste by type of material: concrete, ceramics, asphalt concrete, mixed fractions, rock materials, etc., which shall be sized according to the capacity of the crushing plant. A separate area is planned for the temporary storage of construction waste, for which contamination is suspected, until the necessary tests are carried out and/or their disposal is organized.

The site shall have a specification of the accepted waste, which details the requirements for the waste that can be accepted, for example uncontaminated concrete and reinforced concrete lumps, separately collected ceramic fractions consisting of tiles and bricks, asphalt concrete from reconstruction and overhaul of roads, rock materials from basic and sub-basic layers of roads, etc.

Ordinance for the essential requirements to the constructions and the conformity assessment of construction products, adopted with Decree No. 325 of 06.12.2006, in force from 01.01.2007, amend. SG. 60/22 Jul 2014. The regulation is divided into three parts. In the first part, general requirements and essential requirements for constructions are considered. In part two: conditions and procedure for assessing the conformity of construction products that comply with European technical specifications; conformity assessment and certification; requirements for conformity assessment persons; procedure for issuing permits to persons for assessing the conformity of construction products; European technical approval; control for compliance with the conditions under which the permit was issued for assessing the conformity of construction products and for issuing ETA.

The third part describes: conditions and procedure for assessing the conformity of construction products that correspond to the Bulgarian technical specifications; assessment and certification of conformity; Bulgarian Technical Approval.

According to the regulation, construction products intended for permanent investment in constructions are placed on the market when: they are suitable for their intended use and, more specifically, they satisfy the essential requirements for constructions under Art. 169, para. 1 of the Spatial Planning Act and meet the technical specifications. They must have suitable characteristics for embedding, mounting, placement or installation in the constructions works that are designed, executed and put into operation in accordance with the technical rules, norms and standards determined by the relevant normative acts.

The technical requirements for the construction products and the levels and classes of their operation features, which arise from the essential requirements for the constructions, are determined by the technical specifications and by the normative acts.

Construction products are evaluated in accordance with the requirements of the technical specifications under Art. 5, para. 2 of the Technical Requirements to Products Act, hereinafter referred to as "European technical specifications", as follows: 1. national standards of the member states of the European Union, which implement harmonized European standards, the numbers of which are published in "Official Journal" of the European Union; 2. European technical approvals, when there are no technical specifications under item 1; 3. national technical specifications when there are no technical specifications under items 1 and 2.

When the technical specifications do not exist, have not been published or have not entered into force, the construction products are evaluated in accordance with the requirements of the normative acts and the technical specifications under Art. 5, para. 3 of the Technical Requirements to Products Act, hereinafter

referred to as "Bulgarian technical specifications", as follows: 1. the normative acts for the design, implementation, control and maintenance of constructions, when they contain requirements for construction products, and/or 2. the national standards that introduce European or international standards; 3. Bulgarian national standards or national standards with equivalent Bulgarian methods and requirements, when there are no standards under item 2; 4. the Bulgarian technical approvals, when there are no standards under items 2 and 3.

The manufacturer or his authorized representative is obliged to put on the market the construction products that comply with the European technical specifications, with the CE mark of conformity, accompanied by the EU declaration of conformity and application instructions prepared in Bulgarian language. The CE mark of conformity of construction products certifies that the products comply with the technical specifications, according to the relevant legal acts.

The placing on the market of construction products suitable for use is carried out after assessing their compliance with the essential requirements for construction, hereinafter referred to as "conformity assessment".

The manufacturer or his authorized representative is obliged to put on the market the construction products that comply with the Bulgarian technical specifications, with a declaration of conformity and with application instructions prepared in Bulgarian language and is obliged to assess and certify the conformity of the construction products with the essential requirements to constructions.

Construction products that comply with Bulgarian technical specifications are not marked with the CE marking.

The evaluation procedures and the methods for controlling conformity are the following: 1. initial testing of the type of construction product by the manufacturer or by a person who has received permission to assess conformity; 2. testing of test samples from the production, selected in accordance with a test plan drawn up in advance by the manufacturer or by a person who has received permission for conformity assessment; 3. control testing (audit) by the manufacturer or by a person authorized to assess conformity, of test samples taken from production, from the market or from the construction site; 4. testing by the manufacturer or by a person authorized to assess the conformity of test samples from a batch that is prepared for shipment or has already been delivered; 5. production control; 6. initial inspection of the production and of the production control by a person who has received permission to assess conformity; 7. supervision and assessment of production control by a person who has received permission to assess conformity.

The conformity of the construction product is certified with the CE marking and, depending on the conformity assessment system, with the EU declaration of conformity of the construction product.

The **European Technical Approval (ETA)** is a positive technical assessment of the suitability for use of a given construction product to satisfy the essential requirements for the constructions in which the product is invested long-term, depending on its purpose.

The European Technical Approval is issued for construction products for which there are no Bulgarian standards, which introduce harmonised European standards, a recognized national standard or a mandate/standardization request for the development of a harmonised European standard, and for construction products that differ significantly from Bulgarian standards, which introduce a harmonised European standard, or from a recognized national standard.

European technical approval can also be issued under the conditions of an issued mandate/ standardization request for the development of a harmonised European standard. In this case, the ETA applies until the entry into force of the harmonized standard. The validity period of ETA is 5 years and can be extended.

European technical approvals are developed on the basis of studies, tests and assessment of the suitability of construction products for their intended use or on the basis of the Guidelines for European Technical Approval (if any) and the general procedural rules for application, preparation and issuance of ETA. When there is no Guideline for European Technical Approval for a given product, the ETA is issued with reference to the relevant essential requirements for the constructions and the mandates/requests, applying the

general procedural rules for applying, preparing and issuing the ETA.

Order No. RD-02-14-1329 of 3.12.2015 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works determines Bulgarian national requirements for the use of construction products in construction in connection with their intended use or uses according to: 1. The national annexes to the harmonized standards from Annex No. 1; 2. The national annexes to the standards from Annex No. 2; 3. The national requirements by product groups from Annex No. 3; 4. The period for simultaneous application of the harmonized standards under Art. 17, paragraph 5, letters "b" and "c" of Regulation (EU) No. 305/2011 also applies to the corresponding national applications developed for them, which are an integral part of the order.

Order No. RD-02-14-590/5.7.2017 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works amends and supplements Order No. RD-02-14-1329/3.12.2015 for determining Bulgarian national requirements for the Annex of construction products in relation to their intended use, as follows:

A new item 74 "BDS EN 12620/NA Aggregates for concrete – National Annex (NA)"

Annex No. 3 amends/supplements national requirements for determining and declaring the constancy of the characteristics of hydraulically bound mixtures depending on the intended use. The requirements are applied according to the BDS EN 14227 series of standards.

Order No. RD-02-14-252/10.03.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works amends and supplements Order No. RD-02-14-590/5.7.2017, amended and supplemented by Order No. RD-02-14-1329 of 3.12.2015 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works to determine Bulgarian national requirements for the use of construction products in construction in connection with their intended use or uses, with the relevant amendments and additions regarding the researched "group A" being as follows:

In Annex 3, point 17 is created, regarding the national requirements for determining and declaring the constancy of the performance of starting mixes for sprayed concrete and hardened sprayed concrete according to BDS EN 14487-1 Depending on the intended use of the following construction products: 1. Starting mixes for sprayed concrete including: wet mixes for sprayed concrete; factory-produced dry mixes for sprayed concrete with a minimum moisture content of no more than 0.5%; dry mixtures for sprayed concrete with a moisture content of additional materials no more than 6%.

2. Hardened sprayed concrete filled with factory-produced mixtures according to point 1 or with dry mixtures mixed on site with additional materials with a moisture content of not more than 6%.

Notes indicate that: these national requirements do not cover packaged dry mixtures intended for recovery which must fulfill the requirements of BDS EN 1504-3; Hardened sprayed concrete filled with packaged dry mixtures for restoration produced according to BDS EN 1504-3 must satisfy the present requirements.

Order № RD-02-14-707/12.08.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Type: Administrative acts. Institution: National Ministries. Date: 12 August 2021. Level: Nationally. Status: In force. Subject matter: Approves Working Procedure № RP-OSSPNI-2.1, ISSUE № 04 for Certification of the conformity of concrete with the national requirements for the Annex of construction products in constructions in connection with their intended use or uses determined by Order № RD-02-14-1329 of 3.12.2015, amended and supplemented by Order № RD-02-14-590 of 07.05.2017, and by Order № RD-02-14-257 of 13.03.2019 and by Order № RD-02- 14-252 of 10.03.2021.

The procedure regulates the procedure and rules for certifying the conformity of concrete in accordance with the national requirements for their use in construction. object of the procedure, with the following products: ordinary, heavy and light concrete; concrete prepared on site, ready-mix concrete or concrete produced in a ready-mixed concrete plant; compacting or self-compacting concrete to achieve negligible entrapped air content other than air entrainment according to BDS EN 206:2013+A2:2021 „ Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity” and BDS EN 206:2013+A2:2021/NA:2021 „ Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity - National Annex (NA)” intended for concrete for structures cast in situ, precast structures, and structural precast products for buildings and civil engineering structures. The procedure is applied in accordance with the general procedure "Assessment of conformity of

construction products with national requirements" of the Association of Conformity Assessment Bodies of Construction Products, approved by the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Conformity assessment is carried out according to the national requirements for determining and declaring the characteristics of the specifics specified in this procedure.

Assessed characteristics related to the fulfillment of national requirements are given in Table 11. These characteristics are of objects assessed for conformity by the conformity assessment body and are declared by the manufacturer.

Table 11. Assessed characteristics related to the fulfillment of national requirements [22].

Characteristic	In all cases when evaluating concrete	When requested *
Environmental impact class		X
Chloride content	X	
Maximum size of additive material	X	
Consistency: - subsidence or - degree of compaction or - spreading diameter - spreading during settlement (for self-compacting concrete)	X	
Air content in the concrete mix	X (when air-entraining additives are used)	
Density of hardened concrete	X (for light and heavy concrete)	X
Compressive strength	X	
Composition of concrete		X
Viscosity (for self-compacting concrete)		X
Passability (for self-compacting concrete)		X
Resistance to delamination (for self-compacting concrete)		X
Split tensile strength		X
Flexural Tensile Strength		X
Water tightness		X
Depth of water penetration		X
Frost resistance		X
Drying	X (when using recycled additives)	X
Crawling	X (when using recycled additives)	X
Modulus of elasticity	X (when using recycled additives)	X
Increase in strength		X

* The manufacturer specifies in an application which characteristics will be evaluated for individual concretes.

In the process of the procedure for assessing compliance with national requirements, the Conformity Assessment Bodies carry out control and assessment of compliance with regard to: composition of the

concrete; production control; delivery of the concrete mixture; conducting concrete tests; concrete mix testing; testing of hardened concrete; criteria for conformity of concrete characteristics. By applying the requirements set in the relevant standards specified in the order during the assessment.

Regarding the conformity of concrete characteristics: Modulus of elasticity (for recycled materials); Drying and Creep, no standardization requirements have been set for evaluation. Compliance with these characteristics is declared by the manufacturer.

According to the considered order, the procedure for assessing the conformity of concrete with national requirements goes through the following stages:

- Submitting an application and concluding a contract.
- Determining the type of product.
- Initial inspection of production and production control:
 - Inspection (audit) of production and production control;
 - Initial tests to verify the reliability of the production control and the conformity of the concretes with the criteria of the technical specification regarding the evaluated characteristics (initial control tests).
- Assessment of conformity and issuance of certificate of conformity.
- Annual inspections:
 - annual inspection (audit) of production and production control;
 - tests to verify the reliability of the production control and the conformity of the concretes with the criteria of the technical specification regarding the evaluated characteristics (control tests).
- Assessment for continued validity of the issued certificate.

Order № RD-02-14-761/02.09.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works approves working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-3.17.1, edition № 01 for certification of conformity of starting mixtures for sprayed concrete and working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-3.17.2, ed. № 01 for certification of the conformity of hardened sprayed concrete with the national requirements for the Annex of construction products in constructions in connection with their intended use or uses.

The order defines: the characteristics related to the fulfillment of the national requirements regarding the certification of the conformity of starting mixes for shotcrete; the obligations of the conformity assessment person; The conformity assessment procedure (general provisions; determination of product type; initial inspection and assessment of production control; issuance of a certificate of conformity; annual inspection of production control; decision on the validity of issued certificates; extension of the scope of the certificate).

In the work procedure, requirements are set regarding the characteristics of wet mixes for sprayed concrete; factory-produced dry mixes for sprayed concrete with a minimum moisture content of not more than 0.5%; as well as for dry mixtures for sprayed concrete with a moisture content of additional materials not greater than 6%, related to the fulfillment of the national requirements applied to determine and declare compliance depending on the intended use. For each of the characteristics, the following are set: declaration method class/level/description (variable unit); test/determination method; declaration requirement/threshold level.

2.1.3. Conclusions

2.1.3.1. Requirements provided for in the legislation supporting the achievement of results for the implementation of environmental and digital transition policies.

The Construction Products Regulation 305/2011 does not contain specific requirements to support the digital and ecological transition.

In the proposal for a new regulation for construction products, such requirements are laid down:

- introduction of 3D printing
- opportunities are foreseen to supplement and develop the legislative framework of the regulation through additional acts;
- introduction of machine-readable documents;
- introduction of a digital passport of construction products.

Existing national legislation enables manufacturers of construction products for which: no European Technical Assessment (ETA) has been issued; there is no Harmonised European Standard; there are no national standards that introduce European or international ones; there are no Bulgarian national standards or national standards with equivalent to Bulgarian methods and requirements, or which differ significantly from them, to issue Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTA), which supports putting on the market of innovative construction products, through which results aimed at the ecological and digital transition can be achieved.

The issuance of Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTA) is paid for by the manufacturers. This can be a financial obstacle for some of them.

2.1.3.2. Existence of mechanisms to stimulate "Green building".

The Construction Products Regulation 305/2011 does not contain mechanisms to stimulate "Green building".

The proposal for a new regulation on construction products includes mechanisms for:

- inclusion of green public procurement;
- stimulation of the use of higher efficiency classes of construction products.

At national level, no active incentives were found for investors, builders and manufacturers of cement and cement-based products, promoting the production and investment in construction works of low-carbon cement products.

2.1.3.3. Obstacles in legislation to require the use of environmentally friendly materials in public procurement.

The Construction Products Regulation 305/2011 does not include requirements regarding the use of environmentally friendly materials in public procurement.

The proposal for a new Regulation introduces minimum thresholds for the environmental friendliness of construction products.

From the beginning of 2024, in the Law on Public Procurement, which is in force for the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, when awarding public contracts by public contractors, with an estimated value, for construction, greater than or equal to BGN 10,526,116, the documentation shall contain environmental requirements for the products that are supplied or used for the services provided. The products, the minimum mandatory environmental requirements and the method of proving them shall be determined by an Ordinance on the environmental requirements. In the so-prepared draft of the Ordinance, the words (term) "construction products" is not mentioned at all. At the same time, there is no other national ordinance that shall determine what the environmental requirements should be for construction products and, in particular, for cement and cement-based products. This, in turn, can be seen besides as an obstacle in legislation and as a prerequisite for discrimination.

2.1.3.4. Difficulties in implementation at a national level.

The research carried out and the subsequent analysis of the existing European and national legislation, in relation to construction products, in particular the considered Group A: Cement and cement-based products, established a well-regulated legislative framework, which does not appear to be an obstacle to the standardization processes within the the twin transition. The inefficiency of market surveillance and law enforcement, as well as the lack of economic incentives, regarding the production and investment in construction of low-carbon cement products can be cited as difficulties.

2.1.3.5. *Specific focus on the relation between the existing legislative framework and the twin transition*

The relation between the existing legislative framework and the twin transition is summarized in Table 12, where we list a series of enabling features and barriers related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”, specifically the “green transition” and the “digital transition”.

Table 12. List of legislative barriers and enabling features related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”

Framework	Enabling features	Barriers
Green transition	<p>In the proposal for a new Construction Products Regulation from 2023, which is expected to enter into force soon, mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the green transition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inclusion of green public procurement; • introduction of 3D printing; • introduction of minimum thresholds for environmental friendliness of construction products; • possibilities are foreseen to complement and develop the legislative framework of the regulation through additional acts; • possibilities are foreseen to stimulate the use of higher efficiency classes of construction materials 	<p>In Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, and in its amendment from 2014, no mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the green transition.</p> <p>In Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, and in its amendment from 2014, requirements regarding the use of environmentally friendly materials in public procurement are not included.</p> <p>In the existing European and national legislation, there is a lack of economic incentives regarding the production and incorporation into construction works of low-carbon construction products pertained to group "A".</p>
Green transition	<p>In the Law on Public Procurement of the Republic of Bulgaria from 01.01.2024, an article was added, according to which the documentation shall contain environmental requirements for the products.</p> <p>The products, the minimum mandatory environmental requirements and the method of proving them shall be determined by an Ordinance on environmental requirements.</p>	<p>In the so-prepared draft of the Ordinance, the words (term) "construction products" is not mentioned at all. At the same time, there is no other national ordinance that shall determine what the environmental requirements should be for construction products and, in particular, for cement and cement-based products.</p>
Green transition	<p>Existing national legislation enables manufacturers of construction products for which: no European Technical Assessment (ETA) has been issued; there is no Harmonised European Standard; there are no national standards that introduce European or international ones; there are no Bulgarian national standards or national standards with equivalent to Bulgarian methods and requirements, or which differ significantly from them, to issue Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTA), which supports putting on the market of innovative construction products, through which results aimed at the</p>	<p>The issuance of Bulgarian Technical Approvals (BTA) is paid for by the manufacturers. This can be a financial obstacle for some of them.</p>

	ecological and digital transition can be achieved.	
Green transition	The research carried out and the subsequent analysis of the existing European and national legislation, in relation to construction products, in particular the considered Group A products: Cement and cement-based products, ascertained a legislative framework that does not appear to be an obstacle to the standardization processes within the framework of the green transition.	
Digital transition	In the proposal for a new Construction Products Regulation from 2023, which is expected to enter into force soon, mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of cement-based construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the digital transition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduction of machine-readable documents; • introduction of a digital passport of construction products; • introduction of 3D printing; 	In Regulation (EU) No 305/2011, and in its amendment from 2014, no mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the digital transition.
Digital transition	The research carried out and the subsequent analysis of the existing European and national legislation, in relation to construction products, in particular the considered Group A products: Cement and cement-based products, ascertained a legislative framework that does not appear to be an obstacle to the standardization processes within the framework of the digital transition.	

2.2. Regulatory framework for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope, with special focus on Romania

Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner ASRO.

2.2.1. Structure of the regulatory framework for the object of study for group B

2.2.1.1. Research on European Legislation for acts related to the object of study for group B

2.2.1.1.1. Research on Regulations

- Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 157/2014 of 30 October 2013 on the conditions for making a declaration of performance on construction products available on a website. Regulates the conditions for making a declaration of performance on construction products available on a website
- Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on market

surveillance and compliance of products and amending Directive 2004/42/EC and Regulations (EC) No 765/2008 and (EU) No 305/2011

- Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardization. This Regulation establishes rules about the cooperation between European standardization organizations, national standardization bodies, Member States, and the Commission, the establishment of European standards and European standardization deliverables for products and services in support of Union legislation and policies, the identification of ICT technical specifications eligible for referencing, the financing of European standardization and stakeholder participation in European standardization.
- Regulation (EC) No 765/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 July 2008 setting out the requirements for accreditation and repealing Regulation (EEC) No 339/93. This Regulation lays down rules on the organization and operation of accreditation of conformity assessment bodies performing conformity assessment activities.
- Proposal Regulations:
 - COM(2022) 144 final - Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011
 - COM(2022) 144 final - ANNEXES to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011. The Commission's 2016 implementation report on the CPR identified certain shortcomings in its implementation and a significant number of challenges, linked among others to standardization, simplification for micro-enterprises, market surveillance, and enforcement, deserving further examination and discussion. The evaluation of the CPR, opinions of the REFIT platform as well as Member States' and stakeholders' feedback pointed clearly to the shortcomings of the framework, hindering the functioning of the single market for the construction products, and therefore did not succeed in achieving the CPR's objectives.

2.2.1.1.2. Research on Delegated Decisions to Regulations

- Commission communication in the framework of the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC (Publication of titles and references of harmonized standards under Union harmonization legislation) OJ C 398, 28.10.2016, p. 7–56
- Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/1517 of 9 September 2022 amending Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 as regards the publication of references of European Assessment Documents for insulation made of loose-fill or compound granulated expanded cork or loose-fill granulated natural cork and rubber and other construction products C/2022/6304

2.2.1.1.3. Research on Directives

- Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast). This Directive promotes the improvement of the energy performance of buildings within the Union, considering outdoor climatic and local conditions, as well as indoor climate requirements and cost-effectiveness.
- Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast). This Directive establishes a common framework of measures to promote energy efficiency within the Union to ensure that the Union's targets on energy efficiency are met and enable further energy efficiency improvements. That common framework aims to contribute to the implementation of Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of

the European Parliament and of the Council (35) and to the Union's security of energy supply by reducing its dependence on energy imports, including fossil fuels.

- Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast). This Directive establishes a common framework for the promotion of energy from renewable sources. It sets a binding Union target for the overall share of energy from renewable sources in the Union's gross final consumption of energy in 2030. It also lays down rules on financial support for electricity from renewable sources, on self-consumption of such electricity, on the use of energy from renewable sources in the heating and cooling sector and the transport sector, on regional cooperation between Member States, and between Member States and third countries, on guarantees of origin, on administrative procedures and information and training. It also establishes sustainability and greenhouse gas emissions saving criteria for biofuels, bioliquids, and biomass fuels.

2.2.1.1.4. Research on Decision

- Commission Decision (EU) 2017/133 of 25 January 2017 on the maintenance with a restriction in the Official Journal of the European Union of the reference of harmonized standard EN 14342:2013 'Wood flooring and parquet: Characteristics, evaluation of conformity and marking' following Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and the Council
- European Parliament decision to raise no objections to the Commission delegated regulation of 30 October 2013 on the conditions for making a declaration of performance on construction products available on a website (C(2013)7086 — 2013/2928(DEA))
- COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS A New Industrial Strategy for Europe COM/2020/102 final
- COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE, AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Updating the 2020 New Industrial Strategy: Building a Stronger Single Market for Europe's Recovery COM/2021/350 final
- COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE, AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS An EU Strategy on Standardization Setting Global Standards in support of a resilient, green and digital EU Single Market COM/2022/31 final

2.2.1.1.5. Examination for other administrative acts

- Supporting study for the impact assessment of the CPR Review. This study provides input for the impact assessment (IA) that would accompany a revision of the Construction Products Regulation (CPR) if the Commission decides to revise it. The main purpose of this study is to collect evidence and complement the available evidence to analyze potential future options for EU legislation on construction products and to assess their possible impacts.
- COM(2016) 445 final - REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL on the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC

2.2.1.2. *Research on National legislation in the field of construction products for group B*

2.2.1.2.1. Research on Laws

- Law no. 10/1995 regarding quality in constructions, republished. This law establishes the construction quality system, which leads to the realization and operation of appropriate quality constructions, to protect people's lives, their goods, society, and the environment.

- Law no. 163 of 24 June 2015 regarding national standardization [23]. This law establishes the legal framework for the organization of national standardization activities, Romania's participation in European and international standardization and the necessary measures to apply the provisions provided for in Regulation (EU) no. 1025/2012.
- Law no. 372 of December 13, 2005 (*republished*) regarding the energy performance of buildings. The purpose of this law is to promote measures to increase the energy performance of buildings, taking into account external and site climatic conditions, indoor comfort requirements, and optimal level, from the point of view of costs and energy performance requirements, as well as to improve the appearance town planning of the localities. Increasing the energy performance of buildings by designing new buildings with reduced energy consumption and by thermal rehabilitation of existing buildings, as well as correctly informing building owners/managers through the energy performance certificate represent actions of major and general public interest in the context of saving energy in buildings, improvement of the built urban framework and environmental protection.

2.2.1.2.2. Research on Decision

According to the EU legislative framework, a European Regulation doesn't need to be transposed at the national level by a national law.

Nevertheless, in Romania, all the listed harmonized standards in OJEU under CPR 305/2011 are transposed and implemented by Romanian Ministry Decisions, as follows [24]:

- MDLPA Decision no. 833/2024 regarding the approval of the List containing the reference numbers of the Romanian standards that transpose harmonized European standards in the field of construction products, published in the Romanian Official Monitor, Part I, no. 192 on March 8, 2024
- MDLPA Decision no. 313/2023 regarding the approval of the List containing the reference numbers of the Romanian standards that transpose harmonized European standards in the field of construction products, published in the Romanian Official Monitor, Part I, no. 207 of March 13, 2023
- The list including the reference numbers of the Romanian standards in the field of construction products that represent the national versions of the harmonized European standards included in the updated list and published by the European Commission in the Official Journal of the European Union no. L 77 of 09.03.2019

DECISION no. 668 from September 13, 2017, Regarding the establishment of the conditions for the sale of construction products, issued by the Romanian Government, published in the Official Monitor no. 752 on September 20, 2017, and in force since November 19, 2017

The present decision establishes the conditions regarding the sale of construction products for their use in the execution of constructions that ensure the maintenance, for the entire duration of their existence, of the fundamental requirements applicable to constructions provided in Law no. 10/1995 regarding quality in constructions, republished. The provisions of this decision are addressed to producers/manufacturers, their authorized representatives, importers, distributors, and factors that compete in the conception, design, approval, execution, reception, use, and post-use of the constructions in which the construction products are incorporated, as well as the authorities of supervision of the construction products market.

2.2.1.2.3. Research on Regulations

- Regulation regarding technical approval in constructions - Annex no. 5 of Government Decision no. 766/1997 for the approval of some regulations regarding quality in construction, with subsequent amendments and additions, published in the Official Monitor, Part I, no. 829 on October 19, 2017
- GP 120-2013 Guide regarding the design and execution of green roofs on new and existing buildings [25].

2.2.1.2.4. Examination of other administrative acts

According to Decision no 668/217 a ***technical approval in constructions*** is the favorable technical

assessment, concretized in a written document, on the suitability for use following the fundamental requirements applicable to the constructions provided in Law no. 10/1995, republished, of some products or sets, referred to as construction products, which are not the subject of a technical specification.

Construction products for which there are no harmonized technical specifications or non-harmonized technical specifications are marketed accompanied by the declaration of conformity drawn up by the manufacturer based on technical approval in construction. The technical approval in construction is elaborated by a technical approval in construction body authorized by the Romanian Ministry of Development and Administration. The technical approval in construction is accompanied by the technical approval issued by the Permanent Technical Council for construction.

The necessary tests to develop the technical approval in construction are carried out in laboratories accredited according to SR ISO/CEI 17025:2005 and SR ISO/CEI 17025:2005/AC:2007 by a national accreditation body in the sense and according to the provisions of Regulation (EC) no. 765/2008, in laboratories notified for the evaluation of the performance related to the essential characteristics provided for in point 3 of Annex V to Regulation (EU) no. 305/2011 or in laboratories authorized by the State Construction Inspectorate - ISC; laboratories must be accredited/notified/authorized for the tests or tests provided for in the technical approval in question.

For bio-based products, the research performed by ASRO identified national technical approvals for sheep wool insulation, cellulose insulation, wood-based products for thermal insulation, and hemp-based products for thermal insulation.

Regarding construction products for which the manufacturer has drawn up a declaration of conformity based on technical approval in construction, the CE marking does not apply, so it is impossible to sell the assessed product across the border.

During the national consultation stage with the Romanian manufacturers of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope was noted that this national procedure hampers a lot of their activity due to the high costs and difficult bureaucracy.

2.2.2. Analysis of the regulatory framework for the object of study for group B

The added value of CE marking is that all EU countries must allow the selling of construction products bearing the CE mark. This means that public authorities cannot ask for any additional marks or certificates, let alone additional testing. Therefore, the manufacturer or the distributors of the product can trade the product in any country of the European Internal Market with the same documentation.

Together with the Declaration of Performance (DoP), this helps the customers and final users to check the performance of the product and compare it with other products under the same technical approach. When a manufacturer affixes the CE marking to a product it means that he is assuring that the performance of the product he is selling is the same as what he is declaring and that it has been obtained using the right European technical specification.

The CE marking contains certain essential information about the product and provides a link to other additional documents that also contain important information [26].

2 routes for CE marking can be followed by a manufacturer: CEN and EOTA. Brief description of the two routes is provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4. 2 possible routes for CE marking that can be followed by a manufacturer: CEN and EOTA.

For the CEN route, the manufacturer must check the Official Journal of the European Union and search for the last update of the publication of titles and references of harmonized standards, to identify the proper harmonized standard (hEN) for the specific product.

For bio-based products, the analysis performed at T.2.3 showed that there are 3 hENs, listed in the Table 13.

Table 13. List of hENs related to biobased products.

Standard reference	Standard Title	Responsible Body Technical Committee (TC)	EU Legislation
EN 13171:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13168:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood wool (WW) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13170:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made products of expanded cork (ICB) - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED

When the product is not in the scope of any harmonized standards the manufacturer must check if it is covered by one of the existing European Assessment Documents (EAD).

For bio-based products, the analysis performed at T.2.3 identified the EADs listed in Table 14.

Table 14. List of EADs related to biobased products.

No crt	EAD Number	EAD Title	OJEU	Status
1	040138-01-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres.	2018/C 417/07	Cited
2	041125-00-1201	In-situ loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres to be used in floor constructions without additional load-bearing structures	Decision (EU) 2023/424	Cited
3	040005-00-1201	Factory-made thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable or animal fibres	2016/C 054/14	Cited
4	040146-00-1201	Thermal insulation for buidlings made of straw bales	Decision (EU) 2023/1473	Cited
5	040313-00-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation product made of granulated expanded cork	2017/C 118/04	Cited
6	040369-01-1201	Insulation made of loose-fill or compound granulated expanded cork or loose-fill granulated natural cork and rubber	Decision (EU) 2022/1517	Cited
7	041389-00-1201	Boards made of agglomerated natural cork for thermal and acoustic insulation	Decision (EU) 2020/962	Cited
8	040456-00-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation material made of animal fibres	2017/C 343/06	Cited

The list of EADs can be found on the EOTA website [27].

If the product is included in the scope of one EAD, the manufacturer can ask a Technical Assessment Body (TAB) from the official registry of TABs to assess the product to affix the CE mark [28].

In case the product and the intended use or uses are not in the scope of any of the European Assessment Documents, the manufacturer can request a Technical Assessment Body to develop a European Assessment Document.

As shown in T2.3, hENs are developed under a mandate/standardization request given to CEN by the European Commission.

The legislative process and the long duration for developing an EN led to the current situation of the European standards being refused for citation in OJEU.

According to the EY's report on the assessment of HAS (Harmonized Standards Consultant) on CPR standards, as it is shown also in Figure 5, 100% of the evaluated standards were found to be in the category of *Lack of Compliance* and refused to be cited in OJEU [29].

Figure 5. Outcomes of assessment reports per sector since August 2022 [29].

The use of standards is mandatory when they are cited in the Official Journal of the European Union (OJEU).

Construction products covered by such standards shall bear the CE marking which indicates that they comply with their declared performance. Such products can then freely circulate within the single market. EU Member States are not allowed to require any additional marks, certificates, or testing. CPR does not set product requirements. EU Member States are responsible for the safety, environmental, and energy requirements applicable to buildings and civil engineering works.

The Report *from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products and repealing Council Directive 89/106/EEC, COM/2016/0445 final* identified certain shortcomings in its implementation and a significant number of challenges linked among others to standardization, simplification for micro-enterprises, market surveillance and enforcement, deserving further examination and discussion.

The evaluation of the Construction Products Regulation and the feedback received from EU authorities and stakeholders point clearly to shortcomings in its functioning. Its objectives have not been achieved and barriers to the free movement of construction products in the single market persist. This underperformance is due to several overarching issues, identified in the evaluation: a malfunctioning standardization process hampered implementation on the ground in EU countries complex and unclear rules, ambiguous relationship between the Regulation and other EU legislation, and/or national rules. Finally, the Regulation was not ready to contribute to broader policy priorities, particularly the green and digital transitions, because it lacks rules to this effect. There is a clear potential for making these rules more suitable for new business models and the data economy and making construction products considerably more sustainable and innovative.

The two general objectives of the CPR revision are to [30]:

1. achieve a well-functioning single market for construction products and to
2. contribute to the objectives of the green and digital transition, particularly the modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy.

The rationale behind the revision of the CPD was thus to:

- respond to clarification needs in the construction sector for the operators;
- reinforce the credibility of the system (particularly concerning increased harmonization of the procedures and criteria for designation by the national authorities of the notified bodies and better coordination of the market surveillance mechanisms);
- simplify the overall system.

In addition to the objectives of removing barriers to trade and setting up a common technical language, the CPR's objectives are to ensure legal clarity (including simplicity) and certainty, to keep costs incurred by manufacturers proportionate/fair (also for SMEs), and to provide appropriate means for public authorities at all levels to set performance requirements and to check compliance. From a financial point of view, it is difficult for small bio-based producers to get involved in the standardization activity and support their point of view.

The SME Strategy for a sustainable and digital Europe stressed the important role of the SMEs in driving the green transition and reiterated the need to equip them with instruments to understand and mitigate environmental risks, including in the construction sector.

'An EU strategy on Standardization: Setting global standards in support of a resilient, green and Digital EU Single Market' identified construction as one of the most pertinent areas where harmonized standards could improve competitiveness and reduce market barriers.

Revising the Construction Products Regulation can improve the overall functioning of the single market for construction products, particularly by addressing the current issues relevant to the standardization process and removing barriers to the single market, such as overlapping rules at EU or national level. This can increase legal certainty and make the conditions for competition fairer in the construction ecosystem while ensuring a high level of safety and protection for health and the environment. Improved market surveillance can

improve trust in the system across the EU. Finally, a revision enables the environmental sustainability of construction products to be improved.

The revision of the Regulation aims to improve the single market for construction products. It will ensure a level playing field for all producers, especially small and medium businesses in all EU countries. Producers will probably meet extended obligations to uptake their products to the market, but at the same time, they will have more business opportunities. Simplification requirements specifically aim to provide micro-companies with simplified procedures when assessing and verifying performance. Moreover, EU governments will be empowered to exempt certain micro-businesses from the Regulation's obligations.

The intended planned work-sharing and the technical fine-tuning with the Sustainable Products Initiative will avoid unnecessary burdens for businesses of all sizes. A better functioning single market will give construction companies access to a broader choice of products. Overall, producers and the construction ecosystem will benefit from the revision.

Three main types of benefits could be expected to arise from the implementation of the CPR:

- Direct benefits:
 - Cost savings for manufacturers and distributors:
 - cost savings are generated because the testing and certification for each national market are no longer necessary once the CE-marking is applied;
 - the possibility of providing an electronic version of the DoP contributes to the reduction of the cost burden;
 - simplified procedures for specific types of tests (test sharing under Article 36), specific types of companies (micro-enterprises under Article 37) and specific types of products (custom-made products under Article 38).
 - Improved provision of information and improved safety along the value chain (manufacturers, distributors, end-users) through the DoP and CE marking. Benefits would translate into improved safety due to better communication on the technical performance of the construction products; for professional end-users, improved information about the performances of the construction product, improved comparison of products thanks to the harmonized way of declaring the performance as well as increased availability and choice of products.
- Indirect benefits:
 - New market opportunities in the Internal Market – benefits associated with business opportunities created or facilitated by the CPR. New market opportunities can create benefits in terms of increased turnover, reduced trade barriers, and increased competition for economic operators in the home and EU markets.
- Ultimate (long-term) impact of the Regulation:
 - Improved information about the conditions for better hygiene, health, and environment - potential impacts related to Basic Work Requirements 3 and 7 concerning environmental protection and sustainability.

2.2.3. Conclusions

2.2.3.1. General conclusions

The analysis of National legislation highlighted the need for the emergence, simplification, and adaptation of the legal framework in bio-based products for the insulation of the building's envelope at current needs and opportunities for implementing environmental and digital transition policies. Producers of sustainable materials should be supported by the authorities to be competitive in the market and be on the same level as producers of classic materials. Regulations in this area must ensure effective market surveillance to

encourage more natural product manufacturers to enter the market.

2.2.3.2. Specific focus on the relation between the existing legislative framework and the twin transition

The relation between the existing legislative framework and the twin transition is summarized in Table 15, where we list a series of enabling features and barriers related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”, specifically the “green transition” and the “digital transition”.

Table 15. List of legislative barriers and enabling features related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”

Framework	Enabling features	Barriers
Green and digital transition at the European level	<p>The revised CPR emphasizes the need for digital solutions to reduce existing administrative burdens, including a construction products database or system. The EU has also highlighted that the revised CPR will need to align with circular economy principles – promoting the sustainability, durability, and recyclability of products.</p> <p>The new Construction Products Regulation will equip constructors to be key actors of the green and digital transitions. Construction products of the future will require the extraction of fewer resources and generate less pollution and less waste, so buildings will not only shelter us from extreme climate conditions but also help fight climate change.</p>	<p>Manufacturers have expressed concerns about bearing a far greater practical, administrative, and financial burden than presently, with additional obligations regarding the design, manufacture, declaration, labelling, and repair of a broad range of construction products.</p> <p>Industry bodies and manufacturers have expressed concerns about the protection of intellectual property rights and the confidentiality of data held on databases owned and controlled by others.</p>
Green and digital transition at the National level	<p>The existing national legislation provides requirements for putting on the market construction products that are the subject of harmonized technical specifications, for putting on the market construction products that are the subject of a non-harmonized technical specification as well as requirements for putting on the market construction products that are the subject of a technical approval in construction and sustains the measures needed for the twin transition by promoting the use of construction products from natural resources.</p>	<p>The green transition requires much more investment than the world currently provides, but reaching the levels needed is not impossible. There are no support programs for economic sectors and target groups affected by the green transition.</p> <p>National digital transformation is a complex process involving multiple stakeholders and their interests, covering various domains such as health care, education, transportation, energy, environment, governance, and others. It involves significant investment, the need to address complex ethical and legal issues, and demands continuous adaptation to remain relevant in the ever-changing digital landscape. Navigating through the process is likely to be challenging, requiring the use of appropriate tools, and comprehensive and coordinated approaches. The absence of regulations to promote or enforce digitization in the industry contributes to the stagnation of progress.</p>
Green and digital transition at the standardization level		<p>The twin transition is hampered by the lack of a standardized framework for new bio-based products used as raw material. There is no in force legislation supporting the standardization framework, both at European and National level and this hampers the transition to green and</p>

		digital for new products from natural resources and the use of digital technologies.
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3. Standardization context

In this chapter, a specific analysis of the regulatory standardization is performed. This study has been performed within the activities of the Task T2.3.

As already anticipated, within the framework of the AFCOS project, two different product families have been analyzed:

- group A: Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.),
- group B: bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

Specific attention has been put on Bulgarian market for the low carbon cement products and on the Romanian market for the bio-based products.

The work described in this chapter presents a common structure applied to the two product families, each of them focused on a reference market (Bulgaria on the one hand and Romania on the other hand). Since these are distinct products, there is not full overlap. Similarly to chapter 0, in order to maintain consistency, it was preferred to report separately the analyses carried out on low carbon cement products referring to the Bulgarian market on the one hand, and on bio-based products referring to the Romanian market on the other hand.

For this reason, this chapter is divided in two separate sections.

- A. Section 3.1 will concentrate on the standardization framework of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products, with special focus on Bulgaria. Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner BDS.
- B. Section 3.2 will concentrate on the standardization framework of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope, with special focus on Romania. Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner ASRO.

3.1. Standardization framework for low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products

Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner BDS.

3.1.1. Research on European and international standards and other harmonized technical specifications

3.1.1.1. *Objects of research*

Groups of standards

1. Product standards

- Cements
- Concrete mixtures – fresh and dry
- Concrete products
- Mortars – fresh and dry mixtures
- Grout
- Products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures
- Lightweight aggregate concrete products
- Autoclaved aerated concrete products

2. Test methods standards
 - Mechanical characteristics of concrete products
 - Chemical analyses of cement and low carbon cement
 - Carbon metric methods
 - Methods for carbon dioxide capture

3. European Assessment Documents EAD

- Special type of cements

3.1.1.2. Structure of researching

Research on European and international existing standards. Completeness and weaknesses of existing standards.

- General review on each group of standards.
- Deeper research on selected standards from each group and EADs in terms of missing requirements and/or test methods for low carbon cements and low carbon concrete products

Identification of potential barriers to development of new standards for new construction materials and products

Special attention was given to the impact of different standards on the twin transition of construction – do they enable or rather hamper the deployment of “greener” or “circular” materials in the sector?

3.1.2. Analysis

3.1.2.1. Introduction to methodology

In order to identify all the relevant European, international and national standards for cement and cement-based products, as concrete products, mortar and grout, BDS performed a thorough desk research using:

- CEN-CENELEC Project online platform (<https://experts.cen.eu/>) gives an overview of CEN and CENELEC Work Programme, including monitoring functionalities for following-up the work within Technical Bodies and provides access to CEN Working area (submission of CEN TC decisions) and foreign Partner standards implementation.
- ISO Portal - technical committees working area (<https://sd.iso.org/home/>),
- ISO search standards (<https://www.iso.org/standards.html>)
- EOTA (<https://www.eota.eu/eads>)
- BDS (<https://bds-bg.org/>)

With special attention on impact of different standards on the twin transition of construction sector and existing situation in cement and concrete industry, we should note that:

For buildings, roads, tunnels, bridges, dams or skyscrapers – concrete is an indispensable part of construction. But let’s not fool ourselves: concrete doesn’t have the best carbon footprint. And yet, it will continue to play an important role in construction in the future – because few other building materials have such good structural properties. This is why the continuous decarbonisation of concrete construction is a key element of the sustainability strategy.

Standard concrete contains cement as a binding agent. And the production of cement alone is responsible for about 6-7 % of the world’s greenhouse gas emissions. That is four times as much as all of the global air traffic combined. That’s because the production of cement involves the use of cement clinker, made from limestone, sand and clay, which is burned at high temperatures involving a high energy consumption. Most of the carbon emissions are caused by the chemical reaction that takes place in the process, as the deacidification of the limestone produces unavoidable, resource-related greenhouse gas emissions.

Low-carbon concretes are concretes that have a lower Global Warming Potential (GWP) compared to standard concretes. About 80 % of the greenhouse gas emissions of common standard concretes come from the Portland cement clinker used in its production. The key to reducing emissions here is therefore to lower the percentage of clinker used.

Three alternatives to reduce or replace the cement clinker content in concrete:

- Reducing the cement content of concrete
- Using low-clinker cement
- Using alternative binders with a low Global Warming Potential [31].

BDS made an Analysis on the base of identified Technical Committees for cement, concrete and cement-based products in CEN and ISO.

CEN/TC 51 Cement and building limes

The scope of this Technical Committee is Standardization in the field of definitions and terminology, specifications and methods of test for cements and limes used in building and civil engineering.

CEN/TC 104 Concrete and related products

CEN/TC 104 deals with the standardization of provisions for concrete and related products, in particular with respect to properties and requirements for:

- fresh and hardened concrete;
- production and delivery of fresh concrete;
- constituent materials of concrete, e.g. mixing water, additions and admixtures;
- sheaths for prestressing tendons; grout for prestressing tendons;
- fibres for use in concrete;
- execution of concrete structures;
- production and execution of sprayed concrete;
- products for the protection and repair of concrete structures.

Additionally relevant test methods and provisions for the assessment of conformity for the products and procedures mentioned above are standardized.

Today, concrete is one of the mostly used material in the building industry which is applied to almost all kinds of buildings and civil engineering works. Due to a permanent technical development and its great flexibility of mechanical and physical properties it is applied for structural and non-structural purpose from simple housing to sophisticated long span bridge systems. Thus, the production of fresh and hardened concrete as well as the production of its constituent materials covers an important proportion of the entire market in the construction field.

Although the production of concrete and the erection of concrete structures is a rather experienced technique with long-term tradition in various countries, a permanent development with respect to concrete technology, advanced production methods and the use of modern and refined constituent materials is taking place.

This development concerns not only the improvement of concrete performance and quality under economical aspects, but it is increasingly influenced by environmental demands required by the society [32].

CEN/TC 125 Masonry (mortars)

The scope of CEN/TC 125 is "Standardization in the field of masonry units of clay, calcium silicate, dense aggregate concrete, lightweight aggregate concrete, autoclaved aerated concrete, natural stone, manufactured stone, mortar for masonry, ancillary components for masonry and associated test methods."

Masonry products covered by CEN/TC 125 are:

- masonry units, comprising bricks and blocks;
- mortar, with the exception of site made mortars;
- ancillary components, including ties, straps, hangers, lintels and bed joint reinforcement [33].

CEN/TC 177 Prefabricated reinforced components of autoclaved aerated concrete or light-weight aggregate concrete with open structure

CEN/TC 229 Precast concrete products

- Industrially prefabricated concrete products are currently used in all Europe for all kinds of constructions (buildings, bridges, floorings, environment, etc).
- They are used in the private or public domain.
- They are produced in highly automated factories.
- The sector mainly consists of small and medium-sized enterprises.
- For structural products the implementation of EUROCODES creates a common design rule, which is taken into account by the relevant product standards.
- Thermal performance of buildings, environmental declaration, sustainability of resources, the construction works foot-print, durability and fire safety engineering are taken into account [34].

ISO/TC 59 Buildings and civil engineering works

The scope of ISO/TC 59 is the standardization of terminology, organization of information in building and civil engineering processes, geometric requirements for building, building elements and components including modular coordination, general rules for joints, tolerances and fits; performance requirements of buildings and building elements.

The need for common terminology, rules of information exchanges, measurement techniques and material descriptors increase as globalization and international trade expands.

The construction industry is well known as one of the largest industrial employers, and one of its particular characteristics is its function as a generator of employment. The so-called "multiplier effect" is such that 1 person working in the construction industry gives rise to 2 further jobs in other sectors. In Europe, this means almost 2 million firms directly employing a work force of 11 million. In other regions with less automation, construction industry employs even more people and is usually a local activity [35].

ISO/TC 265 Carbon dioxide capture, transportation, and geological storage

The intent of ISO/TC 265 is to prepare International Standards for the design, construction, operation, environmental planning and management, risk management, quantification, monitoring and verification, and related activities in the field of carbon dioxide capture, transportation, and geological storage. The focus is on CO₂ being emitted from stationary point sources. Existing standards will be utilized where possible.

The focus of the committee's work is on the capture, transport and geological storage of anthropogenic CO₂ generated from industrial activities. Example industries include power generation, cement plants, gas plants,

petroleum refineries, chemical and fertilizer productions, and iron and steel plants. The work of the technical committee does not encompass mobile emitters of CO₂ [36].

Regarding the relationship with the EU legislation, the following aspects were taken into account in the present analysis:

The first draft list, the extensive list, resulting from the research comprises of 172 standards, including product standards with requirements and test method standards from defined groups: cement, concrete mixtures, precast concrete products, mortars for masonry, grout, products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures, lightweight aggregate concrete products, autoclaved aerated concrete products and EADs for special types cements. For all 172 items it was necessary to include the following information, under the standardized format (see Annex 1 and Annex 2).

The structure of analysed standards is shown on Figure 6.

Figure 6. Analyzed 172 selected standards.

The biggest group is the group of product standards. It should be noted, that almost all standards for precast concrete products of CEN/TC 229 are harmonized standards, referenced in OJ. The correlation between harmonized and non-harmonized standards is shown on Figure 7.

Figure 7. All product standards.

According to the structure of researching (see 4.2) we selected standards from each group for deeper research in terms of completeness and weakness of standards regarding the purposes of AFCOS Project (see Annex 2). The number of the selected standards for deeper research is 77 in total. The structure of this group is shown on Figure 8.

Figure 8. Researched standards.

3.1.2.2. Analysis of product standards

The product standards for structural products are selected in 7 groups. Figure 9 gives the structure of selected 15 product standards for which deeper research were performed.

Figure 9. Analysed 15 selected product standards from each group.

From 15 selected standards 10 are harmonized and 5 are non-harmonized, see Figure 10.

Figure 10. Analysed 15 selected product standards

Group 1 Cement

EN 197-1:2011 *Cement - Part 1: Composition, specifications and conformity criteria for common cements*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 176 OJ publication date: 19.06.2012

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

EN 197-5:2021 *Cement - Part 5: Portland-composite cement CEM II/C-M and Composite cement CEM VI*

EN 197-6:2003 *Cement - Part 6: Cement with recycled building materials*

Analysis of the group: EN 197-1 is the main standard for entire group of cements. It is referenced in all other standards for cement and cement-based products regarding chemical composition. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. EN 197-5 is now the only standard which allows the use of cements with decreased content of clinker. EN 197-6 allows the use of cement with recycled concrete fines. The cement types and strength classes defined in 197-5 and 197-6 allow the specifier and/or the user to fulfil objectives of sustainability for cement-based constructions and to minimize the use of natural resources in accordance with local conditions of production.

In EN 197-5 and 197-6 it is noted: “The performance tests available at the time of publication of this document (i.e. for the determination of setting time, strength, soundness and heat of hydration) have been included in this document. In addition, work is being carried out by CEN/TC 51 to identify any additional tests which are needed to specify further performance characteristics of cement. Until further performance tests are available, it is necessary that the choice of cement, especially the type and/or strength class in relation to the requirements for durability depending on exposure class and type of construction in which it is incorporated, follows the appropriate standards and/or regulations for concrete, mortar, grout, etc. valid in the place of use.”

Weakness: Need to include possibility for use in construction low-carbon cements and cements with recycled concrete fines. Need to extent the field of application of low-carbon cements and cements with recycled materials.

Potential barriers: The main standard EN 197-1 limits cement composition for 27 types common cements. Need for development of performance-based standards, including parts for special types cements. Shifting

to a performance-based cement standards for all common cements will strengthen the internal market for construction products. Shifting to performance-based cement standards will – finally – align cement standards with the CPR, strengthening and deepening the European internal market. This will create new opportunities for industry and green growth. Shifting to performance-based cement standards is crucial to foster innovation and accelerate decarbonization in cement production in Europe. This is vital at a time when cement industry is not on track to meet net-zero by 2050.

Group 2 Concrete mixtures

EN 206:2013+A1:2021 *Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity*

Analysis of the group: This is the main standard for concrete production and it is referenced in all standard for fresh and hardened mixtures, precast concrete products etc. It is based on EN 197-1 regarding use of cement as basic constituent of concrete.

Weakness: The standard EN 206:2013+A2:2021 establishes restriction on minimum cement content and limiting values for composition and properties of concrete. The cement shell conforms to EN 197-1 in which the concept for low-carbon cement is not establish.

Potential barriers: Need for revision of EN 206. Revision is now starting and EN 206 will be divided into two parts: EN 206-1 *Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity — Part 1: Performance, requirements, factory production control and assessment criteria for individual values* and EN 206-2 *Concrete - Specification, performance, production and conformity - Part 2: Conformity assessment and certification*. The new drafts are in very early stage 10.99.

Group 3 Precast concrete products

EN 13225:2013 *Precast concrete products - Linear structural elements*

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

EN 15050:2007+A1:2012 *Precast concrete products - Bridge elements*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 176 OJ publication date: 19.06.2012

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

EN 13369:2023 *Common rules for precast concrete products*

Analysis of the group: The standards for precast concrete products are developed in a uniform stile. They are relatively old standards and they not reflect the new concept for sustainable and innovative construction products, as low-carbon concrete. Only in EN 13369:2023 the concept for the performance-based approach (PBA) is developed. As mentioned by the Joint chairmen Panel, “another benefit of Performance-Based Approach for the producer is the possibility to use easier the potential of cementitious constituents”. This point is particularly important in today's context characterized by the need to go further toward low carbon concrete.

All standards for precast concrete products are harmonized standards to CPR and include procedure for conformity assessment and CE marking.

EN 13369:2023 is intended to outline the general common specifications applicable to a large variety of precast concrete products manufactured in a factory environment. It acts as a reference standard for other standards to enable a more consistent approach to standardization in the field of precast concrete products and to reduce the variations brought about by a large number of standards produced in parallel by different groups of experts. The performance-based approach (PBA) considers not only the data related to the composition of the concrete but relies also on physical and chemical properties in relation with the environmental conditions of a concrete structure. The PBA is mentioned in EN 206 as one of the possible

approaches to define a durable concrete in a given environment.

Weakness: The requirements for precast concrete products do not include any requirements about use of low-carbon concrete in production of these products. Need of new requirements.

Potential barriers: It is necessary to revise the standards for precast concrete products so that they incorporate the principles developed in EN 13369:2023 and allow the application of Performance-Based Approach. Insofar as the standards for precast concrete products refer to EN 206, it should be revised to allow the use of low carbon cement.

Group 4 Products of autoclaved aerated concrete

EN 12602:2016 *Prefabricated reinforced components of autoclaved aerated concrete*

305/2011 OJ reference: C 76/40 OJ publication date: 10.03.2017

Group 5 Products of lightweight aggregate concrete

EN 1520:2011 *Prefabricated reinforced components of lightweight aggregate concrete with open structure with structural or non-structural reinforcement*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 246 OJ publication date: 24.08.2011

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

Analysis of the two groups: The standards for autoclaved aerated concrete/lightweight aggregate concrete products should be used in building construction for:

- a) Structural elements: loadbearing wall components; retaining wall components; roof components; floor components; linear components (beams and piers).
- b) Non-structural elements: non-loadbearing wall components (partition walls); cladding components (without fixtures) intended to be used for external facades of buildings; small box culverts used to form channels for the enclosure of services; components for noise barriers.

Components covered by these standards are only intended to be subjected to predominantly non-dynamic actions, unless special measures are introduced in the relevant clauses of this European Standard.

The standards in the group are harmonized to CPR and include procedure for conformity assessment and CE marking.

Weakness: The requirements for products of autoclaved aerated concrete/lightweight aggregate concrete do not include any requirements about use low-carbon concrete in production of these products. Need of new requirements.

Potential barriers: Need to revise the standards for products of autoclaved aerated concrete/lightweight aggregate concrete so that they incorporate the principles developed in EN 13369:2023 and allow the application of Performance-Based Approach.

Group 6 Products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures

БДС EN 1504-3:2006 *Products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures - Definitions, requirements, quality control and evaluation of conformity - Part 3: Structural and non-structural repair*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 304 OJ publication date: 13.12.2006

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

Analysis of the group: This series of European Standards specifies requirements for the identification, performance (including durability) and safety of products and systems to be used for the structural and non-structural repair of concrete structures.

The European Standards cover repair mortars and concretes, possibly used in conjunction with other products and systems, to restore and/or to replace defective concrete and to protect reinforcement, necessary to extend the service life of a concrete structure exhibiting deterioration.

The standard EN 1504-3 is harmonized to CPR and includes procedure for conformity assessment and CE marking.

Weakness: The requirements for products and systems for the protection and repair of concrete structures do not include any requirements about use low-carbon concrete in production of these products. Need of new requirements.

Potential barriers: The revision of EN 197-1 and EN 206 should be reflected in future revision of entire series EN 1504.

Group 7 Mortars, binders, screed materials, fibre-cement products

EN 14487-1:2022 *Sprayed concrete - Part 1: Definitions, specifications and conformity*

EN 998-2:2016 *Specification for mortar for masonry - Part 2: Masonry mortar*

305/2011 OJ reference: C 267 OJ publication date: 11.08.2017

EN 13282-1:2013 *Hydraulic road binders - Part 1: Rapid hardening hydraulic road binders - Composition, specifications and conformity criteria*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 186 OJ publication date: 28.06.2013

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

EN 13813:2002 *Screed material and floor screeds - Screed material - Properties and requirements*

89/106/EEC OJ reference: C 320 OJ publication date: 20.12.2002

305/2011 OJ reference: C 259 OJ publication date: 8.08.2014

EN 492:2012+A2:2018 *Fibre-cement slates and fittings - Product specification and test methods*

305/2011 OJ reference: L 77/82 OJ publication date: 20.03.2019

Analysis of the group: The group of standards for mortars, binders, screed materials, fibre-cement products etc. are based on EN 206 and EN 197-1. They are only operable with product standards for constituent materials (i.e. cement, aggregates, additions, admixtures, fibres and mixing water) and related test methods.

The requirements for sprayed concrete do not include any requirements about use of low-carbon concrete in production. Need of new requirements.

EN 13813 defines for fresh screed material the performance related to setting time, consistency, pH value and for the hardened screed material, compressive strength, flexural strength, wear resistance, surface hardness, resistance to indentation, resistance to rolling wheel, shrinkage and swelling, modulus of elasticity, bond strength, impact resistance, reaction to fire, acoustic performance, thermal resistance and chemical resistance.

In EN 492 fibre-cement slates and fittings shall consist essentially of cement or a calcium silicate formed by chemical reaction of a siliceous and a calcareous material, reinforced by fibres. The cement shall comply with EN 197-1 or with technical specifications relevant in the country of use.

Weakness: All standards has taken EN 197-1 as a basis. Need for revision and new requirements.

Potential barriers: The revision of EN 197-1 and EN 206 should be reflected in future revision of entire group of standards for mortars, binders, screed materials, fibre-cement products etc.

Common problems for all harmonized standards in the field of Regulation 305/2011

Since early 2019, no standard in support of the CPR has been cited in the OJEU

This situation reflects the current situation of the hEN standards and the present critical issues that the manufacturers from the construction industry are dealing with. Many of the cited harmonized standards are withdrawn and the new ones published by CEN standards are not cited in OJ. The manufacturers use withdrawn standards for purposes of assessment constancy of performance of construction products and CE marking. This problem shall be sold with new CPR.

3.1.2.3. Analysis of test method standards

3.1.2.3.1. Analysis of EN test methods

The structure of the EN test methods group is shown on Figure 11.

Figure 11. Analysed 50 selected EN test methods standards.

Series EN 196 Methods of testing cement

Part 1: Determination of strength

Part 2: Chemical analysis of cement

Part 3: Determination of setting times and soundness

Part 4: Quantitative determination of constituents

Part 6: Determination of fineness

Part 8: Heat of hydration - Solution method

Part 9: Heat of hydration - Semi-adiabatic method

Analysis of the series: EN 197-1 is the main standard for the entire group of cements. It is referenced in all other standards for cement and cement-based products regarding chemical composition. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 196 is developed for the purposes of cements of series EN 197.

The series EN 196 covers all necessary test methods for testing cement.

Weakness: According to EN 197-6:2023 the performance tests available at the time of publication of the document (i.e. for the determination of setting time, strength, soundness and heat of hydration) have been included in this document. In addition, work is being carried out by CEN/TC 51 to identify any additional tests which are needed to specify further performance characteristics of cement. Until further performance tests are available, it is necessary that the choice of cement, especially the type and/or strength class in relation to the requirements for durability depending on exposure class and type of construction in which it is incorporated, follows the appropriate standards and/or regulations for concrete, mortar, grout, etc. valid in the place of use. Need of new/revised methods.

Potential barriers: The series 196 is based on EN 197. After the revision of EN 197, it should be established for which characteristics of the new cements the existing standards of the EN 196 series should be developed and/or supplemented.

Series EN 12350 Testing fresh concrete

Part 2: Slump test

Part 3: Vebe test

Part 4: Degree of compatibility

Part 5: Flow table test

Part 6: Density

Part 7: Air content - Pressure methods

Part 8: Self-compacting concrete - Slump-flow test

Part 9: Self-compacting concrete - V-funnel test

Part 10: Self-compacting concrete - L box test

Part 11: Self-compacting concrete - Sieve segregation test

Part 12: Self-compacting concrete - J-ring test

Analysis of the series: EN 206 is the main standard for concrete. It is referenced in all other standards for concrete and precast concrete products. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 12350 are developed for the purposes of concrete conforming to EN 206.

The series EN 12350 covers all necessary test methods for testing fresh concrete.

Weakness: Need of new/revised methods for testing low-carbon fresh concrete.

Potential barriers: The series 12350 is based on EN 206. After the revision of EN 206, it should be established for which characteristics of the new concretes the existing standards of the EN 12350 series should be developed and/or supplemented

Series EN 12390 Testing hardened concrete

Part 3: Compressive strength of test specimens

Part 5: Flexural strength of test specimens

Part 6: Tensile splitting strength of test specimens

Part 7: Density of hardened concrete

Part 8: Depth of penetration of water under pressure

Part 9: Freeze-thaw resistance with de-icing salts - Scaling

Part 10: Determination of the carbonation resistance of concrete at atmospheric levels of carbon dioxide

Part 11: Determination of the chloride resistance of concrete, unidirectional diffusion

Part 13: Determination of secant modulus of elasticity in compression

Part 14: Semi-adiabatic method for the determination of heat released by concrete

Part 15: Adiabatic method for the determination of heat released by concrete

Part 16: Determination of the shrinkage of concrete

Part 17: Determination of creep of concrete in compression

Analysis of the series: EN 206 is the main standard for concrete. It is referenced in all other standards for concrete and precast concrete products. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 12390 is developed for the purposes of concrete conforming to EN 206.

The series EN 12390 covers all necessary test methods for testing hardened concrete.

Weakness: Need of new/revised methods for testing low-carbon fresh concrete.

Potential barriers: The series 12390 is based on EN 206. After the revision of EN 206, it should be established for which characteristics of the new concretes the existing standards of the EN 12390 series should be developed and/or supplemented

Series EN 1015 Methods of test for mortar for masonry

Part 1: Determination of particle size distribution

Part 3: Determination of consistence of fresh mortar

Part 6: Determination of bulk density of fresh mortar

Part 7: Determination of air content of fresh mortar

Part 9: Determination of workable life and correction time of fresh mortar

Part 10: Determination of dry bulk density of hardened mortar

Part 11: Determination of flexural and compressive strength of hardened mortar

Part 12: Determination of adhesive strength of hardened rendering and plastering mortars on substrates

Part 17: Determination of water-soluble chloride content of fresh mortars

Analysis of the series: EN 998-1 and EN 998-2 are the standards with requirements for masonry mortars. They are based on EN 197-1. It is referenced in all other standards for cement and cement-based products regarding chemical composition. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 1015 are developed for the purposes of cements of series EN 998.

The series EN 1015 covers all necessary test methods for mortar for masonry.

Weakness: Need of new/ revised methods for testing low-carbon fresh concrete.

Potential barriers: The series 196 is based on EN 197. The revision of EN 197 shall reflect on all standards for cement-based products and test methods.

Series EN 1170 Test methods for glass-fibre reinforced cement

Part 1: Measuring the consistency

Part 4, 5: Measuring bending strength

Part 6: Determination of the absorption of water

Part 8: Cyclic weathering type test

Analysis of the series: EN 197-1 is the main standard for the entire group of cements. It is referenced in all other standards for cement and cement-based products regarding chemical composition. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 1170 is developed for the purposes of glass-fibre cements according EN 197. The series EN 1170 covers all necessary test methods for glass-fibre reinforced cement

Weakness: Need of new/ revised methods for testing glass-fibre reinforced low-carbon cement.

Potential barriers: The series 1170 is based on EN 197. The revision of EN 197 shall reflect on all standards for cement-based products and test methods.

Series EN 14488 Testing sprayed concrete

Part 2: Compressive strength of young sprayed concrete

Part 3: Flexural strengths (first peak, ultimate and residual) of fibre reinforced beam specimens

Part 4: Bond strength of cores by direct tension

Part 5: Determination of energy absorption capacity of fibre reinforced slab specimens

Part 6: Thickness of concrete on a substrate

Analysis of the series: The standards from series 14487 are the standards with requirements for sprayed concrete. They are based on EN 206 and EN 197-1. It is referenced in all other standards for cement and cement-based products regarding chemical composition. It is relatively old standard and the new concept regarding low-carbon cements is not concerned. The series EN 14488 is developed for the purposes of cements of series EN 14487.

The series EN 14488 covers all necessary test methods for sprayed concrete.

Weakness: Need of new/ revised methods for testing sprayed low-carbon concrete.

Potential barriers: The series 14488 is based on EN 206. The revision of EN 206 shall reflect on all standards for cement-based products and test methods.

3.1.2.3.2. Analysis of ISO test methods

Carbon dioxide capture

ISO/TR 27912:2016 *Carbon dioxide capture. Carbon dioxide capture systems, technologies and processes*

ISO 27913:2016 *Carbon dioxide capture, transportation and geological storage. Pipeline transportation systems*

ISO 27914:2017 *Carbon dioxide capture, transportation and geological storage. Geological storage*

ISO/TR 27922:2021 *Carbon dioxide capture. Overview of carbon dioxide capture technologies in the cement industry*

Analysis of the series: There is two TR, that describe the principles and information necessary to clarify the CO₂ capture system and provide stakeholders with the guidance and knowledge necessary for the development of a series of standards for CO₂ capture and provide an overview of technologies that are under development to capture carbon dioxide (CO₂) that is generated during cement manufacture.

The documents provide requirements for determining and reporting a carbon metric of an existing building, associated with the operation of the building. It sets out methods for the calculation, reporting and communication of a set of carbon metrics for GHG emissions arising from the measured energy use during the operation of an existing building, the measured user-related energy use, and other relevant GHG emissions and removals. These carbon metrics are separated into three measures designated CM1, CM2, and CM3, specify additional requirements and recommendations not covered in existing pipeline standards for the transportation of CO₂ streams from the capture site to the storage facility where it is primarily stored in a geological formation or used for other purposes (e.g. for EOR or CO₂ use) and establish requirements and recommendations for the geological storage of CO₂ streams, the purpose of which is to promote commercial, safe, long-term containment of carbon dioxide in a way that minimizes risk to the environment, natural resources, and human health

Weakness: Need actualization in accordance with the advanced requirements for building construction. Need to include advanced technologies (additional units) for decarbonization.

Potential barriers: Lack of sufficient number of established technologies and test methods, representing useful limits for implementation.

3.1.2.4. Analysis of EADs for special types of cements

EAD 150001-00-0301 Calcium sulphoaluminate based cement

EAD 150002-00-0301 Calcium aluminate based refractory cement

EAD 150003-00-0301 High strength cement

EAD 150004-00-0301 Rapid hardening sulfate resistant calcium sulphoaluminate based cement

EAD 150007-00-0301 Portland-pozzolana cement for use in tropical conditions

EAD 150008-00-0301 Rapid setting cement

EAD 150009-00-0301 Blast Furnace Cement CEM III/A with assessment of sulfate resistance (SR) and optional with low effective alkali content (LA) and/or low heat of hydration (LH)

EAD 150036-00-0301 Fluoraluminate rapid setting cement

These EAD's documents include different types of cement intended to be used in different conditions. "Calcium sulphoaluminate based cement" is refractory cement made up of calcium aluminates and alumina-rich materials with high compressive strength and high refractoriness, the "Rapid hardening sulfate resistant calcium sulphoaluminate based cement" is a hydraulic binder with rapid hardening features and sulfate resistance property and the "Blast furnace cement CEM III/A (SR/LH/LA)" is characterized by an evidently high resistance against sulfate attack on concrete and in case for the characteristic "LA" to prevent a damaging alkali silica reaction in the concrete.

Need for requirements and established test results.

Potential barriers: Need specification of composition materials, including recycling materials, limits of useful

area. Possibility to include these specifications in European standards.

3.1.2.5. Analysis of the results of the Multistakeholder Working Group for legislation and standardization research

BDS – Bulgarian Institute for Standardization identified the national stakeholders among industry, researchers, and authority, and invited them to attend the meeting sessions. The main purpose of the meeting sessions was to have the multistakeholder national research groups` feedback for use of cement and cement-based products with low CO2 print. The participants are from cement industry, researches and authority, responsible for construction products market.

The conclusions of the multi-stakeholders working group are:

- the concrete producers should have better knowledge on the new cements, as in Bulgaria the new cements are not very well known yet, which can be taken into account when developing the trainings within the project;
- need of new/ revised European standards for low-carbon cement and low-carbon concrete products developed under an accelerated procedure;
- need to work on the awareness of manufacturers and participants in the construction process, as well as on changing their attitudes;
- lack of sufficient tests for new types cements and concrete; new cements should be tested to prove that they have good characteristics and can be applied in construction
- the target group of the trainings should be not only the concrete producers (who do not have the base, experience and capacity), but also the construction companies and the designers;
- changing attitudes towards new trends among all participants in the construction process is extremely important, because the old state standards contain specific formulas that are directly applied, and the new standards do not offer a ready-made recipe;
- lack of a technical basis for the production of concrete in accordance with the new requirements (lack of a sufficient number of silos at the concrete producers)
- the main problem of construction companies is lower early strength of concrete, because this slows down the demoulding and, respectively, the whole process. The application of the new standards will invariably require increased control throughout the construction process.
- within the planned trainings under the project, more emphasis should be placed on the explanatory part - what are the general definitions and the next steps concerning all participants in the construction process, in order to be prepared for the new requirements. It would be good to include as a target group also the building control experts who carry out inspections - for example through interviews and meetings, because they can have a positive influence, having the closest contact with the concrete batching plant.
- the application of the new standard requires updating a number of other documents – such as the Public Procurement Law, which should impose specific environmental requirements.

3.1.3. Conclusions and recommendations based on the analysis of the results.

3.1.3.1. Identification of weaknesses

The analysis of standards for cement and cement-based products shows the following weaknesses and problems in existing standards and standardization documents:

- Lack of standards for cement and cement-based products allowing production and use of low-carbon cement;
- Blocking of EN standards supporting CPR for OJ citation. Many of the cited harmonized standards are withdrawn and new published by CEN standards are not cited in OJ. The manufacturers should use

withdrawn standards for purposes of assessment constancy of performance of construction products and CE marking. This problem shall be solved with the new CPR.

- Lack of sufficient knowledge among all participants in the construction process – designers, concrete producers, construction companies, building control experts, etc.
- Usually, the concrete producers are small local entrepreneurs with limited resources. They have difficulties to ensure different silos for the different types of cement;
- Lack of sufficient tests for new types cements and concrete; new cements should be tested to prove that they have the required characteristics and can be applied in construction;
- Lower early strength of concrete, which slows down the demoulding and, respectively, the whole process.
- The application of the new standard requires updating a number of other documents – such as the Public Procurement Law, which should impose specific environmental requirements.
- Need of dedicated training for knowledge in standardization.

3.1.3.2. Specific focus on the relation between the existing standardization framework and the twin transition

The relation between the existing standardization framework and the twin transition is summarized in Table 16, where we list a series of enabling features and barriers related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”, specifically the “green transition” and the “digital transition”.

Table 16. List of standardization barriers and enabling features related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”

Framework	Enabling features	Barriers
Green transition	<p><u>Group of cements</u> Shifting to a performance-based cement standards for all common cements will strengthen the internal market for construction products. Shifting to performance-based cement standards will – finally – align cement standards with the CPR, strengthening and deepening the European internal market. This will create new opportunities for industry and green growth. Shifting to performance-based cement standards is crucial to foster innovation and accelerate decarbonization in cement production in Europe. This is vital at a time when cement industry is not on track to meet net-zero by 2050. Need to include possibility for use in construction low-carbon cements and cements with recycled concrete fines.</p>	<p>The main standard EN 197-1 limits cement composition for 27 types common cements. Need for development of performance-based standards, including parts for special types cements</p>
Green transition	<p><u>Group of concretes and cement-based products</u> EN 206 is the main standard for concrete production and it is referenced in all standard for precast concrete/autoclaved aerated concrete/lightweight aggregate concrete products. It is based on EN 197-1 regarding use of cement as basic constituent of concrete. Need for revision of EN 206. It is necessary to revise the standards for precast concrete products so that they incorporate the principles developed in EN 13369:2023 <i>Common rules for precast concrete products</i> and allow the application of Performance-Based Approach.</p>	<p>The standard EN 206:2013+A2:2021 establishes restriction on minimum cement content and limiting values for composition and properties of concrete. The cement shall conform to EN 197-1 in which the concept for low-carbon cement is not established.</p>

Green transition	<p><u>Test methods standards</u></p> <p>The series EN 196 are based on EN 197-1. After the revision of EN 197-1, it should be established for which characteristics of the new cements the existing standards of the EN 196 series should be developed and/or supplemented.</p> <p>The series EN 12350, EN 12390, EN 1015 and other series for testing cement-based products, are based on EN 206. After the revision of EN 206, it should be established for which characteristics of the new concretes the existing test methods standards should be developed and/or supplemented.</p> <p>Need of new/revised methods.</p>	<p>According to EN 197-6:2023 the performance tests available at the time of publication of the document (i.e. for the determination of setting time, strength, soundness and heat of hydration) have been included in this document. In addition, work is being carried out by CEN/TC 51 to identify any additional tests which are needed to specify further performance characteristics of cement. Until further performance tests are available, it is necessary that the choice of cement, especially the type and/or strength class in relation to the requirements for durability depending on exposure class and type of construction in which it is incorporated, follows the appropriate standards and/or regulations for concrete, mortar, grout, etc. valid in the place of use.</p>
Green transition	<p><u>EAD – Special types of cements</u></p> <p>Need specification of composition materials, including recycling materials, limits of useful area. Possibility to include these specifications in European standards.</p>	<p>Need requirements and established test results. Need to include the requirements and limits to the useful area.</p>
Digital transition	<p>In the proposal for a new Construction Products Regulation from 2023, which is expected to enter into force soon, mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of cement-based construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the digital transition:</p> <p>introduction of machine-readable documents; introduction of a digital passport of construction products;</p>	<p>In Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 (CPR), as well as in existing standards supporting CPR (harmonized and non-harmonized), no mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the digital transition.</p>

3.2. Standardization framework for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope

Activities described in this section have been coordinated by the project partner ASRO.

3.2.1. Research on European and international standards and other harmonized technical specifications

3.2.1.1. Objects of research

Groups of standards

1. Product standards

- Cellulose
- Wood fiber
- Cork
- Grass
- Flax
- Jute
- Sisal
- Untreated chipped wood

- Cotton fibres
 - Straw bales
 - Sheep wool
 - Hemp fiber
2. Test methods standards
 - Mechanical and geometrical characteristics of the products
 - Organic content of the products
 3. European Assessment Documents EAD
 - Special type of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope

3.2.1.2. *Structure of researching*

Research on European and international existing standards. Completeness and weaknesses of existing standards.

- General review on each group of standards.
- Deeper research on selected standards from each group and EADs in terms of missing requirements and/or test methods for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope.

Identification of potential barriers to development of new standards for new construction materials and products

Special attention was given to the impact of different standards on the twin transition of construction – do they enable or rather hamper the deployment of “greener” or “circular” materials in the sector?

3.2.2. **Analysis**

3.2.2.1. *Introduction to methodology*

In order to identify all the relevant European, international and national standards for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope ASRO performed a thoroughly desk research using:

- CEN-CENELEC Project online platform (<https://experts.cen.eu/>) gives an overview of CEN and CENELEC Work Programme, including monitoring functionalities for following-up the work within Technical Bodies and provides access to CEN Working area (submission of CEN TC decisions) and foreign Partner standards implementation process (download cart).
- ISO Portal - technical committees working area (<https://sd.iso.org/home/>),
- ISO search standards (<https://www.iso.org/standards.html>)
- PrgASRO (Romanian IT app dedicated for planning and forecast of the EN and ISO standards development, as well for Romanian homegrown standards)
- StaGest (Romanian IT app that collects all the in force, withdrawn and replaced standards, from the beginning of IRS-Romanian Institute for Standardization)

There are 2 main aspects that define the standards research: the building envelope definition and the bio-based definition, according to the EU policy and the related standardization work.

According to Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast), Article 2, Definitions, point 7:

a building envelope means the integrated elements of a building that separates its interior from the outdoor environment.

Regarding the bio-based products definition ASRO identified all the relevant standardization and legislative work on this topic, as follows:

CEN Technical Committee on bio-based products CEN/TC411 *Bio-based products*

The scope of this Technical Committee is the Development of standards for bio-based products covering horizontal aspects. This includes consistent terminology, sampling, certification tools, bio-based content, application of and correlation towards life cycle analysis, sustainability criteria for biomass used and for final products, and aspects where further harmonization is needed on horizontal level (<https://www.biobasedeconomy.eu/centc-411-bio-based-products/>).

Reference	Title	Standard Status	Responsible Body	Mandate
CEN/TR 16721:2014	Bio-based products - Overview of methods to determine the bio-based content	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16575:2014	Bio-based products - Vocabulary	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16848:2016	Bio-based products - Requirements for Business-to-Business communication of characteristics using a Data Sheet	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16751:2016	Bio-based products - Sustainability criteria	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16760:2015	Bio-based products - Life Cycle Assessment	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16785-1:2015	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 1: Determination of the bio-based content using the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16640:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
CEN/TR 16957:2016	Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16785-2:2018	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 2: Determination of the bio-based content using the material balance method	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16935:2017	Bio-based products - Requirements for Business-to-Consumer communication and claims	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
CEN/TR 17341:2019	Bio-based products - Examples of reporting on sustainability criteria	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 17351:2020	Bio-based products - Determination of the oxygen content using an elemental analyser	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492

EN 16766:2017	Bio-based solvents - Requirements and test methods	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/491
CEN/TR 17674:2021	Bio-based products- Use of stable isotope ratios of Carbon, Hydrogen, Oxygen and Nitrogen as tools for verification of the origin of bio-based feedstock and characteristics of production processes - Overview of relevant existing applications	Published	CEN/TC 411	
prEN 18027	Bio-based products - Life cycle assessment - Additional requirements and guidelines for comparing the life cycles of bio-based products with their fossil-based equivalents	Not Published	CEN/TC 411	
prEN 16640 rev	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	Not Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492
EN 16640:2017/AC:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	Published	CEN/TC 411	M/492

According to the Report on implementation for creation of new or revised standards, Standards and Regulations for the Bio-based Industry STAR4BBI, document freely available at the link <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5bff106ab&appld=PPGMS> :

Mandated by the European Commission, the CEN/TC 411 'Bio-based products' developed standards that cover horizontal aspects of bio-based products. These standards play a crucial role in supporting the growth of the bio-based products market. They can help to increase market transparency by providing common reference methods and requirements that enable the verification of claims and certification regarding the bio-based content, biodegradability, or environmental sustainability of different products.

The building sector is a traditional sector when looking at materials. As bio-based materials do not have a track record as long as traditional fossil-based products, bio-based product developers are required to prove that these materials are functionally equivalent to traditional materials. Certification of bio-based materials in the building industry is important as the provision of objective information on the performance (and guarantee of performance) of available bio-based technologies by product certifications can boost customers' acceptance and accelerate deployment.

Harmonized and standardized national/international testing and evaluation procedures for specific bio-based products and technologies increase understanding of functionalities and performance of bio-based building materials among developers, architects and installers and accelerates the maturity of the industry more broadly. The current standardized tests are not always sufficient to be applied to bio-based materials.

According to the European Commission page on *Research and innovation for Bio-based products and processes* [37]:

Bio-based products are derived from biological resources (urban bio-waste, organic residues or wastes from primary production and industrial processes, dedicated industrial crops, biogenic CO₂, etc.) and they cover a variety of sectors and uses, such as textiles, home, and personal care, furniture and construction, chemicals, plastics, fertilizers, etc. These products can replace fossil-intensive ones, potentially saving up to 2.5 billion tons of CO₂ equivalent per year by 2030 and may have better environmental and technical performance. They contribute to reducing Europe's dependency on fossil resources and help accelerate the transition to a green

and circular economy. Bio-based products and processes may also bring economic and social benefits e.g. by establishing new markets and creating new job opportunities, both in innovative sectors and in rural and coastal areas, where the production of biological resources rarely happens.

According to EN 16575:2014, article 2 Terms and definitions:

- bio-based means derived from biomass (Biomass can have undergone physical, chemical or biological treatment(s)) and
- bio-based product is a product wholly or partly derived from biomass ("bio-based product" is often used to refer to a product which is partly bio-based. In those cases, the claim should be accompanied by a quantification of the bio-based content)
- biomass is material of biological origin excluding material embedded in geological formations and/or fossilized (examples of biomass (whole or parts of) plants, trees, algae, marine organisms, micro-organisms, animals, etc.)

Regarding the relationship with the EU legislation, the following aspects were taken into account in the present analysis:

- CEN process for development of an EN standard
- CEN policy for transposing an ISO standard as EN standard
- CEN policy for parallel working CEN-ISO according to Vienna Agreement
- CEN policy and ASRO rules for homegrown standards
- European Commission policy for harmonized standards
- EU Regulation no 305/2011 known and referred to in this document as CPR and the current work for revision.

To have a global overview of the standardization process integrated with the legislative framework needed for drawing the analysis conclusions, the next section of this analysis is allocated to the description of the above-mentioned topics.

A definition issued by the European Commission for hEN according to is [38]:

Harmonized European standards provide a technical basis to assess the performance of construction products. They enable manufacturers to draw up the Declaration of Performance as defined in the Construction Products Regulation and affix the CE marking. Harmonized European standards create a common technical language used by all actors in the construction sector to:

- *define requirements (regulatory authorities in EU countries);*
- *declare the product's performance (manufacturers);*
- *verify compliance with requirements and demands (design engineers, contractors).*

Supporting testing standards relevant to construction products cover:

- *resistance to fire, reaction to fire, external fire performance, noise absorption;*
- *construction products in contact with drinking water;*
- *release of dangerous substances into indoor air, soil and (ground)water;*

When developing an EN standard intended to be an harmonized standard (hEN, referred in this document), the European Commission sends CEN a standardization request (ex-mandate) containing the need for standardization work on a specific topic and the essential characteristics of the future products dealt in the future standards subject to the standardization request. An up-to-date list of standardization requests is

available at [39].

CEN/TC responsible for the work in the specific domain of the future standardization work answers to the standardization request.

According to CEN-CENELEC guidance – Core rules for drafting hEN for construction products available at [40]:

- *Answers to mandate cannot contradict, modify, reduce or extend the content of the original mandate. They can be used only to facilitate and clarify the operationalization of the targets contained in the mandate.*
- *Answer to the mandate cannot extend the scope of the mandate but only restrict the mandated scope.*
- *Some modifications to the original mandate are possible for the operationalization of the essential characteristics for example by means of sub-characteristics (new or modified when compared to the original mandate) if the content is still in the scope of the original mandate.*

Regarding the future standard content, the above-mentioned document states:

- *The candidate hEN for construction products should be coherent with the mandate or standardization request and only contain:*
 - *the essential characteristics covered in the mandate/updated TC answer to the mandate (following the current EC instructions) or standardization request (if available);*
 - *the assessment methods (e.g. test methods, calculation, tabulated values) to determine the performance of the construction product in relation to these essential characteristics.*
- *The essential characteristics covered in the candidate hEN shall be identical with the list of essential characteristics in the mandate/ updated TC answer to the mandate following the current EC instructions or standardization request (if available).*
- *Non-mandated characteristics shall not be included in the candidate hEN.*
- *Classes and threshold levels can be used under the following conditions:*
 1. *Classes/threshold levels included in a delegated regulation published in the OJEU as a result of the delegated act process developed by the EC and scrutiny of the European Parliament and Council, e.g. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2016/364;*
 2. *Classes/threshold levels included in the relevant standardization request;*
 3. *Classes/threshold levels included in previous cited version of the harmonized standard.*
- *Harmonized standards cannot include any classification/threshold level not included in at least one of the previous documents, but TC can request the launch of the delegated act development to establish a classification/threshold level. However, TCs should be aware that establishing new classes/thresholds of performance or changing existing classes/thresholds via delegated act is a challenging and lengthy process, i.e. it could take a couple of years to be published in the OJEU.*

To be cited in OJEU (Official Journal of European Union) a standard developed under a standardization request needs to be accepted by the European Commission and the standard number must be included in a Commission implementing decisions under the CPR.

The list of Commission implementing decisions under the CPR is available at [41]

Figure 12. hEN standards track (from [42], page 63)

The following statement is included in the document *BRIEFING EU Legislation in Progress. Revision of the Construction Products Regulation* available at the European Parliament webpage at [43], namely

Since early 2019, no standard in support of the CPR has been cited in the OJEU

reflects the current situation of the hEN standards and the present critical issues that the manufacturers from the construction industry are dealing with.

To solve this problem, the European Parliament issued the following resolution:

European Parliament resolution of 10 March 2021 on the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products (the Construction Products Regulation), available at [44].

On 30 March 2022 the proposal for a revised Construction Products Regulation (CPR) was adopted and an update status is available at [45].

ASRO's analysis concentrates on the above-mentioned information, rules, and procedures, and also on the CPR revision for drawing up the conclusions.

The first draft list, the long list, resulting from the research includes 289 standards and project standards. For all 289 items was necessary to include the following information, under the standardized format:

Standard reference	Standard Title	Responsible Body Technical Committee (TC)	Abstract	EU Legislation
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According to the bio-based product definition from **EN 16575:2014** the initial list containing 289 items was revised resulting in a short list of **23 standards** dedicated to the bio-based products domain (excluding the test methods standards subject to 4.2).

3.2.2.2. Analysis of product standards

List of standards for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope is reported in Table 17.

Table 17. List of standards for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope.

No crt	Standard reference	Standard Title	TC	EU Legislation
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1	EN 15101-1:2013+A1:2019	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 1: Specification for the products before installation	CEN/TC 88	M/103 Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Rejected for citation by EC
2	EN 15101-2:2013	Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 2: Specification for the installed products	CEN/TC 88	–
3	EN 13171:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
4	EN 13168:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood wool (WW) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
5	FprEN 17139	Thermal insulation products for building - Factory made vegetal fibres-based products (VFBP)	CEN/TC 88	M/103 305/2011 (CPR) - Not candidate for citation
6	ISO 17749:2018	Thermal insulation products — Sheep wool mat and board — Specification	ISO/TC 163/SC 3	–
7	ISO 24260:2022	Thermal insulation products — Hemp fiber mat and board — Specification	ISO/TC 163/SC 3	–
8	EN 13170:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made products of expanded cork (ICB) - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
9	ISO 2219:2010	Thermal insulation products for buildings — Factory-made products of expanded cork (ICB) — Specification	ISO/TC 87	–
10	ISO 9149:2010	Cork wallcoverings in rolls — Specifications	ISO/TC 87	–
11	EN 13085:2001	Wallcoverings - Specification for cork rolls	CEN/TC 99	305/2011 (CPR) - Not candidate for citation

12	EN 12103:1999	Resilient floor coverings - Agglomerated cork underlays - Specification	CEN/TC 134	305/2011 (CPR) - Not candidate for citation
13	EN 655:2011	Resilient floor coverings - Tiles of agglomerated composition cork with polyvinyl chloride wear layer - Specification	CEN/TC 134	305/2011 (CPR) - Not candidate for citation
14	EN 688:2011	Resilient floor coverings - Specification for corklinoleum	CEN/TC 134	305/2011 (CPR) - Not candidate for citation
15	EN 12104:2023	Resilient floor coverings - Cork floor tiles - Specification	CEN/TC 134	–
16	ISO 2509:1989	Sound-absorbing expanded pure agglomerated cork in tiles	ISO/TC 87	–
17	ISO 633:2019	Cork — Vocabulary	ISO/TC 87	–
18	ISO 1215:2015	Virgin cork, raw reproduction cork, ramassage, gleanings, burnt cork, corkwaste, boiled cork pieces and raw corkwaste — Definitions and packaging	ISO/TC 87	–
19	ISO 1216:2017	Boiled reproduction cork — Grading, classification and packing	ISO/TC 87	–
20	ISO 1997:2018	Granulated cork and cork powder — Classification, properties and packing	ISO/TC 87	–
21	ISO 3869:2017	Agglomerated cork — Expansion joint fillers — Specifications, packaging and marking	ISO/TC 87	–
22	ISO 4714:2000	Composition cork — Specifications, sampling, packaging and marking	ISO/TC 87	–

For the bio-based products for insulation of building's envelope the analysis includes 11 standards developed by CEN and 11 standards developed by ISO:

- the testing methods standards, analyzed at chapter 3.2.2.3 of the present document
- the relevant project standards (FprEN 17139 *Thermal insulation products for building - Factory made vegetal fibres based products (VFBP)*)
- the hENs relevant for our research (3 hENs)

Standards Development Organizations distribution

Figure 13. Standards development organizations distribution.

CEN-ISO Drafting TCs repartition

Figure 14. Repartition between technical committees

CEN/TC 88 Thermal insulating materials and products

Scope: Standardisation in the field of thermal insulating materials and products for application in buildings, including insulation for installed equipment and for industrial insulation, covering: terminology and definitions, list of required properties with regard to different applications, methods for the determination of these properties, sampling procedures, conformity criteria, specifications for insulating materials and products, marking and labelling of insulating materials and products

CEN/TC 99 Wallcoverings

Scope: To elaborate ENs for wallcoverings in the sense that the term "wallcoverings" is used to cover all forms of flexible webs supplied in roll form for hanging onto walls or ceilings by means of an adhesive; it includes "finished wallcoverings", "wallcoverings for subsequent decoration", "heavy duty wallcoverings" and "textile wallcoverings" and cork wallcoverings in roll and panel form

CEN/TC 134 Resilient, textile, laminate and modular mechanical locked floor coverings

Scope: Standardization of definitions, requirements, classification and test methods, and development of guidance documents and reports for resilient, textile, laminate and modular mechanical locked floor coverings. The main use areas for floor coverings within the scope of CEN/TC 134 are residential (homes, apartments) and commercial, (health care, education, hospitality, public buildings, offices, retail, transportation). These areas are limited to indoor use. Excluded are screeds, raised access floors, paving, surfaces for sports areas, as well as parquet, wood veneer and bamboo floorings

ISO/TC 87 Cork

Scope: Standardization in the field of cork, both the raw material and products manufactured and prepared from cork.

ISO/TC 163/SC3 Thermal insulation products, components and systems

Scope: Standardization and specification of thermal insulating products, components and installed systems for application in buildings, including insulation for equipment, and industrial insulation, covering and including:

- specification of required properties
- specification of specific test methods for products, components and systems
- specification and proof of conformity
- marking and labelling of insulating materials, components and systems
- specification for installation
- specification for applications

For the relationship with the European Commission policy for the development of EU standards, the list of standards was analyzed regarding the standardization requests (ex-mandates) and the report is shown in Figure 15. Standardization requests with and without mandate..

Standardization requests (ex-mandates)

Figure 15. Standardization requests with and without mandate. M/103 = Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products

Regarding the harmonization under CPR, 3 European standards are referred to in the OJEU, representing 13% from the total number of identified standardization work, as it is shown in Figure 16. Harmonized standards under CPR and listed in Table 18.

Figure 16. Harmonized standards under CPR

Table 18. List of Harmonized standards under CPR

Standard reference	Standard Title	Responsible Body Technical Committee (TC)	EU Legislation
EN 13171:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13168:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood wool (WW) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13170:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made products of expanded cork (ICB) - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED

Regarding the raw material for the 22 standards the repartition is shown in Figure 17.

No of standards by raw material

Figure 17. Number of standards by raw material.

1. Identification of lacking EN standards for several types of products:

a. Thermal insulation products made of sheep wool.

Only ISO standard, **ISO 17749:2018** *Thermal insulation products — Sheep wool mat and board — Specification*. This document specifies requirements for factory-made products of sheep wool, which are used for thermal insulation of buildings. This document applies to material containing more than 50 % (by mass) natural sheep wool, with the balance being polymeric material. The products are delivered as a mat or board with or without facings. This document describes product characteristics and testing methods, marking, labelling and packaging. Products covered in this document are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels; the performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. The sheep wool mat and board thermal insulation is not to be used when the continuous service temperature of the substrate is outside the range of $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The use of mothproof agent residues is outside the scope of this document. This document does not address all the health and safety aspects associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this document to establish appropriate health and safety practices.

b. Thermal insulation products made of hemp fiber

Only ISO standard, **ISO 24260:2022** *Thermal insulation products — Hemp fiber mat and board — Specification*. This document specifies requirements for factory-made products of hemp fibre, which are used for the thermal insulation of buildings. This document applies to material containing more than 50 % (by mass) natural hemp fibre, with or without the other natural fibre, and the balance being polymeric material. The products are delivered as a mat or board with or without facings. This document describes product characteristics and testing methods, marking, labelling, and packaging. Products covered in this document are also used in prefabricated thermal insulation systems and composite panels. The performance of systems incorporating these products is not covered. The use of moth-proof agent residues is outside the scope of this document. This document does not address the health and safety aspects associated with its use. It is the responsibility of the user of this document to establish appropriate health and safety practices.

c. Thermal insulation products for building - Factory made vegetal fibres based products (VFBP)

FprEN 17139 work in progress document

EOTA developed EAD Number 040005-00-1201 Factory-made thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable or animal fibres (cited by 2016/C 054/14) and according to this EAD

1.1 Description of the construction product

The construction products consist of vegetable or animal fibres with or without binding agent or supporting/binding fibres, in form of mats or boards, with or without a facing, hereinafter referred to as insulation product.

The insulation product can be treated with a flame retardant.

The vegetable fibres consist of e.g. grass, flax, hemp, jute/sisal, paper or untreated chipped wood. The animal fibres consist e.g. of sheep wool.

Conclusion: EAD 040005-00-1201 covers sheep wool, hemp, etc

2. Lack of European and International standards for raw materials as: grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales

For these bio-based products the manufacturers must use the EOTA path, see the EAD at 4.3

As informative documents for these raw materials the research includes the standards reported in Table 19.

Table 19. Standard analysis for raw materials as: grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales

No crt	Standard reference	Standard Title	TC	Abstract
1	ISO 2403:2021	Textiles. Cotton fibres. Determination of micronaire value	ISO/TC 38/SC 23	This document specifies a method of determining the micronaire value of loose disorientated cotton fibres taken from bales, laps and slivers, or other sources of lint cotton.
2	ISO 2370:2019	Textiles — Determination of fineness of flax fibres — Permeametric methods	ISO/TC 38/SC 23	This document specifies three permeametric methods for the determination of the fineness of flax fibres. — Constant flow method, with two compressions, using a test piece of parallel fibres (see Clause 5); — Simplified constant flow method, with one compression, using a test piece of fibres distributed "at random" (see Clause 6); — Constant pressure method, with one compression, using a test piece of fibres distributed "at random" (see Clause 7). This document is applicable to the various forms possible for

				flax fibres, i.e. long strands, broken strands, all kinds of tow and at all stages of manufacture of these substances.
3	ISO 3060:1974	Textiles — Cotton fibres — Determination of breaking tenacity of flat bundles	ISO/TC 38/SC 23	The method is applicable to fibres being tested either at a nominal gauge length of zero or at a finite gauge length. It is especially intended to be used with tensile strength test instruments which have been designed for specific use on flat bundles of cotton fibres. It may be used with other tensile strength test instruments if equipped to accommodate the fibre clamps.
4	ISO 4912:1981	Textiles — Cotton fibres — Evaluation of maturity — Microscopic method	ISO/TC 38/SC 23	As measurements of the degree of wall thickening of the fibres is too laborious for most practical purposes, this method of determination of maturity of cotton fibres is an indirect test. It consists of an appraisal, based on judgment and experience, and is suitable for routine research purposes.
5	ISO 10306:2014	Textiles-Cotton fibres-Evaluation of maturity by the air flow method	ISO/TC 38/SC 23	ISO 10306:2014 specifies a method for the evaluation of the maturity of loose randomized cotton fibres by measuring the resistance to air flow of a plug of cotton fibres under two prescribed conditions. The method is applicable to cotton taken at random from bales. Laps and slivers or other sources of lint cotton may be tested, however results may differ if fibres are taken from bales.

6	ISO 11860:1999	Textile floor coverings-Jute carpet backing fabric-Specification	ISO/TC 219	This International Standard specifies requirements for primary and secondary jute carpet backing fabrics.
7	ISO 11861:1999	Textile floor coverings — Coir mats — Types and specification	ISO/TC 219	This International Standard specifies the requirements for mats produced from coir fibre, with or without pile.
8	ISO 1181:2004	Fibre ropes-Manila and sisal-3-, 4- and 8-strand ropes	ISO/TC 87	The following characteristics are determined: dimensions and squareness, apparent density, tensile strength, initial and residual indentation, ash content and resistance to boiling hydrochloric acid. Replaces the first edition of which this constitutes a technical revision.

3. Low number of hENs for bio-based products for building's envelope

EN 15101-1:2013+A1:2019 *Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 1: Specification for the products before installation* was developed by CEN/TC 88 under M/103 Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products. After the finalization of standard, this was Rejected for citation by EC under 305/2011 (CPR). At the present time the cellulose products for building envelope manufacturers don't have any European standard to attest their products conformity and to affix CE marking.

FprEN 17139 *Thermal insulation products for building - Factory made vegetal fibres based products (VFBP) under development* by CEN/TC 88 under M/103 was from the beginning of the work not intended to be a candidate for citation under CPR, meaning that after finalizing the standard, this will not be a hEN under CPR. At present, the vegetal fibres based products for building envelope manufacturers don't have any European standards to attest to their products' conformity and to affix CE marking. The analysis performed by ASRO showed that there are EADs developed for this type of products, namely:

- **EAD no 040005-00-1201** Factory-made thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable or animal fibres (cited in 2016/C 054/14)
- **EAD no 040138-01-1201** In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres (cited in 2018/C 417/07)
- **EAD no 041125-00-1201** In-situ loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres to be used in floor constructions without additional load-bearing structures (cited by Decision (EU) 2023/424)

For cellulose, hemp, sheep wool, grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales there are no European harmonized standards at present that could be used by the manufacturers for CE marking.

For cellulose, hemp, sheep wool, grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales products the EAD specified at 4.3 can be used for conformity assessment of the product

(EAT-EOTA path)

3.2.2.3. Analysis of test method standards

For the purpose of this analysis the most relevant testing methods standard were identified. In the Annex to this analysis all the standards shown in Table 20 were detailed.

Table 20. Test method standards.

No crt	Standard reference	Standard Title	TC
1	EN 16785-1:2015	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 1: Determination of the bio-based content using the radiocarbon analysis and elemental analysis	CEN/TC 411
2	EN 16640:2017	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	CEN/TC 411
3	CEN/TR 16957:2016	Bio-based products - Guidelines for Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the End-of-life phase	CEN/TC 411
4	EN 16785-2:2018	Bio-based products - Bio-based content - Part 2: Determination of the bio-based content using the material balance method	CEN/TC 411
5	EN 17351:2020	Bio-based products - Determination of the oxygen content using an elemental analyser	CEN/TC 411
6	EN 16766:2017	Bio-based solvents - Requirements and test methods	CEN/TC 411
7	CEN/TR 17674:2021	Bio-based products- Use of stable isotope ratios of Carbon, Hydrogen, Oxygen and Nitrogen as tools for verification of the origin of bio-based feedstock and characteristics of production processes - Overview of relevant existing applications	CEN/TC 411
8	prEN 18027	Bio-based products - Life cycle assessment - Additional requirements and guidelines for comparing the life cycles of bio-based products with their fossil-based equivalents	CEN/TC 411
9	prEN 16640 rev	Bio-based products - Bio-based carbon content - Determination of the bio-based carbon content using the radiocarbon method	CEN/TC 411
10	ISO 2066:2004	Resilient floor coverings — Determination of moisture content of agglomerated composition cork	ISO/TC 87
11	EN 12105:1998	Resilient floor coverings - Determination of moisture content of agglomerated composition cork	CEN/TC 134

12	ISO 3810:1987	Floor tiles of agglomerated cork — Methods of test	ISO/TC 87
13	ISO 3850:2004	Resilient floor coverings - Determination of apparent density of composition cork	ISO/TC 87
14	ISO 9366:2001	Agglomerated cork floor tiles — Determination of dimensions and deviation from squareness and from straightness of edges	ISO/TC 87
15	ISO 2030:2018	Granulated cork — Size analysis by mechanical sieving	ISO/TC 87
16	ISO 2031:2015	Granulated cork — Determination of apparent bulk density	ISO/TC 87
17	ISO 2067:2019	Granulated cork, broken cork and crushed cork — Sampling for the determination of moisture content	ISO/TC 87
18	ISO 2190:2016	Granulated cork — Determination of moisture content	ISO/TC 87
19	ISO 2385:2020	Packed cork — Virgin cork, raw reproduction cork, burnt cork, boiled reproduction cork and raw cork waste — Sampling to determine moisture content	ISO/TC 87
20	ISO 2386:2019	Packed cork — Virgin cork, raw reproduction cork, burnt cork, boiled reproduction cork and raw cork waste — Determination of moisture content	ISO/TC 87
21	ISO 3867:2017	Composition cork — Expansion joint fillers — Test methods	ISO/TC 87
22	ISO 7322:2014	Composition cork — Test methods	ISO/TC 87
23	EN 16783:2024	Thermal insulation products - Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) - Product Category Rules (PCR) complementary to EN 15804 for factory made and in-situ formed products	CEN/TC 88
24	EN 16783:2017	Thermal insulation products - Product category rules (PCR) for factory made and in-situ formed products for preparing environmental product declarations	CEN/TC 88
25	EN 13498:2002	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the resistance to penetration of external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS)	CEN/TC 88
26	EN 16724:2015	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Instructions for mounting and fixing for determination of the reaction to fire testing of external thermal Insulation composite systems (ETICS)	CEN/TC 88
27	EN 16383:2016	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the hygrothermal behaviour of external thermal insulation composite systems with renders (ETICS)	CEN/TC 88

28	EN 13495:2019	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the pull-off resistance of external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS) (foam block test)	CEN/TC 88
29	EN 13820:2003	Thermal insulating materials for building applications - Determination of organic content	CEN/TC 88
30	EN 15715:2009	Thermal insulation products - Instructions for mounting and fixing for reaction to fire testing - Factory made products	CEN/TC 88
31	EN 1607:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of tensile strength perpendicular to faces	CEN/TC 88
32	EN 824:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of squareness	CEN/TC 88
33	EN 1603:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of dimensional stability under constant normal laboratory conditions (23 °C/ 50 % relative humidity)	CEN/TC 88
34	EN 1604:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of dimensional stability under specified temperature and humidity conditions	CEN/TC 88
35	EN 1605:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of deformation under specified compressive load and temperature conditions	CEN/TC 88
36	EN 12086:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of water vapour transmission properties	CEN/TC 88
37	EN 12090:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of shear behaviour	CEN/TC 88
38	EN 12430:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of behaviour under point load	CEN/TC 88
39	EN 12089:2013	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of bending behaviour	CEN/TC 88

40	EN 16382:2016	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the pull-through resistance of plate anchors through thermal insulation products	CEN/TC 88
41	EN 13494:2019	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the tensile bond strength of the adhesive and of the base coat to the thermal insulation material	CEN/TC 88
42	EN ISO 29767:2019	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of short-term water absorption by partial immersion (ISO 29767:2019)	CEN/TC 88
43	EN ISO 16535:2019	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of long-term water absorption by immersion (ISO 16535:2019)	CEN/TC 88
44	EN ISO 16536:2019	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of long-term water absorption by diffusion (ISO 16536:2019)	CEN/TC 88
45	EN 17886:2023	Thermal insulation products - Assessment of the susceptibility to mould growth - Laboratory test method	CEN/TC 88
46	EN ISO 16546:2020	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of freeze-thaw resistance (ISO 16546:2020)	CEN/TC 88
47	EN ISO 29470:2020	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of the apparent density (ISO 29470:2020)	CEN/TC 88
48	EN ISO 16534:2020	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of compressive creep (ISO 16534:2020)	CEN/TC 88
49	EN ISO 29469:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of compression behaviour (ISO 29469:2022)	CEN/TC 88
50	EN ISO 29766:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of tensile strength parallel to faces (ISO 29766:2022)	CEN/TC 88
51	EN ISO 29468:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of flatness (ISO 29468:2022)	CEN/TC 88
52	EN ISO 29466:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of thickness (ISO 29466:2022)	CEN/TC 88

53	EN ISO 29465:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of length and width (ISO 29465:2022)	CEN/TC 88
54	EN ISO 29770:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of thickness for floating-floor insulating products (ISO 29770:2022)	CEN/TC 88
55	EN ISO 29768:2022	Thermal insulating products for building applications - Determination of linear dimensions of test specimens (ISO 29768:2022)	CEN/TC 88
56	EN ISO 18097:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of maximum service temperature (ISO 18097:2022)	CEN/TC 88
57	EN ISO 12624:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of trace quantities of water-soluble chloride, fluoride, silicate, sodium ions and pH (ISO 12624:2022)	CEN/TC 88
58	EN ISO 12628:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of dimensions, squareness and linearity of preformed pipe insulation (ISO 12628:2022)	CEN/TC 88
59	EN ISO 18096:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of maximum service temperature for preformed pipe insulation (ISO 18096:2022)	CEN/TC 88
60	EN ISO 18098:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of the apparent density of preformed pipe insulation (ISO 18098:2022)	CEN/TC 88
61	EN ISO 18099:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of the coefficient of thermal expansion (ISO 18099:2022)	CEN/TC 88
62	EN ISO 12629:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of water vapour transmission properties of preformed pipe insulation (ISO 12629:2022)	CEN/TC 88

63	EN ISO 12623:2022	Thermal insulating products for building equipment and industrial installations - Determination of short-term water absorption by partial immersion of preformed pipe insulation (ISO 12623:2022)	CEN/TC 88
64	EN 13497:2018+A1:2021	Thermal insulation products for building applications - Determination of the resistance to impact of external thermal insulation composite systems (ETICS)	CEN/TC 88
65	EN ISO 18393-1:2023	Thermal insulation products - Determination of settlement - Part 1: Loose-fill insulation for ventilated attics simulating humidity and temperature cycling (ISO 18393-1:2023)	CEN/TC 88

3.2.2.4. Analysis of EADs

European assessment documents and European technical assessments [46].

The European technical assessment (ETA) is an alternative for construction products not covered by a harmonised standard. It is a document providing information on their performance assessment. The procedure is established in the construction products regulation and offers a way for manufacturers to draw up the declaration of performance and affix the CE marking. It contributes to the free movement of construction products and the creation of a strong single market.

How the procedure works:

1. A manufacturer requests the European technical assessment for a construction product that is not covered or not fully covered by a harmonised standard. The request is addressed to the technical assessment body (TAB) for the respective product area – see list of TABs in the NANDO database
2. The technical assessment body issues the European technical assessment on the basis of a European assessment document (EAD) adopted by the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA)
3. An updated list of references for the final EADs is published by the Commission in the Official Journal of the European Union

The main content of the European technical assessment is information on the intended use and performance of a product.

The European assessment document.

The European Assessment Document (EAD) is a harmonised technical specification for construction products. It is developed by the European Organisation for Technical Assessment (EOTA) for cases where a product is not fully covered by harmonised European standards. EADs are the basis for issuing European technical assessments. The document contains

- a general description of the construction product
- the list of essential characteristics agreed between the manufacturer and EOTA
- the methods and criteria for assessing the performance of the product in relation to these essential characteristics
- principles for factory production control to be applied

Technical assessment bodies

Technical assessment bodies (TABs) assess construction products on the base of European assessment

documents. These bodies are designated by EU countries according to national procedures. A list of technical assessment bodies including their respective product areas is available in the NANDO-CPR database.

The European organisation for technical assessment

To facilitate the co-operation of technical assessment bodies, the European Organisation for Technical Assessment was established. The organisation carries out the following tasks

- adopts European assessment documents (EAD) and ensures that they are publically available
- coordinates requests for the European technical assessment and the procedure for adopting a European assessment document
- organises the coordination of all TABs

The list of EADs for bio-based products for buildings' envelopes is shown in Table 21.

Table 21. List of EADs for bio-based products for buildings' envelopes.

No crt	EAD Number	EAD Title	OJEU	Status
1	040138-01-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres.	2018/C 417/07	Cited
2	041125-00-1201	In-situ loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable fibres to be used in floor constructions without additional load-bearing structures	Decision (EU) 2023/424	Cited
3	040005-00-1201	Factory-made thermal and/or acoustic insulation products made of vegetable or animal fibres	2016/C 054/14	Cited
4	040146-00-1201	Thermal insulation for buidlings made of straw bales	Decision (EU) 2023/1473	Cited
5	040313-00-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation product made of granulated expanded cork	2017/C 118/04	Cited
6	040369-01-1201	Insulation made of loose-fill or compound granulated expanded cork or loose-fill granulated natural cork and rubber	Decision (EU) 2022/1517	Cited
7	041389-00-1201	Boards made of agglomerated natural cork for thermal and acoustic insulation	Decision (EU) 2020/962	Cited
8	040456-00-1201	In-situ formed loose fill thermal and/or acoustic insulation material made of animal fibres	2017/C 343/06	Cited

Due to the lack of existing hENs for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope (cellulose, grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales, sheep wool, hemp fiber products, etc.), the manufacturers have to follow EOTA path for conformity evaluation of their products in order to affix CE mark and freely commercialize their products within EEA.

The EADs listed above cover the vegetable and animal fibers and cork products.

For cork products, wood wool and wood fibers the manufacturers have the hEN identified previously, and are relisted in Table 22.

Table 22. Harmonized standards for cork products, wood wool and wood fibers

Standard reference	Standard Title	Responsible Body Technical Committee (TC)	EU Legislation
EN 13171:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood fibre (WF) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13168:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made wood wool (WW) products - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED
EN 13170:2012+A1:2015	Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made products of expanded cork (ICB) - Specification	CEN/TC 88	M/103 (CPD: Thermal insulating prod.) Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products 305/2011 (CPR) - Cited/referenced C 226 (2015-07-10) HARMONISED

3.2.2.5. *Analysis of the results of the Multistakeholder Working Group for legislation and standardization research*

Under the WP 2 - Pre-normative research of legislative framework, existing standards and industrial needs, ASRO – National Standardization Body from Romania identified the national stakeholders among industry, researchers, and authority, and invited them to attend the meeting sessions. The main purpose of the meeting sessions was to have the multistakeholder national research groups` feedback for insulation products and to find out more about the documents used to prove the conformity of the product, obstacles to the use of European standard (Romanian standard that adopts a European standard), and if the national/European legislation smooths or complicates the activities carried out.

The conclusions of the multi-stakeholders were that:

- To be competitive in the building materials market, a product standard is necessary for sustainable thermal insulation.
- The biggest problem for Romanian manufacturers, who want to uptake the European market, is the very high cost of the European Assessment Document (EAD) and the long duration of the preparation of an ETA. A harmonized standard or the EOTA document is necessary for better promoting and selling the product on the European market.
- The standardization for bio-based construction products has some gaps (lack of harmonized standards, high prices, lack of consumer knowledge, low support from the authority, etc.), therefore some common initiatives from the stakeholders are needed.
- The producers of sustainable materials are still a niche in the market, they are not at the size of the producers of classic thermal insulation materials. It is very difficult for bio-based and sustainable manufacturers to access the market, and they should be supported by regulations to be competitive in the market, and to be on the same level as the producers of classic materials.
- The authorities must strengthen their activities related to this area, and ensure that there are some constraints, and that the market is efficiently checked.
- There should be more facilities available for the producers of construction insulation products. For e.g. one of the European Union for sustainable development - the hemp, which contributes to reducing the consumption of pesticides, and the possibility of exploiting the plant in its entirety is also an advantage because - the waste-technological material that remains after processing the fiber and harvesting the seeds is ecological and a way should be found to circulate freely in the European Union and the technological material can be imported from outside the Union. These products are very difficult to be standardized because technology must be used to control very well even the *degree of compaction, the dosage of the binder, the amount of water, and the temperature, there is a very large margin even in the heat transfer coefficient.*
- Things move very hard even though bio-based materials are sustainable, durable, and renewable. In Romania are very few wool producers. Wood fiber insulation is for the entire house envelope and is custom-made by different manufacturers with the same features but a huge price difference. The transport barrier is also very high. Another barrier is the effectiveness of the fire resistance class. The thermal system shall be compatible with the insulation; these things shall be specially regulated. In no technical data sheet is a direct recommendation that a class E for fire protection is harmonized or corresponds to a certain thermo-system which means that with a certain type of plaster, it reaches class B.
- There is no regulated thermo-system, and no regulation mentions the necessary package for thermal insulation, namely, plaster, primer, and decorative, that this package strengthens the penetration of the flame until it reaches the wood fiber that does not burn with the flame, this is carbonized. The end-users could also choose sustainable natural products if they had known all the fully transparent arguments regarding the advantages and disadvantages of using sustainable materials, even if the cost of these materials is quite high. The end-users feel the disadvantages of not using natural

products after the construction is finished when it is too late.

- Natural product manufacturers are not encouraged to access the market because the process is very cumbersome, and the duration and costs of certification are higher. The standard product is introduced much more easily to the market with much lower costs compared to a new product that has no standard or even EAD, where the costs are much higher.
- There are no standardized parameters for indoor air quality regarding bio-based products. In nZEB or passive houses, the control of the ventilation inside is done only based on the temperature, only the energy part matters. Carbon dioxide sensors began to be introduced to control this parameter as well because the beneficiaries can inhale carbon dioxide and thus headaches and other symptoms appear.
- The B(ROOF) fire resistance testing of the insulations is done on the three big thermal insulation groups, namely, polystyrene, mineral wool, and PIR panels. In Romania, manufacturers are obliged, when there is no harmonized European standard, to have a declaration of performance -DoP. The DoP is still used, and this document is not standardized, and there is no clarity about how a declaration of conformity should look like. Also, there is no state regulation for B(ROOF)(t1) external fire resistance of waterproofing materials. In other countries, authorities are already involved, and an external fire classification regulated in construction exists. For e.g., in Hungary, users are not allowed to mount the membrane on the building if it is not a B(ROOF)(t1) certified membrane. There are very high costs, a very long time to develop or revise European standards, as well as very high bureaucracy.
- The lack of harmonized standards for manufacturers to apply the CE mark makes the processes difficult. The European or international standardization process takes a long time and does not always reflect the interests of SMEs.
- European Assessment Documents (EADs) have much higher prices than National Assessment Documents, sometimes even 10 times higher.
- Regarding the National Assessments, the legislative process is difficult and requires numerous documents.
- At the national level, there is a lack of promoting bio-based products and there is no direct reference to the harmonized standards in the legislation. On the other hand, the manufacturers of established solutions have high economic interests.
- Not being members of the Technical Committees, the stakeholders do not know about the standards (in detail) and do not understand how they can be helped by the NSB. Therefore, there is a high demand for education about standardization in the area.

3.2.3. Conclusions and recommendations based on the analysis of the results.

3.2.3.1. Identification of weaknesses

The standards analysis for bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope (cellulose, wood fiber, cork, grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibers, straw bales, sheep wool, hemp fiber products, etc.) shown the following lacks in the standardization process:

- lack of hENs for products made of cellulose, grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales, sheep wool, hemp fiber products, etc
- only 3 hENs for: cork products, wood wool, and wood fibers
- difficult procedures for manufacturers to prove their product conformity in order to apply CE marking
- CPR 305/2011 is under revision to solve the actual situation concerning major blocking of EN standards for OJEU citation. This ENs blocking citation creates the lack of hENs and all the resulting problems for manufacturers

- Lots of ISO standards that are not transposed at the European level as EN, due to the lack of interest and consensus at the European level
- The EOTA path is very difficult to follow for a small manufacturer due to the lack of proper budget and insufficient information (conclusion from the meetings with the Romanian stakeholders)
- Usually, the manufacturers of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope are small local entrepreneurs with limited resources and limited knowledge on standardization processes and policies (conclusion from the meetings with the Romanian stakeholders)
- Including standardization in R+I projects could raise awareness (e.g Online Seminar 25-03-2024, available at [47]).
- dedicated training for standardization knowledge

3.2.3.2. *Specific focus on the relation between the existing standardization framework and the twin transition*

The relation between the existing standardization framework and the twin transition is summarized in Table 23, where we list a series of enabling features and barriers related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”, specifically the “green transition” and the “digital transition”.

Table 23. List of standardization barriers and enabling features related to both the frameworks of the “twin transition”

Framework	Enabling features	Barriers
Green transition	<p><u>Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings` envelope</u></p> <p>A <u>bio-based product</u> is a product wholly or partly derived from biomass, which is a material of biological origin excluding material embedded in geological formations and/or fossilized (examples of biomass (whole or parts of) plants, trees, algae, marine organisms, micro-organisms, animals, etc.)</p> <p>These products support green transition, and can replace fossil-intensive ones, and may have better environmental and technical performance. They contribute to reducing Europe’s dependency on fossil resources and help accelerate the transition to a green and circular economy. Bio-based products and processes may also bring economic and social benefits [48], e.g. by establishing new markets and creating new jobs opportunities, both in innovative sectors and in rural and coastal areas, where the production of biological resources mainly happens</p>	<p>Lack of European and International standards for raw materials as: grass, flax, jute, sisal, untreated chipped wood, cotton fibres, straw bales</p> <p>There is the need to develop standards for these raw materials, and to perform studies and research for other materials</p> <p>Low number of hENs for bio-based products for building’s envelope, only 3 European standards are referred in the OJEU, representing 13 % from the total number of identified standardization work</p> <p>ex: EN 15101-1:2013+A1:2019 Thermal insulation products for buildings - In-situ formed loose fill cellulose (LFCI) products - Part 1: Specification for the products before installation was developed by CEN/TC 88 under M/103 Mandate to CEN/CENELEC concerning the execution of standardization work for harmonized standards on thermal insulating products. After the finalization of standard, this was Rejected for citation by EC under 305/2011 (CPR). At the present time the cellulose products for building envelope manufacturers don’t have any European standard to attest their products conformity and to affix CE marking.</p>

Green transition	<u>Test methods standards</u> <p>There is the need for new test programs, research work to identify proper test methods for Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.</p> <p>This will increase the user's confidence in new products and will raise the degree of usability on bio-based products in construction works</p>	<p>Until further performance tests are available, the choice for using a bio-based product in a specific construction project is strictly related to the costs and the designer's choice.</p>
Green transition	<u>EAD</u> <p>Need specification of composition materials, including recycling materials, limits of useful area. Possibility to include these specifications in European standards.</p>	<p>Need requirements and established test results.</p> <p>Need to include the requirements and limits to the useful area.</p>
Digital transition	<p>In the proposal for a new Construction Products Regulation from 2023, which is expected to enter into force soon, mechanisms are provided to contribute to the realization of the digital transition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduction of machine-readable documents; • introduction of a digital passport of construction products. 	<p>In Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 (CPR), as well as in existing standards supporting CPR (harmonized and non-harmonized), no mechanisms are provided for support the incorporation of construction products into construction works to contribute to the realization of the digital transition.</p>

4. Market context

4.1. Market overview and description of the analyzed markets

In this section, a general overview of the markets analyzed within the AFCOS project is proposed. This study has been performed by the partner RoGBC.

As already anticipated, within the framework of the AFCOS project, two different market have been analyzed:

- Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.),
- Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

Specific attention has been put on Bulgarian market for the low carbon cement products and on the Romanian market for the bio-based products.

For both the analyzed product families, market data is hard to find and usually in costly reports. Romanian and Bulgarian markets are price-driven markets and where these products fail to comply this sole requirement. Both countries are investing in infrastructure and public building and here the national and local governments are using it, and the sole users are the real-estate developers for LEED or BREEAM assessed buildings (and the shrinkage of new office buildings is not helping) for low-carbon cement and the private residential buildings, who try to find a healthier alternative to polystyrene. The problem is similar with green building promotion where investors and contractors want to be convinced about the advantages of the solutions in order to accept the increase of price. In case of low-carbon cement, the only difference with a regular product is the CO2 content, whereas in the case of bio-based insulation there are other characteristics that can be promoted (fire resistance, circular economy etc.). In the case of Romania and Bulgaria there is a

general fear among contractors that in the case of low-carbon cement they pay an extra-price for a producer statement that is hard to be verified. In the case of bio-based insulation, there is a need to be clarified the difference between bio-based and natural insulation, as stone wool is presented as a natural insulation, creating a confusion among users.

Both low-carbon cement and bio-based insulation market share are increasing, with expectation that by 2026 to reach 5% of the market (data based on discussions with Romanian producers).

4.1.1. Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products (concrete, mortar, grout, etc.),

4.1.1.1. General overview

The cement industry in EU is represented by Cembureau, which prepared the document [49]. The paper presents the situation in 1990 where there was 783 kg CO₂/ t of cement to 0 in 2050 (the situation was in 2017 was 667 kg CO₂/ t of cement). The reduction is based on clinker (decarbonated raw materials, alternative fuels, thermal efficiency, low-carbon clinker, and hydrogen and electrification), cement (clinker substitution, electrical efficiency and renewable electricity, carbon neutral transport), concrete (concrete mix, carbon neutral transport) and construction carbonation (concrete in use and CO₂ capture in build environment).

The cement industry depends on the economic growth and construction development in this region, but other factors with equal importance are the reduction of carbon footprint of the industry, the ECT carbon pricing, the removal of free allocations, rising production costs, the availability of financial and raw material resources, the competitiveness of the industry and the ability of the cement producers to solve all this issues. Global growth is projected to fall from 3.5% in 2022 to 3.0% in 2023 and 2024 and inflation is decreasing in most countries but still high. In the Euro Area GDP growth is around 0.9% in 2023 and 1.5% in 2024 below the growth in the Advanced Economies [50].

Historical data and forecasts for cement production and consumption from 2018 to 2030 in the EU27 are shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19 respectively.

In [51] EU27 Cembureau mentioned a cement production figure of 182.5 Mt/a and cement consumption of 170.5 Mt/a for 2021.

Figure 18. Historical data and forecasts for cement production in the EU27 according to the research [50].

Figure 19. Historical data and forecasts for cement consumption in the EU27 according to the research [50].

Global cement main players are listed in the following.

- LafargeHolcim: It is one of the world's largest manufacturers of building materials with a significant presence in Europe. In 2023, LafargeHolcim reported revenues of approximately **\$28 billion** and operations in more than 70 countries. It employs approximately **72,000 people** globally and a significant percentage of them are involved in the company's European operations. The cement production capacity is 386 million Tons and annual production is 286 million Tons.
- Anhui Conch Cement: the Chinese company have revenue around 22 billion USD and approximately 47,500 employes and a capacity production 288 million Tones and an annual production of 217 million Tons.
- China National Building Material (CNBM): this Chinese company have revenue of 43 billion USD and have 155,600 employes, with a capacity production of 406 million Tons and an annual production of 176 million Tons.
- Heidelberg Materials: since November 2023, HeidelbergCement had become Heidelberg Materials and it include now Italcementi and Calcestruzzi. It is another major player in the cement market in Europe and after this new merger, it has the potential to become number 2 globally. There are no new figures after the merger but in 2022 HeidelbergCement operated in more than 40 countries and reported revenues of around **17,3 billion USD**, a cement capacity production of 129 million Tons and an annual cement production of 121 million Tonnes, with more than **57,000 people** globally and, similarly, a significant number are employed in European operations. In 2022 Italcementi reported revenues of 4 billion USD, a cement capacity production of 77 million Tons and an annual production of 76 million Tons
- CRH plc: It is a global company based in Ireland that also operates in the European cement market. In 2023, CRH plc had revenues of approximately **35 billion USD**. With approximately **79,000 employees** globally, the company also involves a significant number of workers in Europe, and it is the third European player. The cement production is not public.
- Cemex: Although Cemex is better known for its operations in Latin America and North America, the company also has a significant presence in Europe, including Spain and the UK.: With approximately **46,000 employees** globally, some of them are involved in European operations. In 2023 have revenues of around 15 billion USD and a cement capacity production of 93 million Tons and a production of 87 million Tons.

If we take into account the number of employees of large companies such as LafargeHolcim, Heidelberg Cement, CRH plc, Italcementi and Cemex, and we also take into account employees from other smaller companies, suppliers and other businesses associated with the cement industry, we can estimate that the total number of employees involved in **Europe is around 100,000 people**.

Since 2021, the European Union invested more than € 1.1 billion into 7 large-scale innovative projects under

the Innovation Fund. The seven projects were selected for funding under the first Innovation Fund call for large-scale projects from 311 applications. Four large-scale projects were selected from the cement industry, that include the Go4EcoPlanet project of Lafarge Cement (Holcim Group) in Kujawy/Poland, the ANRAV project of Devnya Cement (Heidelberg Materials Group) in Devnya/Bulgaria, the Carbon2Business projects of Holcim in Lägerdorf/Germany and the K6 project by Eqiom (CRH Group) in Lumbres/France.

In 2022, the EU Innovation Fund granted more than € 3.6 billion to 41 large-scale clean-tech projects out of a pool of 239 applications, with 5 projects focused on decarbonizing cement. A number of other full-scale carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS) projects have been announced by the cement industry in Europe. In total there are 15 full-scale projects (incl. full-scale demonstration projects) in the EU, comprising a carbon reduction potential of about 10.8 Mt CO₂ per year by the cement producers Cemex, Eqiom (CRH), Heidelberg Materials, Holcim, Rohrdorfer Cement, Titan and Vicat. The 15 plants comprise a clinker production capacity of 15.1 Mt/a, which corresponds to about 10.3% of the EU capacity.

At this stage only major companies and with EU grants can invest in CO₂ emissions.

Today, more than 8% of global carbon emissions are related to cement industry. For the moment there is no substitute for cement in infrastructure and building industry and solutions for decarbonization are looked upon with a strategi till 2050. The main problem is the competitiveness of the industry and that the price of cement remains at its current level.

4.1.1.2. Cement market in Romania

In Romania the cement industry is represented by CIROM, part of CEMBUREAU. CIROM is an patronal organization, established in 1991, which represents the main cement producers from Romania, with more than 90% of the cement used in Romania: CARMEUSE Holding SRL, CEMROM S.A., CEPROCIM S.A, GEOCYCLE (Romania) SRL, ETERMED S.A. MEDGIDIA, HeidelbergCement Romania S.A., HOLCIM (Romania) S.A., INOVECO SRL, Master Builders Solutions, ROMCIM S.A., SIKA România.

CIROM has 11 member companies, which contribute annually to the state budget with approximately EUR 200 million and with 3,000 direct jobs and generate approximately 12,000 jobs throughout the value chain.

On the Romanian cement market there are four major players, each having the production units distributed as follows:

- Heidelberg Marterials Romania – 3 integrated cement plants: Bicz, Deva, Fieni
- Holcim Romania – 2 integrated cement plants - Alesd and Campulung Muscel + a grinding plant in Turda
- Romcim (former CRH Romania) – 2 integrated cement plants – Medgidia and Hoghiz + a grinding plant in Tg. -Jiu
- Cemrom – a grinding plant in Corbu

According to data published by the Ministry of Finance, in 2022, the turnover of cement producers was 5,652,688,835 lei (around 1.13 billion EUR). According to data from the National Institute of Statistics, cement production in 2023 was approx. 10 million tons.

Figure 20. Distribution of cement factories in Romania.

4.1.1.3. Cement market in Bulgaria

In Bulgaria, the cement industry is represented by BACI (The Bulgarian Association of the Cement Industry) - a non-profit association, which represent the main cement producers in Bulgaria. Since 2007, BACI is a member of the European Cement Association – CEMBUREAU and actively supports its policies and initiatives.

Members of BACI are the major cement companies in Bulgaria: Heidelberg Materials Devnya Jsc, Titan Zlatna Panega Cement, Holcim Bulgaria and Heidelberg Materials Vulkan JSC – associated member.

According to ConsTrack360's, cement industry in Bulgaria is expected to grow, recording a CAGR of 2.7% during 2023-2027. The cement output in the country is expected to increase from US\$248.4 million in 2022 to reach US\$285.2 million by 2027.

For Bulgarian exporters of cement, Romania seems to be the most attractive market (in 2028) in terms of export potential followed by Israel, Serbia, North Macedonia and USA.

The below described companies are the major representatives of the cement industry in Bulgaria:

- Heidelberg Materials Devnya JSC (with previous name Devnya Cement JSC) is one of the largest cement producers in Bulgaria, located in the town of Devnya, in operation since 4 December 1958.
- Titan Zlatna Panega Cement - a leading producer of cement, ready-mix concrete, and construction materials in Bulgaria, with a history dating back to 1907.
- Holcim Bulgaria - a member of the Holcim Group - the global leader in innovative and sustainable building solutions, which operates in 60 countries around the world and has around 60,000 employees. Holcim has been present in Bulgaria for over 20 years. It operates the cement plant in Beli Izvor near Vratsa and has aggregates and RMX operations in Sofia, Plovdiv and Pazardzhik.
- Heidelberg Materials Vulkan JSC (with previous name Vulkan Cement JSC, owning a cement plant in Dimitrovgrad.

According to the data published by the National Institute of Statistics, the total production of refractory cements, mortars and similar compositions for 2022 is 2 076 274 kg, and the production of cement clinkers is 1 951 982 440 kg.

Data reported in this paragraph come from [52], [53], [54], [55].

Figure 21. Distribution of cement factories in Bulgaria.

4.1.2. Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

4.1.2.1. General overview

The thermal insulation market in Europe is 11.21 billion Euro with a cumulative average growth of 8.1%

Figure 22. Types of thermal insulation according to JRC [56].

The most widely used thermal insulation is stone and glass wool with around 58% in 2014, followed by plastic/fossil fuel derived with 41% and the rest is under 1%. By 2020 stone and glass wool is around 55%,

plastic is 43% and bio-based has raised to 1,6%. In 2020 there is a total = 265,800,000 m³ of thermal insulation [56].

Figure 23. Thermal insulation market in Europe for 2014 (according for JRC) [56].

There are several companies in Europe that produce natural (inorganic) and bio-based insulation, using environmentally friendly and sustainable materials. Here are some examples of famous companies in this field:

- Rockwool: It is one of the largest companies in the world specializing in mineral wool insulation. Although not all of their products are considered 'bio' in the strict sense of the term, Rockwool produces insulation materials that are recyclable and contribute to energy efficiency.
- Knauf Insulation: It is another large European manufacturer of insulation, including insulation based on glass mineral wool and rock wool. The company is diversifying its product range to include greener and sustainable options.
- Pavatex: It is known for its wood and wood fiber products, which are especially used in environmentally friendly and sustainable construction. Pavatex produces insulating panels from wood and related materials that are considered bio and sustainable.
- Isofloc: This company focuses on the production of cellulose insulation, which is made from recycled materials such as newspapers and paper. These insulations are considered bio and environmentally friendly because they come from renewable resources and are recyclable.
- Homatherm: Homatherm produces insulation based on natural materials, such as wood fiber, recycled cotton and wood fiber boards and drywall. These materials are considered bio and environmentally friendly and are used in sustainable construction.

Rockwool have net sales of 3.6 billion EUR in 2023 with around 10000 employees.

Knauf have a turnover of 2.5 billion EUR and around 6000 employees worldwide.

4.1.2.2. Thermal insulation market in Romania

Some data about Romanian thermal insulation marker in 2023 are shown in Figure 24, Figure 25, Figure 26 and Figure 27. Thermal insulation market is dominated by EPS and XPS, but price increase in 2023 see the a dropping of volume. In 2024 there is an increase of stone wool demand, especially due to a new Rockwool plant in Romania and by lower price difference, compared with EPS. Due to 2022 new nZEB calculation

method – Mc 001/2022, there is an increased interest in thermal insulation.

1.1. Volume and market segmentation of the insulating materials

M ³	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	% YoY
EPS	3.786.500	3.824.000	4.032.000	4.176.000	4.435.000	3.912.000	3.238.500	↓ -17,2%
XPS	442.000	511.000	557.000	640.000	790.000	924.000	807.700	↓ -12,6%

Tons	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	% YoY
Stone wool	80.270	103.560	90.780	98.440	135.130	145.140	125.130	↓ -13,8%
Glass wool	21.900	22.400	23.370	24.240	26.240	21.650	18.160	↓ -16,1%

M ³	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	% YoY
PUR/PIR panels	19.970	25.600	30.843	10.400	18.870	31.720	26.160	↓ -17,5%

Source: Neomar Consulting

Annual growth rate by volume

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
EPS (m ³)	- ↑ 1,0%	↑ 5,4%	↑ 3,6%	↑ 6,2%	↓ -11,8%	↓ -17,2%	
XPS (m ³)	- ↑ 15,6%	↑ 9,0%	↑ 14,9%	↑ 23,4%	↑ 17,0%	↓ -12,6%	
Stone wool (tons)	- ↑ 29,0%	↓ -12,3%	↑ 8,4%	↑ 37,3%	↑ 7,4%	↓ -13,8%	
Glass wool (tons)	- ↑ 2,3%	↑ 4,3%	↑ 3,7%	↑ 8,3%	↓ -17,5%	↓ -16,1%	
PUR/PIR panels (m ³)	↑ 28,2%	↑ 20,5%	↓ -66,3%	↑ 81,4%	↑ 68,1%	↓ -17,5%	

Figure 24. Insulating materials in Romania: volume and market segmentation; annual growth rate [57].

1.2. Value and market segmentation of the insulating materials (euro)

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	% YoY
EPS	118.414.000	119.941.000	107.763.000	108.868.000	163.196.000	219.715.000	125.863.000	↓ -42,7%
Stone wool	45.529.000	64.037.000	54.767.000	52.855.000	85.720.000	141.776.000	116.985.997	↓ -17,5%
XPS	30.124.000	35.222.000	38.449.000	42.574.000	62.338.000	88.675.000	67.754.000	↓ -23,6%
Glass wool	20.754.000	26.440.000	24.421.000	25.723.000	27.884.000	28.122.000	26.308.000	↓ -6,5%
PUR/PIR panels	2.230.000	3.512.000	3.492.000	1.269.000	2.441.000	5.516.000	4.136.000	↓ -25,0%
Total	217.051.000	249.152.000	228.892.000	231.289.000	341.579.000	483.804.000	341.046.997	↓ -29,5%

Source: Neomar Consulting

Figure 25. Insulating materials in Romania: value and market segmentation [57].

Figure 26. Types of thermal insulation in Romania and their market value (euro) [57].

Figure 27. Thermal insulation market values (euro) for Romania [57].

4.1.2.3. Wool industry

The major project in EU is the EcoPartnerSheep factory in Romania, in Arges county. The factory will start producing in summer 2025, with an estimated quantity of 25-30,000 tons of wool insulation, with no plastic addition (totally recyclable). It is a 34 million Euro investment and estimated annual turnover is 250-300 million Euro and 240 employees, covering 0.7-0.8 of the Europe insulation market. It is a Zero Waste factory and the waste from insulation production is converted into fertilizer.

4.1.3. Market overview – statistical data

In Table 24 some statistical data about the analyzed product families are shown, both on national and on international level. From the table it is possible to note that Cement industry, both on national and on international level, has a total turnover that is much higher than that of Thermal insulation products. Similarly, cement companies have an average number of employees which is much higher than that of Thermal insulation products.

Table 24. Statistical data about the analyzed product families in the markets under analysis. The symbol “—” means that those data are unavailable (Romanian data from [58] [59] [60] [61] [62], Bulgarian data from [63] and from the National Statistical Institute in

Bulgaria).

Statistical data	Romania		Bulgaria		Worldwide	
	Cement industry	Thermal insulation materials	Cement industry	Thermal insulation materials	Cement industry	Thermal insulation materials
Total industry turnover	4 642 million RON <i>equivalent to</i> 932 million EUR <i>equivalent to</i> 49 EUR per capita	959 million RON <i>equivalent to</i> 192 million EUR <i>equivalent to</i> 10 EUR per capita	832 million BGN <i>equivalent to</i> 425 million EUR <i>equivalent to</i> 66 EUR per capita	--	363.4 billion USD <i>equivalent to</i> 340 billion EUR	31.40 billion USD <i>equivalent to</i> 29.4 billion EUR
Average turnover per company	663 million RON <i>equivalent to</i> 133 million EUR	9 million RON <i>equivalent to</i> 1.8 million EUR	--	--	--	--
No. of employees in the sector	2 788	1 712	1 364	--	--	--
Average no. of employees per company	398	17	--	--	--	--
Total R&D investments	--	--	508,000 BGN <i>equivalent to</i> 260,000 EUR	--	--	--
Tons produced per year	10.2 million tons	--	--	--	4.1 billion tons	--

4.1.4. Market overview - conclusion

Even though, the market share was previously low, the new investments from low-carbon cement and bio-based insulation industries shows a rise of interest bot at European level, but also for Bulgaria and Romania. Efforts need to be taken both to encourage the demand from the national and local governments, combined with efforts like AFCOS project to override barriers for the wider use of these materials.

4.2. Survey

4.2.1. Survey contents and goals

In order to collect a large amount of feedback from market stakeholders of the analyzed fields, a survey was developed. The survey contents were initially proposed by the AFCOS project members. Thereafter, the survey was presented in the first stakeholder meetings under task T2.4 and was finalized including suggestions coming from the stakeholders.

The survey was presented as an online application, developed to make it easy for the respondents to answer

the proposed questions. The survey contents were presented in English, but also translated in Romanian and Bulgarian languages. This is because of the interest of this project to investigate with particular attention the Romanian and the Bulgarian markets. All the answers were then collected.

Survey distribution started on February 2024 and was closed at the end of April 2024. Survey was first distributed to the stakeholders taking part to the AFCOS project meetings, asking them to distribute it in turn among their contacts. Moreover, the survey was distributed also to other contacts of the project members.

The survey was organized as follows.

1. Introduction to AFCOS project.

2. Data management disclaimer and acceptance.

3. Stakeholder information data input.

Name, affiliation, country, working field, experience in the field.

4. Expertise field.

Selection among the two product families: Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products OR Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

The following questions are different depending on this answer.

5. Identification of barriers for innovation, with special focus on standardization barriers.

6. Identification of standardization urgencies.

7. Thank you and description of next steps.

The main goal of the survey was to collect inputs from stakeholders of the field, based on which organize the discussions held within the meetings of the project. The objective was to identify:

- the perceived growth of innovations and market size in the next years;
- the main barriers preventing the growth of the market, focusing especially on barriers in the standardization field;
- the experience of the stakeholders in the field, reporting on situations where they faced problems with standardization lacks and how they overcame barriers;
- the actions they suggest implementing in order to simplify the market growth and overcoming existing barriers.

As previously reported, the survey inputs were concentrated on two product families. Based on this, the idea is to identify general actions which can also be expanded also to different products.

The main outcomes of the survey and a detailed critical analysis of the received answers is provided in the following paragraphs.

4.2.2. Categorization of the respondents

We received 41 answers to the survey questions.

On the left hand side of Figure 28 we show the country provenience of the respondents, showing that the largest amount of interviewees come from the countries of the main partners of the AFCOS project: 46% of people come from Bulgaria (19 answers), 29% from Romania (12 answers) and 15% from Italy (6 answers). The remaining interviewees come from other European countries.

On the right hand side of Figure 28 we show the experience in the field of the respondents, showing that we mainly received responses from very expert people: more than 70% of the people have more than 10 years of experience in the field, and about 15% have 5 to 10 years of experience.

Figure 28. Provenience of the respondents by country (left) and experience in the field (right).

In Figure 29 we show the working field of the respondents. The most represented area is that of product manufacturers (29%), followed by building construction (16%), certification (14%), building design (13%) and standardization bodies (6%). Other entries represent 5% or less of the respondents. We can generally state that we had the chance to select a quite wide range of expertise.

Summarizing, more than 50% of respondents came from product manufacturing, building construction or building design, providing a full representation of the market of the selected products.

Figure 29. Working field of the respondents.

Figure 30 shows the expertise area of the respondents, 68% of which belong to the low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products field, while the remaining 32% belong to the field of bio-based products

for the insulation of the buildings' envelope.

Figure 30. Expertise area of the respondents

4.2.3. Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products

4.2.3.1. Market and technological improvements

First specific questions for the stakeholders of the field of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products were about their perceptions about the changes they expect in the next 10 years. Results are shown in Figure 31.

From the left-hand side of the figure, we note that stakeholders expect the business in the field growing very much in the next 10 years. Votes 4 and 5 cover about 55% of the answers, meaning that most of the interviewees expect the market size development to be very important.

The expected market growth reflects stakeholders' expectations regarding the effect technological improvements will have on the market, shown on the right-hand side of the figure. In fact, more than 65% of the interviewees expect that market will be affected by technological improvements with high or very high impact.

Summarizing, we see that both business and technological improvements are expected to grow very much, they appear clearly related.

Figure 31. Expected business growth (left) and effect of technological improvements on the market (right) in the next 10 years in the field of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products. Votes go from 1 (meaning “not at all”) to 5 (“a lot”).

The following questions were about the indications about areas with the expected higher technological improvements and with the higher need to improve existing standards. The outcomes are shown in Figure 32.

Here we notice that most of the technological improvements are expected in the cement and in the concrete fields (respectively 30% and 28% of the answers), followed by prefabricate concrete products (22%). Less improvements are expected in the other products.

Similarly, also the need to improve existing standards are indicated for cement and concrete (respectively 26% and 31% of the answers), while standards referred to other cement-based products have less need to be improved.

Both the questions and their answers allow us to state that the technological improvements and the need to change standards start from cement and then reflect to products based on it.

Figure 32. Areas with the expected higher technological improvements (left) and with the higher need to improve existing standards (right)

Figure 33 shows on the left the sectors where interviewees faced main barriers preventing the growth of innovations. The sector with the largest number of answers is infrastructure (47%) followed by residential (34%) and commercial (18%).

On the right-hand side of Figure 33 we show the answers obtained to the question where we asked to indicate which kind of limitation factor they faced. We can notice that just 14% of the answers indicate the limiting factor as related to the technical characteristics of the product, while most of the answers indicate that the limitation factor was related to legislative or normative contexts (80% of the answers in total). This underlines the importance and the impact that the topics treated in the AFCOS project can have on this market, since the main barriers preventing its growth are related to lacks in the existing legislative or standardization contexts.

Figure 33. Sectors with barriers preventing the growth of innovations (left) and main limitation factor (right).

4.2.3.2. Technical changes through cement decarbonization

The following questions were related more specifically to the technical changes that can guide the route towards decarbonization of cement field. These questions were introduced to identify which are the decarbonization actions that stakeholders feel more impactful, trying to identify which are the technical adaptations that updated standards and laws should take into account.

In this framework, question shown in Figure 34 aimed to identify the most promising strategies that stakeholders indicate as enablers for the reduction of embodied carbon in concrete products.

We underline here that interviewees were allowed to provide more than one single answer. We notice that, among 28 interviewees belonging to this area, we received 128 answers. This means that each of them indicated in average more than 4 answers. This allows us to conclude that the decarbonization approach in the cement field cannot be performed referring just to a single action, but stakeholders believe that a spectrum of different actions should be taken.

Figure 34. Most promising strategies to reduce embodied carbon in concrete products.

In the following table, we list the actions ordered by number of answers. We notice that none of them emerged over the others.

Action	Nr. Answers
Increase using different energy sources (non-fossil fuels) for cement production	17
Using alternative binders whenever possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)	17
Carbon capture and utilization (CCU, that is capturing CO2 emissions and converting them into useful products)	17
Using renewable energy in cement (and concrete) production	16
Improving energy efficiency in cement plants (or excess heat second use)	16
Increase use of supplementary cementitious materials	15
CO2 sequestration at the cement plant chimneys and subsequent carbon storage (CCS, including using excess heat to CO2 treatment)	12
Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO2)	9
Lowering the temperature for cement production for newly designed cements	9

Figure 35 shows the main identified barriers presented by today's European cement and concrete standards to tackle the embodied carbon of concrete.

Here we notice that 38% of the interviewees indicated as the main barrier the prescriptive approach of concrete standards (referring to issues with use of novel constituents, minimum cement content, water/cement ratios, etc.).

The second most answered option referred to prescriptive approach of cement standards (referring to the limit of the use of supplementary cementitious materials and novel cements). This answer was indicated by 25% of the interviewees.

By summing up these first two answers, we notice that more than 60% of the interviewees identified the

main barriers as related to prescriptive approach of today's standards, both of cement and of concrete.

Finally, a smaller amount of the respondents identified the main barriers as related to a perceived lack of harmonization of concrete standards on national level (25%) and to a lack of attention for potential of CO2 storage in concrete products (11%).

Figure 35. Main barriers presented by today's European cement and concrete standards to tackle the embodied carbon of concrete.

4.2.3.3. Identification of main problems in the market

To provide to the stakeholders to talk more about their perceptions in this field, we proposed some open questions where we asked them to provide more specific information and descriptions of their experiences with barriers in the market growth.

In order to have a clearer vision of the main identified lacks, we grouped these barriers into three categories, which could briefly summarize the identified barrier. This categorization results from a discussion with the stakeholders, which endorsed this grouping proposal. The grouping categories are the following:

- Demand side/market problems: unfavorable price to value and need for a life cycle and embodied carbon approach
- Limitations with allowed components in cement and concrete (admixtures, alternative binders, ...)
- Limitations related to a still partly prescriptive rather than fully performance-based approach in standards

In Table 25, we list the problems identified by the stakeholders, and for each of them we also indicate the category to which it belongs.

Table 25. Main market problems identified by stakeholders about low-carbon cement and low-carbon cement-based products.

Identified problems have been categorized in 3 categories

Significant barriers exist today for the route to market of low carbon cement and concrete solutions. These include:

- Prescriptive cement standards (EN 197 series): cement standards violate CPR article 1 (requiring a performance-based approach). This results in a lack of a technology neutral standards, and significant costs for new products (outside scope of standard) to obtain CE marking.

<p>- Prescriptive concrete standards (EN 206): due to explicit reference to EN 197 series, EN 206 is also prescriptive (resulting in the same issues). Furthermore, specifications drive up the consumption of cement (e.g. minimum cement content) and/or demand for certain water to cement ratios. All this results in a lack of level-playing field for low carbon solutions.</p> <p>- Lack of harmonization of EN 206: the European internal market is non-existing, with different national provisions in the annexes to EN206. This creates additional barriers for the rapid deployment of new innovations.</p>
<p>This growth is mostly specific to the product (concrete) and not necessary the market: regarding the low carbon solutions, the focus of the market is directed towards energy efficiency of the building and less on embodied carbon.</p>
<p>Reactive Calcium Carbonate to be recognized as a component of cement as well as an addition to concrete production to reducing the clinker content.</p>
<p>All concrete products having restrictions to using alternative side streams not mentioned in standard EN 197.</p>
<p>We face problems with products having non harmonized standards in terms of certification and defining their application domains.</p>
<p>Concrete and cement with reduced carbon footprint aren't very affordable in terms of price and supply.</p>
<p>Concrete (ready mix concrete).</p>
<p>Standards restrict the use of new materials as cement replacement or supplementary cements. It has specific set of supplementary cements in the standard and does not encourage to use new innovative materials. It increases the dependency of small startups with cement company and that destroys the innovation capacity in this field.</p>
<p>Reinforced concrete</p>
<p>Introduction of low carbon cements standards EN 197-5 and EN 197-6 in concrete standard 206.</p>
<p>It is almost impossible to make innovations in road infrastructure as everything is in the hands of the road agency, which spoil any innovations.</p>
<p>The barriers are related to the use of low carbon cements in concrete production.</p>
<p>Administrative burdens, corruption, high prices and low quality of the final product. No control.</p>
<p>Products for roads</p>
<p>Answers relating forecast for the next 10 years have to be considered as affected by a high degree of uncertainty.</p>
<p>Construction technical regulations in Romania is a well developed, detailed and extensive system. Updating and revision of norms is a difficult and long term process which sometimes can not follow the evolution of European standardization.</p>
<p>EN 197 imposes strict requirements on cement content, with restrictions for raw materials. Then concrete standard EN 206 refers to EN 197 and many concrete product standards refer to EN 206 thus, leaving little space for alternative materials and innovation.</p>
<p>Yes, the narrative in the building industry should move towards lifecycle approach of a building when reduction of CO2 emissions is envisioned.</p>
<p>The norms/standards are in urgent need of updating (other markets show that it is possible) + legislators have allowed for to long that cement and concrete standards where not aligned with the CPR. This creates significant legal uncertainty in the future.</p>
<p>In public procurement the approach normally used is not to require particular performance from a product, because its distribution on the market is still limited. This is seen as potentially limiting the ability of manufacturers to</p>

participate in the tender. It is necessary to provide a different approach, which rewards more those who are able to provide products with the required performance

Performance-based material standards should come in action.

Example: Instead of defining what can be a cement, it should be defined in a way that a cement or supplementary can be anything with so and so properties.

Secondary products, by products and semi products are one of the solutions for circular utilization of materials and reducing extraction of natural resources

4.2.3.4. *Lacks in the standardization field*

Results of Figure 33 allowed to identify standardization as one of the main barriers preventing the growth of innovations in the field of bio-based products for thermal insulation. Similarly, we note that one of the most recognized barriers according to results shown in Table 25 is related to the lack of product standards.

We aimed then to explore further the situations where the main limiting factor was determined by gaps in the standardization. For this purpose, we asked interviewees to classify their experience with problems caused by gaps in the standardization into the following categories:

- Inhomogeneous applicability of standards on regional / national level,
- Missing standards for a specific product,
- Outdated standards for new products / new product variants,
- Other.

Results are shown in Figure 36, and show how the main barrier was determined by the presence of outdated standards for new products / new product variants. This answer is immediately followed by the missing standard for a specific product.

We note from Figure 36 that another answer provided by stakeholders is related to the dishomogeneous applicability of standards on regional and national level. However, this answer is perceived less important than others related to the need to update existing norms or to add new ones.

So we can summarize that, according to the interviewees, in the field low-carbon cement and low-carbon cement based products, main standardization gaps are related to the lack of standards for specific product or to the need to update them.

Figure 36. Categorization of gaps in the standardization

By going through the free comments proposed by stakeholders in Table 25, we can have more details about the gaps summarized here in Figure 36.

4.2.3.5. Urgencies in the standardization field

We aimed then to identify urgencies to make progress in standards.

First, we have tried into group them into classes. Therefore, we asked respondents to provide their feedback on how they categorize urgencies. Results are shown in Figure 37.

From the figure almost all the stakeholders agree on the fact that market needs "green products", but existing standards lack mutual compatibility.

Figure 37. Categorization of urgencies to make progress on standards.

We asked then stakeholders to describe more into details about these urgencies as open questions. The main results are shown in Table 26.

Also in this case, by the help of stakeholders, we have grouped urgencies into the three following categories:

- A. Market urgencies (e.g. price to value),
- B. Urgencies related to product performances,
- C. Urgencies related to lack of product standards or proper legislation.

Table 26. Main urgencies identified by stakeholders about low-carbon cement and low-carbon cement-based products. Identified urgencies have been categorized in 3 categories.

Currently there are no product standards that classify green products and, therefore, there is no possibility to prescribe green products in public procurement procedures.
Extensive research and innovation demonstrate the viability of environmentally friendly materials as substitutes for traditional concrete products. However, outdated standards impede the adoption of these innovative solutions
Clearly for decarbonization goal
It is not the market who needs this but the whole planet. It is clear that we need to reduce CO2 emissions worldwide. It is clear that cement and concrete are big contributors to overall CO2 emissions in the world and it is a much-needed product for development of society.
The new issue of carbon neutrality of products requires further regulatory development, despite the recent issue of the ISO 14068 standard. It is important to better regulate the methods for recognizing compensation actions deemed reliable and credible.
There is a demand for low carbon cements, a readiness for cement plants to produce them, but they are not being produced because Concrete Standard EN 206 has not recognized them as a type of cement for concrete mixes.
as I wrote, we cannot use our ETA directly!
A user-friendly DPP
BIM design
To public green products standards.
Launch of national projects could facilitate collection of evidence and progress toward the common good.
ETA by EOTA ... but it takes time and is expensive.!
There are standards for EPD's, the next step would be to create a framework to define, compare, benchmark different types of concrete and cement.
Regulate the requirements and control methods relating to Programs that offer to the market the purchase of compensation measures, similarly to what happens in other similar sector (for example ETS program)
That the topic be reopened in TC-5 of the BDS and that the introduction in EN 206 of EN 197-5 and EN 197-6 occur. This is the only tool available at this time.
Change EN 206 as SOON AS POSSIBLE
More awareness of low carbon cements/concretes - composition and properties, experience in other European countries, tests in Bulgarian laboratories.

4.2.4. Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope

4.2.4.1. Market and technological improvements

Also for the stakeholders of the field of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope, first specific questions were about their perceptions about the changes they expect in the next 10 years. Results are shown in Figure 38Figure 31.

From the left-hand side of the figure, we note that stakeholders expect the business in the field growing in the next 10 years. Vote 4 covers more than 50% of the answers, meaning that most of the interviewees expect the market size to increase.

The expected market growth reflects stakeholders' expectations regarding the effect technological improvements will have on the market, shown on the right-hand side of the figure. In fact, more than 60% of the interviewees expect that market will be affected by technological improvements with high or very high impact.

Summarizing, we see that both business and technological improvements are expected to grow very much, they appear clearly related.

Figure 38. Expected business growth (left) and effect of technological improvements on the market (right) in the next 10 years in the field of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope. Votes go from 1 (meaning "not at all") to 5 ("a lot").

The following questions were about the indications about areas with the expected higher technological improvements and with the higher need to improve existing standards. The outcomes are shown in Figure 39Figure 32.

Here we notice that most of the technological improvements are expected to affect very similarly thermal, fire and acoustic insulation, with a slight predominance of the first (39% against 32% and 29%).

Similarly, also the need to improve existing standards are indicated mostly for thermal insulation products (45%), while fire and acoustic insulation products are indicated by 27% of the interviewees each.

Here we anticipate something that will become clearer from the following questions. Often, the standardization improvement needs for thermal insulating products is due to their fire-reaction performance.

Figure 39. Areas with the expected higher technological improvements (left) and with the higher need to improve existing standards (right).

Figure 40 shows on the left the sectors where interviewees faced main barriers preventing the growth of innovations. The sector with the largest number of answers is residential (56%) followed by commercial (22%) and infrastructure (17%).

Here we can notice a very strong difference with respect to the answers found from stakeholders of the low carbon cement field, which was shown in Figure 33, where infrastructure field emerged. This reflects the very different characteristics of the two markets, which look towards very different applications and feel very different problems in very different areas.

On the right-hand side of Figure 40 we show the answers obtained to the question where we asked to indicate which kind of limitation factor they faced. Here we can notice that, very similarly to the field of low carbon cement, just a minority of the interviewees indicate the limiting factor as related to the technical characteristics of the product (just 28% of the answers). Almost 80% of the answers in total indicate that the limitation factor was related to legislative or normative contexts (80% of the answers in total).

This underlines that, even if the market is very different, both low carbon cement and bio-based insulation products share barriers preventing their growth deriving from lacks in the existing legislative or standardization. This underlines the importance and the impact that the topics treated in the AFCOS project can have both these markets, and more in general in all the construction products markets which are very

related to innovations.

Figure 40. Sectors with barriers preventing the growth of innovations (left) and main limitation factor (right).

4.2.4.2. Identification of main problems in the market

To provide to the stakeholders to talk more about their perceptions in this field, we proposed some open questions where we asked them to provide more specific information and descriptions of their experiences with barriers in the market growth.

In order to have a clearer vision of the main identified lacks, we grouped these barriers into three categories, which could briefly summarize the identified barrier. This categorization results from a discussion with the stakeholders, which endorsed this grouping proposal. The grouping categories are the following:

- A. Demand side/market problems: unfavorable price to value;
- B. Problems with expected product performances (e.g. concerns about fire reaction);
- C. Lack of product standard: need to enlarge applicability of existing norms or need to have new standards.

In Table 27, we list the problems identified by the stakeholders, and for each of them we also indicate the category to which it belongs.

Table 27. Main market problems identified by stakeholders about biobased products for building envelope insulation. Identified problems have been categorized in 3 categories.

LanaTerm thermal sheeps wool insulation.
I sell thermal insulation from wood fibers produced in Germany. The German standard puts them in fire resistance class B2 (they are fireproof), and the European standard in class E. However, in the thermosystem, that is, with plaster on them, the standard puts them in class B2, accepted in construction. This is very difficult to meaning. Architects and designers refuse to use natural insulation on the grounds that they are not fire resistant. They prefer basalt wool (class A, fireproof) and oppose the promotion of natural insulation.
Cellulose fibre insulation
The price of the product is too high compared to standard materials.
Yes. polystyrene insulation burns. But they are very much used. Basalt wool insulation melts. Natural wood fiber insulation carbonizes, turns brown and does not burn with a flame, does not emit toxic fumes. They are better than polystyrene in terms of fire behavior. In a new standard, criteria of equivalence between them should be found.

We cannot talk about the development of the bio-based materials sector, about a market in which these materials can obtain a larger share, if we do not support the standardisation of these products. Today, manufacturers of cellulose fibre insulation produce on the basis of individual technical standards. In theory we have a product in dozens, hundreds of variants. The risk of inefficient or non-compliant products being sold on the market is very high, and the risk of having buildings with high energy efficiency deficiencies is also high. Cellulose fibre thermocellulose needs a product standard, for added credibility, for the benefits it can bring, for the sustainable building materials market.

Evaluating the performance of a product that does not have CE marking requirements for the specific purpose of thermal insulation in buildings is often done without taking into account the correct technical and statistical rules, reducing the insulation value to a number that in reality is not correct and comparable with the performance claimed by a CE-marked insulation material. In addition, it is necessary to make assessments of proper durability and sustainability. The assessment of environmental sustainability must take into account all the indicators in the LCA, and sometimes with new materials brought to market this is not done. So there needs to be more rigor in evaluating products before they are placed on the market to ensure results today and over time.

More incentives for environmental-friendly products as well as taxes on products which are compliant with circular models should be present.

4.2.4.3. *Lacks in the standardization field*

Results of Figure 40 allowed to identify standardization as one of the main barriers preventing the growth of innovations in the field of bio-based products for thermal insulation. Similarly, we note that one of the mostly recognized barriers according to results shown in Table 27 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** is related to the lack of product standards.

We aimed then to explore more the situations where the main limiting factor was determined by gaps in the standardization. For this purpose, we asked interviewees to classify their experience with problems caused by gaps in the standardization into the following categories:

- Dishomogeneous applicability of standards on regional / national level,
- Missing standards for a specific product,
- Outdated standards for new products / new product variants,
- Other.

Results are shown in Figure 41, and show how the main barrier was determined by missing standards for a specific product, immediately followed by the barriers caused by the presence of outdated standards for new products / new product variants. Therefore we can summarize that, according to the interviewees, in the field of bio-based products for the building insulation main standardization gaps are related to the lack of standards for specific product of to the need to update them.

Figure 41. Categorization of gaps in the standardization

Again, by going through the free comments proposed by stakeholders in Table 27, we can recognize many contents related to the lack of norms or to the lack of updated standards.

4.2.4.4. Urgencies in the standardization field

We aimed then to identify urgencies to make progress in standards.

First, we have tried into group them into classes. Therefore, we asked respondents to provide their feedback on how they categorize urgencies. Results are shown in Figure 42.

From the figure we can see that the mostly answered question is about the fact that market needs "green products", but existing standards lack mutual compatibility.

Secondly, stakeholders put the attention on the fact that market needs products with digital information, but the required data are not standardized.

Figure 42. Categorization of urgencies to make progress on standards.

We asked then stakeholders to describe more into details about these urgencies as open questions. The main results are shown in Table 28.

Also in this case, by the help of stakeholders, we have grouped urgencies into the three following categories:

- A. Market urgencies (e.g. price to value),
- B. Urgencies related to product performances,
- C. Urgencies related to lack of product standards or proper legislation.

Table 28. Main urgencies identified by stakeholders about biobased products for building envelope insulation. Identified urgencies.

Currently there are no product standards that classify green products and, therefore, there is no possibility to prescribe green products in public procurement procedures.
Extensive research and innovation demonstrate the viability of environmentally friendly materials as substitutes for traditional concrete products. However, outdated standards impede the adoption of these innovative solutions
Clearly for decarbonization goal
It is not the market who needs this but the whole planet. It is clear that we need to reduce CO2 emissions worldwide. It is clear that cement and concrete are big contributors to overall CO2 emissions in the world and it is a much-needed product for development of society.
The new issue of carbon neutrality of products requires further regulatory development, despite the recent issue of the ISO 14068 standard. It is important to better regulate the methods for recognizing compensation actions deemed reliable and credible..
As I wrote, we cannot use our ETA directly!
A user-friendly DPP
BIM design

To public green products standards.
Launch of national projects could facilitate collection of evidence and progress toward the common good.
ETA by EOTA ... but it takes time and is expensive.!
There are standards for EPD's, the next step would be to create a framework to define, compare, benchmark different types of concrete and cement.
Regulate the requirements and control methods relating to Programs that offer to the market the purchase of compensation measures, similarly to what happens in other similar sector (for example ETS programme)
More awareness of low carbon cements/concretes - composition and properties, experience in other European countries, tests in Bulgarian laboratories.

4.2.5. Digitalization of technical and environmental product performances

The AFCOS project aims to analyze standardization of construction products in the framework of the “twin transition”. Therefore, an important aspect to be considered is that of the use of digital information for construction products. In order to assess the knowledge of stakeholders in this field, we proposed some questions directly related to digitalization of technical and environmental product performances.

According to discussions held within the project consortium, the following questions have been not proposed to Bulgarian stakeholders.

On the left-hand side of Figure 43 we show the familiarity of the stakeholders with using/exchanging information via open standards. We can note that very few of them are familiar or very familiar with them (23% in total). About 46% of the interviewees are not familiar or very low familiar, while 32% of them expressed medium-level familiarity. These answers allow us to conclude that there is still a lot of work to do for the promotion of the use of digital information exchange in construction product field.

The question reported on the right-hand side of Figure 43 was about the main information that, according to stakeholders, to be conveyed in BIM (Building Information Modeling). More than a half of the interviewees (55%) agree on the fact that all the LCA impact categories should be included, while according to 33% energy information are those to be included.

Figure 43. On the left: familiarity with using/exchanging information via open standards (votes go from 1 to 5, moving from not familiar at all to very familiar). On the right: main information to be conveyed in BIM.

Final questions were related to the adoption of EPDs (Environmental Product Declarations). These questions were asked just to product manufacturers.

First question is shown on the left-hand side of Figure 44, showing that almost 90% of the interviewees already adopt or aim to adopt soon EPDs for their products.

Similarly, from the results shown on the right-hand side of Figure 44 we see that 14% of the interviewees already adopt EPDs, while 71% of them is planning to adopt them in the short term (1 to 3 years).

These results show how the EPD adoption process is really ongoing, and the majority of the interviewed stakeholders already introduced them or plan to introduce them very soon.

Figure 44. Adoption or intention to adopt EPD (left) and EPD implementation timing (right). This question was asked just to product manufacturers.

4.3. Discussions in the research groups

After receiving the outcomes from the survey, new meetings with stakeholders were held. The first objective of these meetings was to identify the main legislation and standardization barriers preventing the market growth of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope. Once that the barriers were identified, the group activity was focused on the identification of actions that could overcome these barriers.

Outcomes of these discussions are shown in paragraphs 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 respectively. Due to the very different market sizes and characteristics of the two product families, these outcomes are shown in two different ways. On the one hand, the cement market is very mature, well organized and already strongly regulated. Therefore, it was possible to list a set of structured actions, providing a final priority level list. On the other hand, bio-based products market is still under development and consists of a variety of different products, which often are still not regulated by laws or norms. In this case, it has been possible to identify a more general set of actions aiming mostly at introducing a first level of regulation to this market.

4.3.1. Low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products

In section 4.3.1.1, standardization barriers identified by stakeholders of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products are shown. Corresponding corrective actions are then analyzed in section 4.3.1.2,

while finally in section 4.3.1.3 a priority level list is identified.

We emphasize the fact that the identified barriers and the corresponding corrective actions included in paragraphs 4.3.1.1, 4.3.1.2 and 4.3.1.3 derive from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. The proposals reported in this paragraph are a summary of the conversations had with these stakeholders. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved. They are a summary of the opinions that emerged and the solutions that these stakeholders suggested.

Specific meetings were held with Bulgarian stakeholders by the AFCOS partner Cleantech, together with the activities held under tasks T2.2 and T2.3. The outcomes of these meetings are reported in section 4.3.1.4.

4.3.1.1. Identified barriers

Based on the survey outcomes and to the discussions held during the stakeholder meetings, a list of barriers was identified. For each of the barriers, a corresponding objective was listed. The objective refers to the final goal that should be reached once that the barrier is removed.

As it was identified by results shown in Figure 32, main standardization barriers affect on the one hand cement and on the other hand the main cement-based product, which is concrete. Effect of standardization barriers on other cement-based products was felt as less relevant. For this reason, together with stakeholders, it was decided to concentrate on barriers for cement and for concrete.

The identified barriers and corresponding objectives are listed in Table 29 and in Table 30.

Table 29. Identified barriers and improvement objectives for the low-carbon cement sector. These barriers derive from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CEMENT			
BARRIER		OBJECTIVE	
B-CE-1	Cement regulations are still too prescription-based, preventing the development of new cements	O-CE-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in cement regulations
B-CE-2	Often modern cements cannot be CE marked because of harmonized standards are lacking	O-CE-2	CE mark modern cements (e.g. with reduced amount of clinker, with recycled material, ...)
B-CE-3	Current standards limit the use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)	O-CE-3	Increase use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)
B-CE-4	Current standards limit the use of alternative hydraulic binders	O-CE-4	Using alternative hydraulic binders when possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)
B-CE-5	Current legislation does not encourage re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components	O-CE-5	Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO ₂)
B-CE-6	Current legislation does not encourage carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used	O-CE-6	Ensure appropriate recognition of carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used
B-CE-7	Current legislation does not encourage the use of more sustainable cements	O-CE-7	Inclusion of LCA impact categories in cement DOP as required, no NPD
B-CE-8	Current legislation does not encourage digitalization of product characteristics	O-CE-8	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport

Table 30. Identified barriers and improvement objectives for the low-carbon concrete sector. These barriers derive from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CONCRETE			
BARRIER		OBJECTIVE	
B-CO-1	Concrete regulations are still too prescription-based, preventing the development of new cements	O-CO-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in concrete regulations
B-CO-2	Since concrete standards are not harmonized, national application standards exist, causing different rules in different EU countries	O-CO-2	Need to “harmonize” national application standards through EN 206
B-CO-3	Large variability of nationally applicable technical specifications complementary to EN 206, annex M	O-CO-3	Reduce variability by providing guidance and ranges to a limited number of indexes
B-CO-4	Promotion of low-impact concrete suffers the difficult interpretation of all LCA impact categories	O-CO-4	Summarize the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete Promote and spread knowledge to increase market demand for concrete with declared environmental characteristics
B-CO-5	Current legislation does not encourage carbon capturing solutions	O-CO-5	Ensure proper use and transparency on carbon capturing solutions (CCS, CCU, re-carbonation of components at a production stage)
B-CO-6	General lack of availability of LCA-relevant information	O-CO-6	Ensure the availability of LCA information
B-CO-7	Current legislation does not encourage digitalization of product characteristics	O-CO-7	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport

4.3.1.2. Proposed actions

Once that barriers were identified, it was necessary to identify how to overcome them and so to reach the corresponding objectives. So, for each objective, the aimed to identify:

- a list of actions that can help overcoming the barriers,
- a list of levers that can facilitate the achievement of the objectives.

The list of these actions and levers was prepared together with the stakeholders, and it is shown in Table 31 and Table 32.

Once that actions were identified, the following goal was to identify what actions should be taken with the highest priority. To this purpose, we prepared an exercise that has been performed by each of the involved stakeholders. We asked them to rate each of the actions in terms of urgency and importance.

The following definitions of urgency and importance have been used.

- URGENT matters:
 - require immediate action,
 - are unavoidable,
 - (often) come with clear consequences for not completing these tasks

For this exercise, we rate urgency as related to actions to be taken soon and necessarily, mostly due to existing parallel standardization or regulatory working streams.

MORE URGENT = TO BE NECESSARILY DONE SOONER

- IMPORTANT matters:
 - contribute to long-term goals,
 - require planning,
 - require deep, complex prolonged action.

For this exercise, we rate importance as related to actions which are needed in the mid term and are expected to have a high impact, mostly due to the business environment.

MORE IMPORTANT = WITH GREATER MID TERM IMPACT

In each of the cases, rate goes from 1 to 3, where:

- Rate 1 means most urgent/most important,
- Rate 3 means less urgent/less important.

The rating for each of the actions are shown again in Table 31 and Table 32.

Ratings result from responses from 5 different stakeholders, and are expressed as average values.

Table 31. Low carbon cement sector: for each objective, identified action and lever with rating in terms of urgency and importance. Objectives, actions and levers derive from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CEMENT					
	OBJECTIVE	ACTION	LEVER	URGENCY	IMPORTANCE
O-CE-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in cement regulations	Consider comparable standards in mature markets Considering prioritize performances over composition ensuring comparable or higher durability levels	To match EU standards with US standards New CPR	1 (avg.)	1 (avg.)
O-CE-2	CE mark modern cements (e.g. with reduced amount of clinker, with recycled	Broadening the scope of EN 197-1 standard including cements	New CPR Define	1 (avg.)	1 (avg.)

	material, ...)	today on the market (incl. those in the scope of EN 197-5 and EN 197-6) (already ongoing)	performances linked to essential characteristics related to sustainability into levels and/or classes (so NPD options cannot be used)		
O-CE-3	Increase use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)	Considering prioritize performances over composition	Education and training on innovative cements (e.g. early strength, durability and suitability to new low-carbon mixes)	1.8 (avg.)	1.8 (avg.)
O-CE-4	Using alternative hydraulic binders when possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)	Considering prioritize performances over composition	Education and training on innovative cements	2 (avg.)	2 (avg.)
O-CE-5	Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO2)	Defining an approach independent from techniques and products to assess and disclose the CO2 stored	Considering existing standard from US Consider updating hEN standards for aggregates for structural concretes Education and training	1.75 (avg.)	1.25 (avg.)
O-CE-6	Ensure appropriate recognition of carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used	Need to identify a common reference for carbon accounting and disclosure in all regulatory references	EU taxonomy Promoting EU pilots to showcase the adoption of CCS and CCU in both real building scale and plant scale	1 (avg.)	1.25 (avg.)
O-CE-7	Inclusion of LCA impact categories in cement DOP as	Introduce essential characteristics in	New CPR prescriptions	1 (avg.)	1 (avg.)

	required, no NPD	the next EN 197-1 relative to basic requirement n. 7 in classes (already ongoing)	Work of SH03 committee (horizontal group of notified bodies) CPR acquis process, SG06		
O-CE-8	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport	Already ongoing process in new CPR Include in the product standards provisions concerning digital information Some possible references are: EN ISO 23386 (which provides information on the process) EN ISO 23387 (which provides the data structure) EN ISO 12006 (which provides the data model)	Coordination with CEN/TC 442 activities Education and training to SMEs	2 (avg.)	1.5 (avg.)

Table 32. Low carbon concrete sector: for each objective, identified action and lever with rating in terms of urgency and importance. Objectives, actions and levers derive from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CONCRETE					
	OBJECTIVE	ACTION	LEVER	URGENCY	IMPORTANCE
O-CO-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in concrete regulations	Considering the removal of minimum cement content or in alternative keeping a minimum total equivalent binder content.	Using an equivalency k-factor of alternative binding materials to be counted into the total minimum	1.4 (avg.)	1 (avg.)

		However, provisions on maximum water/cement ratio could be kept for durability reasons	binders content		
O-CO-2	Need to “harmonize” national application standards through EN 206	Harmonization of EN 206 for CE marking of concrete “bypassing” national application standards Suboptimal: force the use of a standardized “DOP” without CE marking	Work of TC 104	1.6 (avg.)	1.3 (avg.)
O-CO-3	EN 206 annex M provides guidance to existing provisions by place of use.	Harmonization of EN206 would remove this barrier. Promote the adoption of EPDs for each type of concrete	Accelerate diffusion of EPDs and online platforms	2 (avg.)	2 (avg.)
O-CO-4	Summarize the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete Promote and spread knowledge to increase market demand for concrete with declared environmental characteristics	Introduce an additional synthetic indicator into “DOP” (calculated based on environmental impact characteristics typical of EPDs, e.g. mostly based on GWP and AD). This could be used for marketing and tenders, broader LCA impacts should be kept Potentially reduce	CPR evolution	1.25 (avg.)	1.25 (avg.)

		the number of indicators to be used for increasing user's awareness, prioritizing GWP			
O-CO-5	Ensure proper use and transparency on carbon capturing solutions (CCS, CCU, re-carbonation of components at a production stage)	<p>Three key factors determine the GWP value of a GHG:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the ability of the gas to absorb infrared radiation, - where along the electromagnetic spectrum (i.e. what wavelengths) the gas absorbs radiation, and - the atmospheric lifetime of the gas. <p>Hence all gasses should be taken into consideration</p> <p>Provide the full breakdown of total GWP (with all contributions)</p>	<p>New CPR and harmonization of EN206</p> <p>Alignment between program operators for EPDs</p>	1.5 (avg.)	1.75 (avg.)
O-CO-6	Ensure the availability of LCA information	An EPD is a standardized document describing the LCA results for a specific product without revealing this sensitive information. EPD should be the reference, being a fully recognized tool.	New CPR pushing EPDs as mandatory	2.3 (avg.)	2.3 (avg.)
O-CO-7	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport	<p>Already ongoing process in new CPR</p> <p>Include in the product standards provisions</p>	<p>Coordination with CEN/TC 442 activities</p> <p>Education and training to SMEs</p>	1.6 (avg.)	1.3 (avg.)

		<p>concerning digital information</p> <p>Some possible references are:</p> <p>EN ISO 23386 (which provides information on the process)</p> <p>EN ISO 23387 (which provides the data structure)</p> <p>EN ISO 12006 (which provides the data model)</p>			
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4.3.1.3. Identification of priorities

Based on the actions rating based on urgency importance criteria shown in the previous section, priority can be assigned. Doing so, we referred to the 3x3 matrix shown in Figure 45. Based on the urgency and importance level, using this matrix we evaluate the corresponding priority level, where 1 means very high priority while 9 means very low priority.

		URGENCY		
		1=high	2=medium	3=low
IMPORTANCE	1=high	1	3	6
	2=medium	2	5	8
	3=low	4	7	9

Figure 45. 3x3 matrix used to assign priorities based on the urgency/importance criteria. Based on the urgency and importance level, using this matrix we evaluate the corresponding priority level, where 1 means very high priority while 9 means very low priority.

This table related to CEMENT is shown in Table 33.

Table 33. 3x3 matrix used to assign priorities about CEMENT. Matrix realized from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they

		IMPORTANCE		
		1 = high	2 = medium	3 = low
URGENCY	1 = high	O-CE-1 Move towards a more performance-based approach in cement regulations	O-CE-8 Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport	
		O-CE-2 CE mark modern cements (e.g. with reduced amount of clinker, with recycled material, ...)		
		O-CE-6 Ensure appropriate recognition of carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used		
		O-CE-7 Inclusion of LCA impact categories in cement DOP as required, no NPD		
		Priority 1	Priority 3	Priority 6
	2 = medium	O-CE-5 Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO2)	O-CE-3 Increase use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)	
			O-CE-4 Using alternative hydraulic binders when possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)	
		Priority 2	Priority 5	Priority 8
	3 = low			
Priority 4		Priority 7	Priority 9	

intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

Similarly, a table related to CONCRETE is shown in Table 34.

Table 34. 3x3 matrix used to assign priorities about CONCRETE. Matrix realized from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

		IMPORTANCE		
		1 = high	2 = medium	3 = low
URGENCY	1=high	O-CO-1 Move towards a more performance-based approach in concrete regulations	O-CO-5 Ensure proper use and transparency on carbon capturing solutions (CCS, CCU, re-carbonation of components)	

			at a production stage)	
		O-CO-4 Summarize the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete; promote and spread knowledge to increase market demand for concrete with declared environmental characteristics	O-CO-7 Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport	
		Priority 1	Priority 3	Priority 6
	2=medium	O-CO-2 Need to “harmonize” national application standards through EN 206	O-CO-3 EN 206 annex M provides guidance to existing provisions by place of use.	
		Priority 2	Priority 5	Priority 8
	3=low			O-CO-6 Ensure the availability of LCA information
		Priority 4	Priority 7	Priority 9

Summarizing results coming from Table 33 and Table 34, it is possible to identify priorities to the identified actions. Identified priority level for cement and concrete are shown in Table 35 and Table 36 respectively.

Table 35. Identified actions priority level for cement. The priority list is realized from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CEMENT				
PRIORITY LEVEL		OBJECTIVE	ACTION	LEVER
Priority level n. 1	O-CE-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in cement regulations	Consider comparable standards in mature markets	To match EU standards with US standards New CPR
			Considering prioritize performances over composition ensuring comparable or higher durability levels	

	O-CE-2	CE mark modern cements (e.g. with reduced amount of clinker, with recycled material, ...)	Broadening the scope of EN 197-1 standard including cements today on the market (incl. those in the scope of EN 197-5 and EN 197-6) (already ongoing)	New CPR Define performances linked to essential characteristics related to sustainability into levels and/or classes (so NPD options cannot be used)
	O-CE-6	Ensure appropriate recognition of carbon captured + sequestered // captured + used	Need to identify a common reference for carbon accounting and disclosure in all regulatory references	EU taxonomy Promoting EU pilots to showcase the adoption of CCS and CCU in both real building scale and plant scale
	O-CE-7	Inclusion of LCA impact categories in cement DOP as required, no NPD	Introduce essential characteristics in the next EN 197-1 relative to basic requirement n. 7 in classes (already ongoing)	New CPR prescriptions Work of SH03 committee (horizontal group of notified bodies) CPR acquis process, SG06
Priority level n. 2	O-CE-5	Re-carbonization of cement components or concrete components (not releasing CO2)	Defining an approach independent from techniques and products to assess and disclose the CO2 stored	Considering existing standard from US Consider updating hEN standards for aggregates for structural concretes Education and training
Priority level n. 3	O-CE-8	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which	Already ongoing process in new CPR	Coordination with CEN/TC 442 activities

		includes new Digital Product Passport	Include in the product norms provisions concerning digital information Some possible references are: EN ISO 23386 (which provides information on the process) EN ISO 23387 (which provides the data structure) EN ISO 12006 (which provides the data model)	Education and training to SMEs
Priority level n. 4	O-CE-3	Increase use of SCMs (supplementary cementitious materials)	Considering prioritize performances over composition	Education and training on innovative cements (e.g. early strength, durability and suitability to new low-carbon mixes)
	O-CE-4	Using alternative hydraulic binders when possible (alternative to clinker / Portland cement)	Considering prioritize performances over composition	Education and training on innovative cements

Table 36. Identified actions priority level for concrete. The priority list is realized from the discussions held within the stakeholder meetings of Task T2.4, listed in Table 6. They do not represent in any way the opinions of the AFCOS project partners, nor are they intended as ideas shared by all stakeholders involved

CONCRETE				
PRIORITY LEVEL	OBJECTIVE		ACTION	LEVER
Priority level n. 1	O-CO-1	Move towards a more performance-based approach in concrete regulations	Considering the removal of minimum cement content or in alternative keeping a minimum total	Using an equivalency k-factor of alternative binding materials to be counted into the total minimum binders

			<p>equivalent binder content.</p> <p>However, provisions on maximum water/cement ratio could be kept for durability reasons</p>	content
	O-CO-4	<p>Summarize the evaluation of the environmental impact of concrete</p> <p>Promote and spread knowledge to increase market demand for concrete with declared environmental characteristics</p>	<p>Introduce an additional synthetic indicator into “DOP” (calculated based on environmental impact characteristics typical of EPDs, e.g. mostly based on GWP and AD). This could be used for marketing and tenders, broader LCA impacts should be kept</p> <p>Potentially reduce the number of indicators to be used for increasing user’s awareness, prioritizing GWP</p>	CPR evolution
Priority level n. 2	O-CO-2	Need to “harmonize” national application standards through EN 206	<p>Harmonization of EN 206 for CE marking of concrete “bypassing” national application standards</p> <p>Suboptimal: force the use of a standardized “DOP” without CE marking</p>	Work of TC 104

Priority level n. 3	O-CO-5	Ensure proper use and transparence on carbon capturing solutions (CCS, CCU, re-carbonation of components at a production stage)	<p>Three key factors determine the GWP value of a GHG:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the ability of the gas to absorb infrared radiation, - where along the electromagnetic spectrum (i.e. what wavelengths) the gas absorbs radiation, and - the atmospheric lifetime of the gas. <p>Hence all gasses should be taken into consideration</p> <p>Provide the full breakdown of total GWP (with all contributions)</p>	<p>New CPR and harmonization of EN206</p> <p>Alignment between program operators for EPDs</p>
	O-CO-7	Alignment to Ecodesign regulation, which includes new Digital Product Passport	<p>Already ongoing process in new CPR</p> <p>Include in the product norms provisions concerning digital information</p> <p>Some possible references are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EN ISO 23386 (which provides information on the process) EN ISO 23387 (which provides the data structure) EN ISO 12006 	<p>Coordination with CEN/TC 442 activities</p> <p>Education and training to SMEs</p>

			(which provides the data model)	
Priority level n. 4	O-CO-3	EN 206 annex M provides guidance to existing provisions by place of use.	Harmonization of EN206 would remove this barrier. Promote the adoption of EPDs for each type of concrete	Accelerate diffusion of EPDs and online platforms
Priority level n. 5	O-CO-6	Ensure the availability of LCA information	An EPD is a standardized document describing the LCA results for a specific product without revealing this sensitive information. EPD should be the reference, being a fully recognized tool.	New CPR pushing EPDs as mandatory

4.3.1.4. Outcomes of specific meetings with Bulgarian stakeholders

Specific meetings were held with Bulgarian stakeholders by the AFCOS partner Cleantech, together with the activities held under tasks T2.2 and T2.3.

Bulgarian stakeholders identified the following challenges in relation to the standardization of low-carbon cement and low-carbon cement-based products.

- Lack of sufficient awareness and preparation on behalf of the participants in the construction process.
- Lack of a technical basis for the production of concrete in accordance with the new requirements (lack of a sufficient number of silos at the concrete producers).
- The higher price of low-carbon concrete compared to the concrete produced with ordinary Portland cement and fly ash.
However, related to this topic, the Bulgarian Association of the Cement Industry (BACI) identifies the problem of a lacking awareness among the stakeholders about the quality and price of new construction products. According to BACI low-carbon cements will not be more expensive than Portland cement, because the additives are not more expensive than the clinker that is used now. On this topic, BACI underlines the need to inform the participants in the construction process about these aspects.
- The lack of synchronization in the legislative framework (Public Procurement Law, etc.).
- The lack of state incentives at the national level that encourage the application of ecological construction products.
- The lack of constant control throughout the construction process for the implementation of the new requirements.
- To research what additives are used in innovative concretes.

- Need to test new construction products, to assess their quality and inform the stakeholders that new construction products have the required quality.
- BACI plans to carry out tests on low-carbon cements and concretes by the end of 2024. They will provide the results of the tests to inform the planned trainings on the AFCOS project.
- Need to include ecological requirements for the new construction products in the Public Procurement Act.
- Necessity of including low-carbon cements in standard EN 206 in Bulgarian National Annex.
- Trainings under the project should be aimed at all participants in the construction process, as well as at conformity assessors, assessors of construction products, bodies developing BTO, as well as at manufacturers of dry mixes
- Proposal to the EC - clarification of the term "Environmental construction product", which are the main indicators defining the product as ecological
- Proposal as an additional project activity to make a CWA simulation in the form of a working group including experts also from the EC.

4.3.2. Bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope

Also in the field of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope, after receiving the outcomes from the survey, new meetings with stakeholders were held, with the to identify the main legislation and standardization barriers preventing the market growth and to identify a list of actions that could overcome these barriers.

Specific meetings were held with Romanian stakeholders by the AFCOS partner ASRO, together with the activities held under tasks T2.2 and T2.3.

4.3.2.1. Identified barriers

First, a list of product categories has been developed. This categorization is based on the nature of the different products. The identified categories are the following.

- Products with vegetal origin:
 - Cellulose
 - Wood fiber
 - Cork
 - Grass
 - Flax
 - Jute
 - Sisal
 - Untreated chipped wood
 - Cotton fibres
 - Straw bales
 - Hemp fiber
 - Posidonia
- Products with animal origin:
 - Sheep wool

All these products can be used for thermal insulation purposes. Some of them also for acoustic and for fire insulation.

Among these products, only 3 hENs have been identified, referring to cork products, wood wool, and wood fibers.

All the other products categories **lack of hENs**. This complicates the procedures for manufacturers to prove their product conformity in order to apply CE marking. In this framework, the only possible way to CE mark is to use the EOTA path. However, at least from the point of view of Romanian stakeholders, this path is very difficult to follow for a small manufacturer due to the lack of proper budget and insufficient information. This is mainly due to the nature of the manufacturers of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope. In fact, at least at the Romanian level, manufacturers are small local entrepreneurs with limited resources and limited knowledge on standardization processes and policies.

Some **ISO standards** related to these products have been developed. However, these have been **not transposed at the European level** as EN, due to the lack of interest and consensus at the European level.

Another critical situation about this is related to the actual situation concerning major **blocking of EN standards for OJEU citation**. The ongoing revision of CPR 305/2011 will help solving this situation.

One more regulatory barrier related to these products concerns the **permits needed to collect raw materials**. For example, concerning the Posidonia-based products and for the specific case of Italy, collecting material on beaches requires a very complicated permitting process. Simplifying this could significantly help the growth of this market.

4.3.2.2. Proposed actions

The mostly shared action which could significantly improve the marketing of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope is to the **introduction of hENs for the CE marking** of the different products.

In this field, two different approaches have been identified:

1. introduce hENs for each of the products mentioned above;
2. introduce a general hENs valid for all the mentioned products.

No specific preference has been given among the two approaches. However, considering the large variety of products belonging to the bio-based category, introducing a general hENs could significantly help the market entrance of new products not belonging to the listed ones.

Another need expressed by stakeholders is related to the need for a **standard to define what is to be considered "bio-based"**. At present there are no clear rules to define it. There is often confusion between what is truly "bio-based" and what is simply of "natural origin".

Related to the introduction of a CE marking process for bio-based products, another proposed action is related to the need to consider mandatory the **introduction of sustainability parameters** in the product DOPs. These should include for example:

- a parameter to measure the carbon footprint of the specific product;
- the recyclability of the product; this could help distinguishing between 100% bio-based products (which are fully recyclable) and products based on mixtures between bio-based materials and synthetic materials (which are not recyclable).

5. Final considerations

5.1. Main considerations on the specific product families

In this deliverable document we often recalled the difference between the two analyzed product families. As it is fully described in Section 4.1, they have very different target markets. The market low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products is very large and well-established, while that of bio-based products for the insulation of the buildings' envelope has a much smaller turnover and still in its initial stages.

For these very reasons, the players involved in the two different groups are very different from each other. In the cement-based market the stakeholders are very large and with a strong awareness of what needs to

be done within a twin transition, while in the other case the subjects are much smaller and with less awareness and history behind them.

All this leads to very different needs in the two areas, which can be clearly seen in Sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2, where a significantly different degree of detail and richness of content is noticeable.

In the case of low carbon cement and low carbon cement-based products, we can basically say that the regulatory environment is clear, but it needs to be adapted to new requirements in terms of sustainability and digitization by adapting or merging existing standards. In the other case, the regulatory context is almost missing and all to be defined.

5.2. Results that can be used in a more general perspective

The above considerations are part of a rapidly advancing legislative/regulatory environment.

On the one hand, we have the new European CPR regulation, awaiting entry into force, as extensively described in Chapter 2. The new CPR allows us to accelerate toward timely production of new standards (e.g., biobased products) and faster standards adaptation (e.g., within standard EN196 with the inclusion of new materials).

Then we have the EPBD recast directive (EU/2024/1275), which mandates life-cycle approach for emissions, and requires the inclusion of global warming potential concepts that consider both embodied and operational carbon.

Last but not least, the European taxonomy, which mobilizes public and private capital toward more sustainable buildings with reduced GWP (EU Regulation EU/2020/852 and delegated acts 2021/2139 - 2023/2485 - 2023/2486).

All this helps to increase the technical capacity of the demand-side value chain and increase demand in financial terms so that investments in supply-side creation are fostered.

6. Towards WP3: guidelines for setting a roadmap for

The analysis performed under WP2 of the AFCOS project puts the grounds for the co-creation of the two roadmaps under WP3, which are the following:

- Roadmap 1: Standardization as enabler of innovation uptake in the new building materials field
- Roadmap 2: Capacity building in standardization of new building materials as a booster of new knowledge in industry

The roadmaps will be designed based on a methodology for co-design, which includes the active participation of the stakeholders and end users, as it is sketched in Figure 46.

Figure 46. Sketch of co-design methodology used to design roadmaps under WP3.

The initial phase of this process has been initiated as a part of the work in WP2 with the organization of stakeholder groups, which brought together policy authorities, business representatives and end-users (incl. from the construction sector, concrete and insulation producers, etc.), research and standardization bodies, academia. In profound sessions of brainstorming and debate, the stakeholders made the significant conclusions concerning the standardization and capacity building in the field of new construction products, which together with the findings from the survey will be the starting points in designing the roadmaps.

Thus, Roadmap 1 will outline the main steps for making the standardization process of new building products quicker and easier. Roadmap 2 will outline the main steps for boosting the understanding of the participants in the construction process about the new construction materials standards and their application. It will also discover the synergies with education and training providers like VET centres and universities.

The roadmaps will be validated by the stakeholders and tested with the industry representatives. The testing of the envisaged trainings regarding roadmap 2 is envisaged in WP 4. Finally, upon the collected feedback from testing, the roadmaps will be refined and presented to the respective authorities.

7. Annexes

Annex 1: STANDSRDS SELECTION_BDS_Annex 1

Annex 2: STANDSRDS SELECTION_BDS_Annex 2

8. Bibliography

- [1] «Construction Products Regulation (CPR, 305/2011),» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02011R0305-20210716>.
- [2] «Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011 (COM/2022/144 final),» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0144>.
- [3] «Directive on industrial emissions (integrated pollution prevention and control) (2010/75/EU),» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02010L0075-20110106>.
- [4] «Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24/11/2010 on industrial emissions and Council Directive 1999/31/EC of 26/4/1999 on the landfill of waste,» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0156>.
- [5] «Directive on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe (2008/50/EC),» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02008L0050-20150918>.
- [6] «Commission Implementing Decision on publication of the European Assessment Documents (EADs) for construction products drafted in support of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 (2019/450),» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02019D0450-20240117>.
- [7] «Commission Implementing Decision amending Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/450 as regards European Assessment Documents for internal partition kits for use as non-loadbearing walls, systems of mechanically fastened flexible roof waterproofing sheets, ...,» [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019D0896&qid=1709206497477>.
- [8] «Law on technical requirements for products (suppl. SG No.105/11 December 2020),» [Online]. Available: <https://lex.bg/bg/laws/ldoc/2134683136>.
- [9] «Law on Public Procurement (amend. SG No.11/6 February 2024),» [Online]. Available: <https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2136735703>.
- [10] «Ordinance № RD-02-20-1 of February 5, 2015, on the terms and conditions for use of construction products in the constructions of the Republic of Bulgaria,» [Online]. Available:

<https://lex.bg/en/laws/ldoc/2136447404>.

- [11] «Ordinance for the essential requirements to the constructions and the conformity assessment of construction products, (amend. SG No.60/22 July 2014),» [Online]. Available: <https://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135540641>.
- [12] «Draft ordinance on environmental requirements for certain products subject to public procurement,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.moew.government.bg/bg/proekt-na-naredba-za-ekologichnite-iziskvaniya-kum-opredeleni-produkti-predmet-na-obstestveni-poruchki/>.
- [13] «Ordinance on the management of construction waste and the use of recycled construction materials,» [Online]. Available: <https://lex.bg/bg/laws/ldoc/2137178691>.
- [14] «Order № RD-02-14-1329/3.12.2015 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works,» [Online]. Available: https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Laws/zapoved_rd_02_14_1320_2015.pdf.
- [15] «Order № RD-02-14-590/5.7.2017 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works,» [Online]. Available: <https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Zapoved590.pdf>.
- [16] «Order № RD-02-14-252/10.03.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works,» [Online]. Available: https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Zapovedi/Zapoved%20RD-02-14-252_10.03.2021.pdf.
- [17] «Order № RD-02-14-707/12.08.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Approves working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-2.1, ISSUE № 04 for Certification of the conformity of concrete with the national requirements,» [Online]. Available: https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Zapovedi/Z_RD_02_14_707_12_08_21_procwadura_beton_na_21.pdf.
- [18] «Order № RD-02-14-761/02.09.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Approves working procedure № RP-OSSPNI-3.17.1, edition № 01 for certification of conformity of starting mixtures for sprayed concrete and working procedure № RP-OSSP,» [Online]. Available: https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Zapovedi/ZAPOVED_RD_02_14_761_02.09.2021.pdf.
- [19] «Order № RD-02-14-1169/30.11.2022 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works,» [Online]. Available: https://cpcp.mrrb.government.bg/cms/assets/Zapovedi/Zapoved%20RD_02_14_1169_30.11.2022_nac.%20iziskv.BG.pdf.
- [20] «Regulations on labor safety in the production of cement,» [Online]. Available: <https://zbut.eu/bulgarianlaw/pravilnik-po-bezopasnostta-na-truda-pri-proizvodstvoto-na-tsiment/>.
- [21] *Ordinance on the management of the construction waste and on the use of recycled building materials adopted with Decree No. 267 of 05.12.2017 and Prom. SG. 98/8 Dec 2017.*
- [22] *Working Procedure № RP-OSSPNI-2.1, ISSUE № 04 for Certification of the conformity of concrete with the national requirements, approved by Order № RD-02-14-707/12.08.2021 of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works.*
- [23] «Legea nr. 163/2015 privind standardizarea națională,» [Online]. Available: https://www.asro.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Lege-nr163_2015.pdf.
- [24] «MINISTERUL DEZVOLTĂRII, LUCRĂRILOR PUBLICE ȘI ADMINISTRAȚIEI - Standarde armonizate,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdipa.ro/pages/standardearmonizate>.

- [25] «GHID PRIVIND PROIECTAREA S1 EXECUTIA ACOPERISURILOR VERZI LA CLADIRI NOI S1 EXISTENTE, INDICATIV GP 120-2013,» [Online]. Available: https://www.mdpa.ro/userfiles/reglementari/Domeniul_VIII/VIII_5_GP_120_2013.pdf.
- [26] «CE MARKING OF CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS STEP BY STEP,» [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/12308/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/nat iv>.
- [27] «EOTA EADs,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.eota.eu/eads>.
- [28] «EOTA TABs,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.eota.eu/tabs>.
- [29] «Webinar 'The functioning of the HAS system, interactions with HAS consultants and best practices',» [Online]. Available: https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/Events/Webinars/2023/2023-05-16_webinar_ey-cen-clc-ec_functioning-has-system.pdf.
- [30] «Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Regulation (EU) 305/2011,» [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/49315>.
- [31] «Sustainable Construction: Low-Carbon Concrete,» [Online]. Available: <https://work-on-progress.strabag.com/en/carbon-emissions/low-carbon-concrete>.
- [32] «CEN/TC 104 - Concrete and related products,» [Online]. Available: https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0::::FSP_ORG_ID:6087&cs=1EF017FD28A2CA7FB8DFED121D7045B7E.
- [33] «CEN/TC 125 - Masonry,» [Online]. Available: https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0::::FSP_ORG_ID:6107&cs=1F7108A312D95152BE38F24E33EEC4D84.
- [34] «CEN/TC 229 - Precast concrete products,» [Online]. Available: https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0::::FSP_ORG_ID:6210&cs=105CCA49576828F3F356391A4D4C12BAE.
- [35] «ISO/TC 265 - Carbon dioxide capture, transportation, and geological storage,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/committee/648607.html>.
- [36] «ISO/TC 59 Buildings and civil engineering works,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.iso.org/committee/49070.html>.
- [37] «Bio-based products and processes,» [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bio-based-products-and-processes_en#:~:text=Bio%2Dbased%20products%20are%20derived,%2C%20biogenic%20CO2%2C%20etc..
- [38] «Harmonised standards ASRO,» [Online]. Available: [https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr/harmonised-standards_en#:~:text=Harmonised%20European%20standards%20create%20a,\(design%20engineers%2C%20contractors\)](https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr/harmonised-standards_en#:~:text=Harmonised%20European%20standards%20create%20a,(design%20engineers%2C%20contractors)).
- [39] «European Commission standardisation requests,» [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/>.
- [40] «CEN-CENELEC guidance – Core rules for drafting hEN for construction products,» [Online]. Available: https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/AreasOfWork/CEN%20sectors/Construction/Quicklinks/Guides/cen-clc-guidance_core-

rules-for-hens.pdf .

- [41] «List of Commission implementing decisions under the CPR,» [Online]. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/search.html?SUBDOM_INIT=ALL_ALL&LB=32011R0305&DTS_SUBDOM=ALL_ALL&DTS_DOM=ALL&lang=en&type=advanced&qid=1711708324641&SELECT=LB_DISPLAY.
- [42] «Webinar 'Harmonized standards under CPR',» [Online]. Available: https://www.cencenelec.eu/media/CEN-CENELEC/Events/Webinars/2023/2023-06-29_webinar_hens_under_cpr.pdf.
- [43] «Revision of the Construction Products Regulation,» [Online]. Available: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/739243/EPRS_BRI\(2022\)739243_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/739243/EPRS_BRI(2022)739243_EN.pdf).
- [44] «European Parliament resolution of 10 March 2021 on the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 305/2011 laying down harmonised conditions for the marketing of construction products (the Construction Products Regulation),» [Online]. Available: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2021-0074_EN.html.
- [45] «Review of the Construction Products Regulation,» [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr/review_en.
- [46] «European assessment documents and European technical assessments,» [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/construction/construction-products-regulation-cpr/european-assessment-documents-and-european-technical-assessments_en#:~:text=The%20European%20assessment%20document%20.
- [47] «aid4greenest,» [Online]. Available: <https://aid4greenest.eu/aid4greenest-presentations/>.
- [48] «Jobs and economy,» [Online]. Available: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/jobs-and-economy_en.
- [49] «Cembureau: Cementing the European Green Deal, Reaching Climate Neutrality along the Cement and Concrete Value Chain by 2050. Cembureau – The European Cement Association, 12.05.2020, Brussels/».
- [50] «Harder. J.: Next-generation carbon capture technologies for cement industries. ZKG Cement Lime Gypsum 6-2022, pp. 38-47».
- [51] «Cembureau: Key facts and Figures. June 2023, Cembureau – The European Cement Association, Brussels/Belgium».
- [52] «Bulgaria Cement Industry Market Size & Forecast by Value and Volume Across 50+ Market Segments by Cement Products, Distribution Channel, Market Share, Import Export, End Markets – Q2 2023 Update,» [Online]. Available: [marketresearch.com](https://www.marketresearch.com).
- [53] «Bulgaria Cement Market (2024-2030) | Trends, Outlook & Forecast,» [Online]. Available: [6wresearch.com](https://www.6wresearch.com).
- [54] «Home - BACI,» [Online]. Available: [bacibg.org](https://www.bacibg.org).
- [55] «Total production and sold production in volume and value terms | National statistical institute,» [Online]. Available: [nsi.bg](https://www.nsi.bg).
- [56] «Pavel, C, Balogeva, D. Competitive landscape of the EU's insulation materials industry for energy-efficient building, JRC 2018».
- [57] «Thermoinsulating materials market in Romania – 2024 edition,» Neomar, [Online]. Available:

<https://neomar.eu/en/portfolio/thermoinsulating-materials-market-in-romania-2017-2023-2/>.

- [58] «Cod CAEN 2351 Fabricarea cimentului,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.coduricaen.ro/2351-fabricarea-cimentului>.
- [59] «Cod CAEN: Fabricarea altor produse din minerale nemetalice, n.c.a. 2399,» [Online]. Available: <https://coduricaen.info/definitie-Fabricarea-altor-produse-din-minerale-nemetalice-n-c-a-2399.html>.
- [60] «Building Thermal Insulation Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Product (Glass Wool, Mineral Wool, EPS, XPS, Cellulose), By Application (Roof, Walls, Floor), By End-use,By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2023 - 2030,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/building-thermal-insulation-market>.
- [61] «Cement industry of India: outlook and challenges,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.infomercials.com/admin/uploads/Cement-Industry-Report-May2023.pdf>.
- [62] «Concrete solutions for a greener cement industry,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.swecogroup.com/topical/industry/concrete-solutions-for-a-greener-cement-industry/>.
- [63] «PRODPROM DATA BY PRODUCT SUBCATEGORIES OF THE CLASSIFICATION OF PRODUCTS BY ACTIVITY (CPA.BG-VER.2.1) - 2022 YEAR,» [Online]. Available: <https://www.nsi.bg/en/content/1227/total-production-and-sold-production-volume-and-value-terms>.